

**A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON THE
INTERACTION AND SOLUBILIZATION OF
SOME HYDROPHOBIC DRUGS IN
AMPHIPHILIC TRIBLOCK COPOLYMERS**

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CERTIFICATE

The work included in the thesis entitled "**A Comprehensive Study on the Interaction and Solubilization of Some Hydrophobic Drugs in Amphiphilic Triblock Copolymers**" submitted to the Faculty of **Sciences**, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, for the degree of **Doctor of Philosophy**, was carried out by **Mr. Pankaj Singla** at the Department of **Chemistry**, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, under my supervision. This is an original work and has not been submitted in part or full for any other degree/diploma at this or any other University/Institute. This thesis is fit to be considered for evaluation and award of degree of Ph.D.

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the thesis entitled "**A Comprehensive Study on the Interaction and Solubilization of Some Hydrophobic Drugs in Amphiphilic Triblock Copolymers**" submitted to the Faculty of **Sciences**, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, for the award of Ph.D degree is entirely my own work and not submitted elsewhere for the award of any other degree. All the ideas and references have been duly acknowledged.

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List of Abbreviations

A	Absorbance
N_{agg}	Aggregation number
N_A	Avogadro's number
n_s	Average number of drug molecules solubilized per micelles
k_a	Binding constant
k_B	Boltzmann constant
CLZ	Clozapine
R_c	Correlation coefficient
cmc	Critical micelle concentration
cmt	Critical micelle temperature
cac	Critical aggregation concentration
β	Degree of counter ion binding
D ₂ O	Deuterium oxide
DLS	Dynamic light scattering
DPV	Differential pulse voltammetry
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FTIR	Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy
D_h	Hydrodynamic diameter
HLB	Hydrophilic- lipophilic balance
HPLC	High performance liquid chromatography
HTM	Heat Transfer Method
IL	Ionic liquid
ITC	Isothermal titration calorimetry
LAM	Lamotrigine
α	Mole fraction

OXC	Oxcarbazepine
$^1\text{HNMR}$	Proton Nuclear magnetic resonance
P	Partition coefficient
PXRD	Powder X-ray diffraction
QCT	Quercetin
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
a	Semi-major axis
b	Semi-minor axis
SANS	Small angle neutron scattering
SDC	Sodium deoxycholate
ΔG°	Standard free energy
SAIL	Surface active ionic liquid
T	Temperature
R	Universal gas constant
λ	Wavelength
ζ	Zeta potential

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 General Introduction

Amphiphiles are surface active agents which lower the surface or interfacial tension between two liquids, between a gas and a liquid or between a liquid and a solid and self-assemble into different types of molecular structures that are physically associated. Amphiphiles exhibit a multitude of applications in daily routine such as in detergency: laundry detergents, dishwasher detergents; wetting: toothpaste; foaming: shampoos, hand soaps and bath products; emulsification and stabilization of dispersions such as in ice-creams. Moreover from technological point of view, amphiphiles are being utilized in textiles, petrochemical industries, coating, paint additives, food processing, pharmaceutical, biochemical industries, agrochemicals and drug delivery.¹⁻⁹ Amphiphiles commonly known as surfactants (a short form of surface active agents), show “dual affinity” because of their molecular characteristics which is composed of a polar hydrophilic part “head” and non-polar hydrophobic moiety known as “tail”. The dual affinity of the amphiphiles gives rise to some remarkable properties in the aqueous solution like adsorption at air/water interfaces, formation of self-assembled structures and solubilization of hydrophobic molecules such as oil, hydrophobic solute and drugs etc.¹⁰ The headgroup of amphiphiles can either be ionic (charged) or non-ionic (non-charged), categorizing them into cationic (positively charged), anionic (negatively charged) or zwitter ionic (both positively and negatively charged) surfactants respectively.

When a surfactant goes into aqueous solution, the relatively large hydrophobic tail then breaks the hydrogen bonding between the water molecules, resulting in increase in free energy of system and disturbing the caged structure of water. In this situation, water molecules oust the surfactant molecules from the bulk in the direction of air-water interface, where the adsorption of hydrophilic head groups takes place at the water phase and the hydrophobic tail orient towards the air phase (**Figure 1.1a**). Afterwards, the entire air-water interface becomes saturated with surfactant molecules

resulting in the formation of a densely packed monolayer (**Figure 1.1b**). Following the completion of adsorption, the surfactant molecules have to come in the aqueous medium and due to the unfavorable interactions of hydrophobic part and water molecules, hydrophobic part of the surfactant gather and try to form hydrophobic domain. However, the hydrophilic part of the surfactant is compatible with the water molecules, so they entangle in the aqueous medium and forming a structure that is spherical in shape containing hydrophobic core and hydrophilic shell structure (**Figure 1.1c**). Such structures known as “micelles” and the specific concentration at which they are formed called as “critical micelle concentration” (*cmc*).^{11,12} Surfactants can form different type of structures such as micelles: spherical, rods, prolates, ellipsoids, disc, worm like micelles; reverse micelles which may contain various phases such as hexagonal, cubic, lamellar, cage *etc*; vesicles; microtubules; liposomes and bilayers.^{13,14}

Figure 1.1 Schematic representation of micelle formation in surfactants.

There are various factors that can affect the *cmc* of surfactants including the molecular characteristics of surfactants, such as nature of head group, length of hydrophobic group; experimental factors including pH, temperature, ionic strength and presence of additives *etc*.¹⁵ The mixture of surfactants have excellent colloidal and interfacial characteristics as compared to individual components, so have wide number of practical applications such as solubilization and delivery of hydrophobic drugs, removal of the contaminants from waste water *etc*.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

Poloxomers are commercially available ABA type triblock copolymers, consists of polyethylene oxide (PEO) and polypropylene oxide (PPO) units arranged in a PEO-

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PPO-PEO structure.^{19,20} The synthesis of poloxomers was reported in 1950s, since from that date they are broadly known as pluronics. They offer a pool of more than 50 amphiphilic molecules that are water soluble and show polymorphism. The first letter of each pluronic represent their physical state: L, P and F for liquid, paste, and flake respectively, represented in **Figure 1.2** named as “Pluronic grid” system.^{21,22} The first one or two numbers are referred to the molecular weight of the PPO block (factor of 300 can be multiplied to obtain molecular weight of PPO units) for example pluronic P84= PPO molecular weight:2400, and the last number signifies the one-tenth of the molecular weight percentage of PEO content per unimers. As an example, P84 and P85 both are pastes, having the different molar weight percentage of PEO units, 40% for P84 and 50% for P85 with same PPO units. However, grid system is generally used to estimate the PEO and PPO content of the pluronics.

Figure 1.2 Pluronic PEO-PPO-PEO copolymers arranged in the "Pluronic grid". The copolymers along the vertical lines have the same PPO/PEO composition ratio, while the copolymers along the horizontal lines have PPO blocks of the same length.

The blocks of the pluronic contain both hydrophilic PEO blocks and more hydrophobic PPO blocks enable them to form the micelles. There are two methods involved in pluronic micelles formation by increasing the concentration of pluronic at or above the *cmc*, or by increasing temperature of the pluronic solution until the critical micelle temperature (*cmt*) which results in decrease of *cmc* as depicted in **Figure 1.3**. The change in hydrophilic–lipophilic balance (HLB) of the pluronic copolymers depends upon the length of the blocks.

Figure 1.3 Schematic of micelles formation of pluronics in aqueous medium.

Pluronic have gained attention over the conventional block copolymers because they have enormous properties such as high surface-active, low-toxicity, low immunogenicity with excellent biocompatibility and biodegradability. Pluronic have extensive industrial applications in dispersion as stabilizing agents, foaming, emulsifiers, lubrication, cosmetics and detectable inks etc., along with number of pharmaceutical applications such as drug solubilization including proteins, growth factors, gene and their controlled release, nano-medicine and artificial skin for burn wounds, artificial blood formulations, tissue engineering, in bioseparation and bioprocessing (protecting microalgae against damage associated with shear stress).²³⁻³²

Another important class of bio-surfactants known as bile salts; are present in ionic form at physiological conditions and amphipathic in nature. Bile salts are obtained from cholic acid and the end products of cholesterol. The synthesis of bile salts occurs in the liver and released into the intestinal lumen where they incorporate cholesterol and other hydrophobic compounds facilitating their gastrointestinal absorption. Hydrophilic

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groups are attached to the hydrophobic tetracyclic steroid ring system; and they are ranging from one to three hydroxyl (OH) groups and one acidic group. The structure of the bile salts is very different from the classical amphiphiles. The polar hydroxyl groups are oriented to the concave side of the rigid steroid ring system, which is thus rendered hydrophilic, while the convex side is hydrophobic. Bile salts have a facial structure with a hydrophobic side and a hydrophilic side or, depending on the position and orientation of the hydroxyl groups, a hydrophilic 'edge' only. Furthermore, the hydrophobic tails of common amphiphiles are liquid-like inside the micellar core, whereas the steroid ring system is very rigid. This rigidity often results in an incomplete separation of the hydrophilic and hydrophobic domains in aggregates; some hydrophobic moieties may remain in contact with water and hydrophilic parts might be buried within micelles.³³ The combination of tight junctions, an endothelial cell membrane with high lateral packing density and the expression of efflux transporters severely limits drug transport across the blood brain barrier (BBB). The ability of the bile salts to influence transfer of solute molecules across the gastrointestinal membrane has been extensively exploited as permeation enhancer to increase the drug transport across biological barriers. Bile salts facilitated the drug transport in biological membranes through both paracellular and transcellular pathways. Recent studies suggest that bile salts are also able to permeate the blood brain barrier (BBB) via modulating membrane fluidity and surface charge.³⁴⁻³⁶ Bile salts are also used in bacterial pathogenesis because of their antimicrobial properties, escalation of the surface area and bioavailability of drugs, binding of heavy metal and formation of biofilm.³⁷⁻³⁹ These unique properties of the bile salts make them the good carrier for the drug delivery, mixed micelles of these bile salts with the non ionic pluronic copolymers can be prepared to improve their drug loading capacity, stability etc.

Besides, ionic liquids (ILs) have also emerged as potential alternative for replacing traditional surfactants because of their intrinsic amphiphilicity and exceptional physicochemical properties such as high ionic conductivity, negligible vapor pressure and non-flammability.⁴⁰⁻⁴³ They are used as solvents and/or materials in the fields of pharmaceutical drug delivery and active pharmaceutical ingredient formulation because of their unique and tunable physicochemical and biological

properties. The ILs having long chain cations are amphiphilic and are known as surface active ionic liquids (SAILs). The appropriate design ability of ILs is the most unique feature as their physicochemical characteristics can be easily modified by simply changing the cation or anion.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁷

About 40% of drugs in the market and nearly 90% of molecules in the new drug development pipeline have minimal water solubility. The poor solubility of hydrophobic drugs can lead to low bioavailability that result in suboptimal drug delivery. Several attempts have been made by many pharmaceutical companies to reformulate the hydrophobic drugs in order to enhance their water solubility, bioavailability, efficacy with targeted drug delivery.^{48,49} The polymeric micelles constituted by hydrophobic-hydrophilic (PPO-PEO) block copolymers have gained utmost attraction as drug carriers in terms of their size and architecture. Several PEO-PPO block copolymers act as thermo-viscosifying materials as approved by FDA (Food and Drug Administration) and US EPA (United States Environmental Protection Agency) and being used as pharmaceutical ingredients, direct and indirect food additives and agricultural products. The poly(ethylene oxide) is the common structural unit present on surfaces of almost all the circulating systems including nanoparticles, liposomes, or micelles. The particles remain 'unrecognizable' by reticulo-endothelial system (RES) due to the presence of dynamic PEO chains, also prevent particle opsonization. The advantages of polymeric micellar drug delivery systems over other types of drug carriers include: **a)** long circulation time in blood stream; **b)** appropriate size (10-30 nm) to escape renal excretion but to allow for the extravasation at the target site; and **c)** simplicity in drug incorporation, compared to covalent bonding of the drug to the polymeric carrier.⁵⁰

The capacity of PEO-coated particles to prevent the adsorption of proteins and cells relies on the surface density of PEO chains, their length and dynamics.^{51,52} However only a few known block copolymers form micelles in aqueous solutions. Among them, AB-type block copolymers, e.g. poly(L-amino acid)-block poly(ethylene oxide) and ABA-type triblock copolymers, pluronic gained special attention.⁵³⁻⁶⁰ The solubilization of drugs in pluronic micelles in aqueous solutions has been extensively investigated by many authors and was recently reviewed by Bodratti and

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Alexandridis.⁶¹ The encapsulation of drugs into pluronic block copolymer micelles may be accomplished through chemical and physical routes. However, chemical routes include covalent interaction of the drug to the hydrophobic block of the copolymer whereas the loading of drugs into the polymeric micelles can be better by physical entrapment.

In the present thesis, we mainly focused on conventional surface active agents such as pluronic triblock copolymer and their mixture with bile salts and surface active ionic liquids (SAILs) to explore the solubilization of antiepileptic, antipsychotic and anticancer hydrophobic drugs. To estimate the solubilization capacity and *in vitro* drug release of various hydrophobic drugs in different surfactant micelles, UV-visible spectroscopy has been employed. Steady state fluorescence spectroscopy has been used to determine the *cmc* values of amphiphilic micelles. The solubilization locus of these drugs is studied by various techniques such as proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹H NMR), high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV). The compatibility between the drugs and amphiphilics is determined by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD), fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The morphological characteristics of unloaded and loaded micelles are identified by dynamic light scattering (DLS), Heat Transfer Method (HTM) and small angle neutron scattering (SANS) measurements.

1.2 Review of Literature

In past years, a number of scientific reports have been published to modify the micellar characteristics of pluronics in the presence of different ionic surfactants such as bile-salts, surface active ionic liquids (SAILs) to achieve the desired solubilization of hydrophobic drugs for the drug delivery system. A brief survey of literature highlighting the physicochemical aspects of solubilization of different hydrophobic drugs in different pluronic micelles, pluronic-bile salts and pluronic-SAILs mixed micelles is presented here.

Bharatiya and co workers investigated the encapsulation of two poorly water soluble drugs, aspirin and 5-methyl salicylate in the pluronic P123, P103 and P105

micelles with variations in their total molecular weight and block contribution.⁶² The micellar characteristics and changes in size during the encapsulation of drugs aspirin and 5-methyl salicylate in the pluronic micelles have been observed by exploring dynamic light scattering (DLS), dynamic surface tension (DST), small angle neutron scattering (SANS) and proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) measurements. The DLS results showed that loading of 5-methyl salicylate results in the significant increase in micellar size of pluronic micelles while aspirin exhibit modest changes on the final morphology. DST measurements revealed that solubilization of drugs within the pluronic micelles alter the diffusivity of the monomers due to stronger hydrophobic interactions leading to the formation of highly stable aggregates. The SANS measurements indicated the formation of ellipsoidal micelles for aqueous solutions of P123/P103 at higher concentration of 5-methyl salicylate whereas spherical micelles were evident in presence of aspirin. ¹H NMR results showed the strong hydrophobic interactions of 5-methyl salicylate with existing pluronic P123 micelles by dehydrating the PPO core, however no change in chemical shift was observed in case of drug aspirin and P105 micelles. These results emphasized that the solubilization has been governed by the partition coefficient of drug and hydrophobic nature of the pluronics.

Prescott *et al.* studied the uptake and release of hydrophobic drug flurbiprofen in the different pluronic micelles viz. P103, P123 and L43 at various pH by using SANS, surface tension measurements and pulsed-field gradient stimulated-echo nuclear magnetic resonance.⁶³ The aggregation behaviour of the three pluronic copolymers in the absence of drug was pH-independent. However, the addition of a weakly acidic drug led to the change in the aggregation behaviour. At pH below the pKa value of flurbiprofen drug, an increase in the aggregation number, core radius, and the fraction of micellization of the pluronic micelles has been observed. Upon increasing the pH of the flurbiprofen above the pKa value, a notable quantity of drug was released from the pluronic micelles into the solution, which led to increase in *cmc/cac* (critical aggregation concentration) ratio. The drug and pluronic micelles showed increase in diffusion coefficients and decrease in scattering values at low Q region. The behaviour of pluronic L43 was found to be very different as compared to pluronic P123 and P103. The presence of flurbiprofen led to 35% increase in the fraction of pluronic micellized

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at low pH. But at higher pH values, the complete breakdown of pluronic micelles occurred that subsequently result in burst flurbiprofen release. Authors emphasized that L43 micelles can serve as efficient drug delivery vehicle than other investigated P103 and P123 micelles, as L43 micelles release entire flurbiprofen drug into solution.

In another report, Prescott *et al.* explored the effect of flurbiprofen drug addition, cosolvent and temperature on the pluronic micellization using SANS measurements.⁶⁴ The data evidenced that presence of ethanol resulted in the increase in the *cmc* values and affected the formation of polymeric micelles as well. They also studied the effect of addition of flurbiprofen drug to the pluronic micelles in the concentration dependent manner. The scattering pattern obtained from SANS measurements revealed the attractive interactions and the morphological change in the micelles at higher flurbiprofen concentrations (1% w/v). The scattering pattern showed that fraction of polymeric micellization, higher aggregation number, core radius and dehydration of micellar core resulted in the enhanced scattering intensity as a function of temperature increase. At 10°C and 15°C, the unloaded polymers existed mainly as unimers but the *cmc* of the micelles get altered in the presence of drug. For pluronic P103, an increase of 25% and 40% in the fraction micellization was observed with the addition of 0.5 wt % of drug at 10°C and 15°C respectively. Authors suggested that some important factors such as effect of various environmental conditions including the presence of cosolvent, temperature and hydrophobic species including drug molecules, impurities and hydrophobicity of pluronics must be considered carefully for clinical or industrial applications.

Terekhova *et al.* illustrated the solubilization behaviour of three antirheumatic drugs; methotrexate, leflunomide and sulfasalazine in the pluronic F127 micelles by employing UV-visible spectroscopy, ¹H NMR, 2D ROESY (rotating-frame nuclear overhauser effect correlation spectroscopy) NMR and DLS techniques.⁶⁵ The solubility pattern of drug in pluronics follows the order leflunomide > sulfasalazine > methotrexate. Authors observed that the size and ionization state of the different drugs played a crucial role in the interaction with the F127 micelles. The higher solubilization of leflunomide in F127 micelles can be attributed to small geometrical dimensions and higher hydrophobic nature of this drug. ¹H NMR and ROESY NMR measurements

confirmed that only leflunomide drug penetrated inside the core of F127 micelle. Membrane permeability effect of pluronic F127 was carried out using Permeapad™ barrier (acted as the model of intestinal membranes), showed the reduced permeability which was a result of solubilization of drug in pluronic F127 micelles.

Yuksel *et al.* probed the solubilization of hydrophobic anticancer drugs, octaethylporphine, meso-tetraphenyl porphine (mTPP) and camptothecin, in pluronic *viz.* F127, F68, P85 and polyethylene glycol–distearoylphosphatidylethanolamine (PEG-DSPE) *viz.* PEG₇₅₀-DSPE, PEG₂₀₀₀-DSPE and PEG₅₀₀₀-DSPE micelles.⁶⁶ Prepared formulations were assessed by different parameters such as micellar size and distribution, zeta (ζ) potential, *cmc* values, loading efficiency and stability. The investigated polymers formed very stable and smaller sized (less than 100 nm) micelles with low *cmc* values. Drug loading efficiency in these micelles was highly dependent on the polymer type, drug type and their mixing ratios. The best drug loading was obtained in case of solubilization of mTPP drug in PEG₂₀₀₀-DSPE and pluronic F127 micelles. These results can be attributed to the presence of phenyl groups in drug mTPP that led to attraction between alkyl groups in the polymer and increase drug loading. PEG-DSPE formulations had higher zeta potential values than pluronic micelles revealed that PEG-DSPE would be more stable against aggregation. But stability test showed enhanced stability of pluronic micelles than PEG–DSPE formulations for a period of 3 months in both lyophilized and aqueous forms.

Gradzielski and co-workers studied the solubilization of two active ingredients of different polarity, carbamazepine and fenofibrate, in different pluronic micelles.⁶⁷ A substantial increase of solubilization of the less polar fenofibrate was observed using pluronics with sufficiently long PPO blocks as those have a *cmt* lower than 25°C, while shorter PPO blocks showed higher *cmt* and therefore less tendency for micelle formation and solubilization. In contrast, only a small enhancement of solubilization for the more polar carbamazepine was observed that somewhat depends on the type of polymer employed. This could be explained such that carbamazepine solubilization was mostly affected by the lowering of the chemical potential of the solvent (as one observes the same effect upon the addition of PEO homopolymer), which was due to the presence of the polymer and presumably by specific interactions between

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carbamazepine and PEO and PPO in solution. Such a pronounced interaction may be ascribed to the strong dipoles of the PEO and PPO units that interact synergistically with the carbamazepine molecule. However, there was also some additional enhancement of solubilization for pluronics forming micelles, which indicates that about the same amount of carbamazepine that is additionally contained in solution due to the changed chemical potential is also solubilized by incorporation within the micelles. In general, one observes that the solubility of the active ingredients increases in a fashion directly proportional to the amount of dissolved polymer, but much more pronouncedly for fenofibrate. For fenofibrate longer-chain pluronics showed a significantly better solubilization than their lower molecular weight counterparts, while for carbamazepine only a small dependence on the pluronic architecture was observed. By combining SANS, PFG-NMR and NOESY experiments they achieved a detailed insight into the different solubilization mechanisms of fenofibrate and carbamazepine which they detailed for the case of Pluronic PE 10400. These experiments yield a consistent picture, in which fenofibrate was exclusively solubilized within the PPO core leading to a corresponding enhancement of the micelle size (as seen by SANS and PFG-NMR). In contrast, carbamazepine did not show such a pronounced interaction with the pluronic micelles and diffuses effectively almost as free molecules. This was in agreement with the observed strong dependence of the solubilization capacity of fenofibrate on the pluronic structure, whereas the solubilization of carbamazepine was increasing to a much lesser extent. PFGNMR experiments showed no separate micellar diffusion of carbamazepine, as apparently it exchanges quickly within the solution between bound and free state, and accordingly diffuses rapidly. Similarly the NOESY experiments showed exclusive interactions of the fenofibrate with the PPO core, while carbamazepine interacted with PEO and PPO in a similar fashion. Obviously the polarity and molecular structure of the solubilized drug molecule has a large effect on its interaction with the pluronic molecules and thereby on the solubilization mechanism. All these points therefore have to be considered accordingly when optimizing such formulations for solubilization.

Dar *et al.* used different techniques *viz.* DLS, SANS, and rheology to investigate the aggregation characteristics of pluronic P123 in ethanol-water mixed solvents in the

presence lavender oil.⁶⁸ As the concentration of pluronic P123 was increased, the formulation of pluronic P123 also showed enhanced solubilization capacity toward lavender oil. The study revealed that short chain alcohol-ethanol serves as important solubilization enhancer. An increase in lavender oil concentration resulted in significant increase in apparent hydrodynamic radius (R_h) at a particular ethanol concentration. The DLS study was performed for different concentrations of pluronic P123 viz. 5, 10, and 15 wt% in the presence of 25% ethanol, showed the existence of large sized micellar clusters other than the presence of oil swollen micelles. The SANS measurement showed the enhancement of hard sphere radius (R_{HS}), core size (R_C), and aggregation number (N) on addition of lavender oil, which confirmed the oil penetration inside the copolymer. Rheological data showed a significant increase in the viscosity on lavender oil addition up to the maximum loading capacity of pluronic P123. Further with increase in oil concentration, a linear decrease in sol-gel transition temperature was observed, which have a great dependency on both P123 as well as oil concentration.

Cosgrove and coworkers employed the pulsed-field gradient stimulated-echo NMR to determine the aggregation behaviour of pluronic copolymers P103, P104 and P105, in the presence of ibuprofen.⁶⁹ The two diffusion rates displayed by pluronic copolymers corresponding to the unimer and the micelle, suggested the slow polymer exchange process between the micelle and solution on NMR time scale. The increase in the hydrophobicity of the pluronic led to the increase in the pluronic micelles size at 25°C, whereas the hydrodynamic radius of the unimer was associated with the unimer chain length. The overall decrease in the pH from 7.5 to 4.5 and an increase in the hydrodynamic radius (R_h) of the micelles from 57.7 to 102.3Å have been observed in pluronic P104 micellar solution upon the addition of ibuprofen drug. The presence of ibuprofen also promoted the micellization of the pluronics which results in increase in the fraction of polymer micellized. The aggregation characteristics of pluronic P104 showed little pH-dependence on the variation of pH, with an exception P104, which showed increased micellization at high alkaline pH which can be related to decrease in solubility of poly-ethylene oxide (PEO) in alkaline solutions. However, ibuprofen loaded pluronic micelles displayed a stronger dependency on pH. As the pH was increased above the pKa of the ibuprofen drug, a considerable amount of drug was

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being released from the pluronic micelle which was attributed to the substantial increase in water solubility of ionized form of ibuprofen. Thus release of ibuprofen from pluronic micelles could be tuned by varying physiological pH.

Grillo *et al.* investigated loading of seven essential oils and some synthetic pure molecules in pluronics F127 micelles with differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), small-angle X-ray (SAXS) and SANS studies.⁷⁰ The study evidenced the involvement of different interaction mechanisms between oils and pluronic monomers revealed by various insertion and swelling behaviours for the different oil molecules. The enhanced release of water molecules led to increase in micellization enthalpy upon addition of oil which led to decrease in *cmt* of micellar system. Morphologically, SANS results demonstrated the existence of large aggregates with oil at temperature lower than *cmt*, at which their size is maximal. The decrease in size above the *cmt* was found and the equilibrium was reached a few degrees after the temperature corresponding to the maximum of the endothermic peak. The combined results of SANS and SAXS evidenced the partial phase separation between the oil and the PPO core at 37 °C. However the PEO, the hydrophilic stabilizing shell remains unchanged.

Ganguly *et al.* investigated the aggregation behaviour of pluronics in an aqueous medium influenced by methyl paraben (MP) and butyl paraben (BP) using DLS, SANS, viscometry and fluorescence measurement techniques.⁷¹ The use of parabens as preservative in cosmetic, pharmaceutical, and food products is well known. This study demonstrated the influence of parabens on interaction and micellar growth which depend on their aqueous solubility and also on the pluronic compositions. The presence of MP in case of P105 and P104 resulted in the reduction of sphere-to-rod transition temperature to room temperature and induced the micellar growth at room temperature whereas the suppression the micellar growth in the presence of BP resulted in the formation of micellar cluster due to the commencement of intermicellar attractive interaction. However the presence of both the MP and BP in case of more hydrophobic pluronic P103 resulted in the induction of sphere-to-rod micellar growth at room temperature, which was not found in the presence of water structure making salts like NaCl and Na₃PO₄. These results have been explained by the fact that the different

locations of parabens within the micellar corona region modulate the growth and restructuring processes of the pluronic micelles.

Dabrowski *et al.* prepared and studied the pluronic (P123, F127) formulation of redaporfin (a fluorinated sulfonamide bacteriochlorin, F₂BMet or LUZ11) in order to improve the therapeutic efficacy of photodynamic therapy (PDT).⁷² Both, the unloaded and redaporfin loaded pluronic micelles did not show any cytotoxicity in a broad concentration range. The *in vitro* studies for redaporfin-P123 micelles were performed in B16F10 melanoma cells, showed the increased cellular uptake with increased oxidative stress as compared to redaporfin-F127 pluronic micelles or photosensitizer alone after particular incubation times. The production of hydroxyl radicals that is responsible for the increased oxidative stress, apoptosis and necrosis was observed by reactive oxygen species (ROS) sensitive fluorescent probes. The bioavailability of the redaporfin loaded pluronic P123 formulation was increased in tumor-bearing mice as compared to cremophor EL and pluronic F127 formulations. The PDT of C57BL/6J mice bearing B16F10 cells was found to be most successful in case of redaporfin loaded P123 micelles. The 100% complete cures were observed when Vascular-targeted PDT with 1.5 mg kg⁻¹ redaporfin in P123 pluronic micelles with a light dose was given. These phenomenal results demonstrated that redaporfin loaded pluronic micelles can overcome the existing problems like resistance of melanoma cells to PDT possibly via increased ROS generation and enhanced tumor selective treatment.

Hassan *et al.* probed the interaction between triblock copolymer pluronic P123 and anionic surfactant Aerosol OT (AOT) with the help of DLS and SANS measurements.⁷³ The study on copolymer/surfactant system has been conducted at the different surfactant concentration up to ~5 mM with 0.5 wt% constant pluronic P123 concentration. DLS data showed the suppression of P123 micellization process on addition of AOT. The addition of AOT resulted in the formation of negatively charged P123-AOT mixed micelles by the interaction between the block copolymer micelles and surfactant molecules. The P123-AOT mixed micelles exhibited enhanced electrostatic repulsion due to AOT solubilization into the PPO core of the pluronic micelle. SANS measurements revealed that by increasing the concentration of AOT, the aggregation number and core size of the pluronic micelles decreased linearly as also observed by

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DLS results. The dynamic surface tension results confirmed the interaction between AOT and doxorubicin hydrochloride (DOX) anticancer drug. The various cell lines were used to study the *in vitro* cytotoxicity and results showed that the complexation of AOT did not affect the anticancer activity of the drug. Moreover in MCF-7 cell line, DOX-loaded micelles exhibited more cytotoxicity as compared to other cell lines [human colon cancer cell line (Colo 205), human oral cancer cell line (Gurav) and human cervix cancer cell lines (SiHa) and (ME180)].

Giustini *et al.* studied the solubilization of anticancer drug doxorubicin hydrochloride in mixed micelles of pluronic F127 and a negatively charged bile salt sodium cholate, at various mole ratios (MR) of range 0 to 1 ($MR = nNaC/nF127$).⁷⁴ Doxorubicin location in mixed micelles was adjudged by steady state fluorescence spectroscopy and time resolved fluorescence spectroscopy. Doxorubicin emission spectra showed a blue shift and a change in the relative intensity of the bands located at 550 nm and 590 nm; revealed that the drug exposed to the hydrophobic environment. Time resolved fluorescence confirmed the exposure of the drug doxorubicin in an apolar environment as well. Moreover the encapsulation of drug doxorubicin granted the increased stability against the chemical degradation as compared to the water solutions. DLS and SAXS results evidenced that the main structural characteristics of the F127 and sodium cholate, mixed micelles remain unaltered in the presence of the guest doxorubicin drug molecules. Authors concluded that the stability of doxorubicin in the F127-sodium cholate mixed micelles was an encouraging advantage; led to an enhancement in the retention time of the drug doxorubicin once reaches in the blood stream.

Fu *et al.* studied the solubilization of drug toltrazuril, a broad-spectrum coccidiostat drug used to prevent and cure of coccidiosis infection in poultry and mammals.⁷⁵ However systemic administration and dose exacerbation of toltrazuril is still a challenge due to its minimal water solubility that is 0.41 g/mL. Film hydration method was used for the preparation of toltrazuril loaded mixed micelle using sodium deoxycholate-Brij C20 polyethylene ether-Triton X-100 surfactant. Toltrazuril loaded mixed micelle were characterized for their physical properties, and the pharmacokinetic properties of toltrazuril and toltrazuril loaded mixed micelle were compared. The

average particle size, drug loading, saturated solubility, and *cmc* of the toltrazuril loaded mixed micellar system were found to be 12.28 ± 0.48 nm, $3.38 \pm 0.12\%$, 3921.70 ± 0.01 g/mL (8170-fold compared with toltrazuril), and 0.0172 mg/mL, respectively. The formation of toltrazuril loaded mixed micelle was confirmed by different techniques viz. transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), DSC and X-ray diffraction (XRD). Moreover the toltrazuril loaded mixed micelle showed higher bioavailability (215%) as compared to the toltrazuril solution. So, toltrazuril loaded mixed micelle can serve as potential oral and parenteral delivery system for toltrazuril as evidenced by the results which showed the significant increase in the drug solubility and bioavailability of toltrazuril loaded mixed micelle.

Bernabeu *et al.* prepared and studied the mixed nanomicellar formulation of sodium deoxycholate and D- α -tocopheryl polyethylene glycol 1000 succinate at varying molar ratios (100:0, 75:25, 50:50, 25:75 and 0:100) to enhance the aqueous solubility and *in vitro* anti-cancer activity of drug methotrexate.⁷⁶ The methotrexate loaded mixed nanomicelles were prepared without use of any organic solvent and characterized for their drug solubilization capacity, particle size and *cmc*. A spherical shaped particle with size of about 8 nm was observed for the optimized formulation (ratio 25:75). The data of *in vitro* release study demonstrated that the micellar formulation exhibited a sustained drug release as compared to methotrexate solution. The cell viability assay in MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7 breast cancer cells showed that mixed micellar formulation attained the lower IC₅₀ value as compared to methotrexate. The cellular uptake of the methotrexate significantly increased in case of mixed micellar formulation as compared to the methotrexate alone in both breast cancer cell lines. Further the compatibility of methotrexate-loaded mixed nanomicelles with red blood cells was confirmed using the hemolytic assay.

Mukherjee *et al.* investigated the interaction of a cationic drug phenosafranin (PSF) with pluronic F127 micelles and F127/SDS mixed micelles.⁷⁷ Steady-state UV-visible and fluorescence measurements showed that phenosafranin experienced a hydrophobic and more constrained environment in the presence of F127/SDS mixed micelles as compared to that of F127 micelles alone. Partition coefficient data proved that ~58% phenosafranin drug was accommodated in the micellar matrix of F127. The

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fraction of the drug bound to F127 micelles increased significantly upon addition of very low concentrations of SDS below its *cmc* values affirmed from the time-resolved fluorescence study. DLS measurements divulged that the interaction of SDS to the F127 pluronic micelles led to the decrease in the hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) due to the formation of the mixed micelles. The values of the iodide ion-induced Stern-Volmer quenching constant confirmed that the mixed micellar system can impart pronounced protection to the probe from external agents (such as an external quencher) than the normal micelles. ITC measurements were used to estimate the binding constant of PSF with F127/SDS mixed micelles, whose order of magnitude was higher than the F127 alone. This result evidenced the stronger interaction of the probe with the F127/SDS mixed micelles as compared to the interaction with the F127 micelles. The hydrophobic force was proved to be the driving force behind the interaction of PSF with both the F127/SDS mixed micelles and the F127 micelles. The results concluded the better efficiency of F127/SDS mixed micelles as a vehicle for drug delivery (with PSF being the model drug) than the F127 micelles alone.

Ventura *et al.* designed the novel aqueous biphasic system consist of pluronic L35 and cholinium-based ILs *viz.* cholinium chloride ([Ch]Cl), cholinium dihydrogen citrate ([Ch][DHCit]), cholinium bitartrate ([Ch][Bit]), cholinium bicarbonate ([Ch][Bic]), cholinium dihydrogen phosphate ([Ch][DHP]), and cholinium acetate ([Ch][Ac]); for their potential application to separate out two glycosylated flavonoids naringin and rutin.⁷⁸ In most of the cases, an unbalanced and strong salting out persuaded by the conventional salts led to the complete extraction of flavonoids with moderate selectivities ranging from 1 to 11.8, while an enhanced extractive performance was provided in the cholinium-based ILs. In fact, the novel aqueous biphasic system based on pluronic L35 and cholinium ILs permitted the manipulation of the affinity of both naringin and rutin to opposite phases that result in the selective separation of these flavonoids. The best results were observed in system comprising [Ch][Bic] as phase former with a selectivity of 18.9. In summary, this work proposed that this process can be used for the selective separation of naringin and rutin from their natural liquid sources and their potential use in nutraceutical, cosmetic, and pharmaceutical applications.

Fang *et al.* reported a novel polymeric mixed micelle composed of Pluronic P105 and F127 copolymers loaded with the poorly soluble antitumor drug docetaxel (DTX) against Taxol-resistant non-small cell lung cancer.⁷⁹ A central composite design was utilized to optimize the preparation process, helping to improve drug solubilization efficiency and micelle stability. Mixed micelles were prepared using thin-film hydration method. The average size of the optimized mixed micelle was 23 nm, with a 92.40% encapsulation ratio and a 1.81% drug-loading efficiency. The optimized formulation showed high storage stability in lyophilized form, with 95.7% of the drug content remaining after 6 months' storage at 4°C. The *in vitro* cytotoxicity assay showed that the IC₅₀ values for Taxotere and mixed micelles were similar for A549, while on A549/Taxol cell lines, DTX-loaded P105/F127 mixed micelles showed a superior hypersensitizing effect; their IC₅₀ value (0.059 µg/mL) was greatly reduced compared to those of Taxotere injections (0.593 µg/mL). The mixed-micelle formulation achieved a 1.85-fold longer mean residence time in circulation and a 3.82-fold larger area under the plasma concentration-time curve than Taxotere observed from *in vivo* pharmacokinetic studies. In addition, therapeutic improvement of mixed micelles *in vivo* against A549/Taxol was obtained. The tumor inhibition rate of the micelles was 69.05%, versus 34.43% for Taxotere. Authors concluded that DTX-loaded P105/F127 mixed micelles might serve as a potential antitumor drug delivery system to overcome multidrug resistance in lung cancer.

Gomez *et al.* investigated the interactions between the bile salt sodium taurodeoxycholate (NaTDC) and pluronic F68 and F127 at physiological concentrations employing DSC, interfacial tension, dilatational rheology, and SEM.⁸⁰ At the oil-water interface the access of bile salt was found to be easier in the presence of pluronic F68 interfacial layer that have smaller molecular area than in the presence of adsorbed pluronic F127 having larger molecular area. The variation in the interfacial morphology of the lipid droplets was responsible for the differences in pluronics ability to delay in the lipid digestion. The degree of interaction with NaTDC in the bulk also influenced the ability of pluronics to compete for the oil-water interface. Pluronic F68 was more prone to interact with bile salt. Pluronic F127 affected the ability of NaTDC molecules to promote the lipolysis cascade in the subsistence of enzymes (lipase and colipase

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because of more molecules/micelles of NaTDC can bind with the pluronic F127 that hinder their adsorption onto the oil-water interface.

Mahajan and coworkers characterized the micellar and interfacial behaviour of pure and mixed systems of pluronics P84 and F108 with twin-tailed cationic surfactants *viz.* didecyldimethylammonium bromide (DDAB), dimethylenebis(decyldimethyl ammonium bromide) (10-2-10) and 1,3-didecyl-2-methyl-imidazolium chloride (DDIC) in the aqueous solution employing the surface tension measurements.⁸¹ The interactions between the each surfactant and pluronics (P84 and F108) have been studied on the basis of head group disparity of the surfactant and the interactions were found to be nonideal and synergistic except for the mixed system of 10-2-10 + F108 which showed the antagonistic interactions. The effect of the mixing ratio on the morphology of the various mixed micellar aggregates that were formed have been determined by SANS, DLS, and zeta potential techniques. Pure 10-2-10 and DDIC formed the prolate ellipsoidal micelles whereas pure DDAB led to formation of unilamellar vesicles. There was the formation of spherical charged mixed micelles upon the addition of 10-2-10 and DDIC in the pluronic P84/F108 micelles. The inclusion of 10-2-10/DDIC molecules in pluronic micelles would spread positive charge to the mixed micellar aggregates, which was confirmed by the zeta (ζ) values of the mixed micelles. The addition of pluronics in the DDAB resulted in the destruction of the unilamellar vesicles in to the spherical mixed micelles via expansion or contraction of vesicles.

Bhattacharyya and colleagues studied the ultrafast fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) in a mixed micelle in the presence of room-temperature ionic liquid (RTIL) by picosecond and femtosecond emission spectroscopy.⁸² The mixed micelles consisted of pluronic P123, and a RTIL, 1-pentyl-3-methyl-imidazolium bromide ([pmim][Br]) or 1-pentyl-3-methylimidazolium tetra-fluoroborate ([pmim][BF₄]). Coumarin 480 (C480) and rhodamine 6G (R6G) were used as the donor and the acceptor respectively. Three different time scales of FRET were detected, one was an ultrashort component of 1-3 ps and two relatively long components (300-400 ps and 2500-3500 ps) attributed to different donor-acceptor distances. Acceptor (R6G) was localized in the polar corona region of the mixed micelle due to the ionic nature,

while the neutral donor (C480) is solubilized over both corona and hydrophobic core regions. The close proximity of donor and acceptor components in the corona region resulted in the ultrafast FRET at 1-3 ps. The acceptor at the corona region and the donor at the core region showed the long-distance FRET components at the 300-400 ps and 2500-3500 ps. The relative contribution of the ultrafast component of FRET (~ 3 ps) increased from 25% at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 375$ nm to 100% at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 435$ nm in the 0.9 M [pmim][BF₄] mixed micelle and from 5 to 30% in the 0.3 M [pmim][BF₄] mixed micelle. Mainly the donor molecules at the corona region were excited at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 435$ nm resulted in the ultrafast FRET due to the shorter donor-acceptor distance. At shorter λ_{ex} , the donor (C480) molecule at the core regions was excited, giving rise to a very long 3400 ps component ($RDA \sim 50$ Å). The counterion dependence (Br⁻ and BF₄⁻) was attributed to the difference in their hydrophobicity and consequent effect on the size and heterogeneity in the mixed micelle.

Mahajan *et al.* studied the mixed micellization behaviour of bile salts *viz.* Sodium deoxycholate (NaDC) and Sodium cholate (NaC) with surface active imidazolium ionic liquid, (SAIL) 1-dodecyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide (C₁₂mimBr).⁸³ The distinct parameters of the binary mixtures of bile salts-SAIL such as hydrodynamic diameter (D_h), *cmc*, surface pressure at *cmc* (π_{cmc}), micellar interaction parameter (β^{m}), surface excess concentration (Γ_{max}) and minimum area per molecule (A_{min}) have been computed by employing surface tension, steady state fluorescence measurements and DLS techniques. The interactions between NaC/NaDC and C₁₂mimBr molecules in the mixed micelles have been found to be highly synergistic that resulted in the origination of newer stronger hydrophobic and electrostatic forces between the components. Among the two bile salts NaDC and NaC, NaDC exhibited better synergistic interactions that resulted in the enhanced adsorption and larger hydrodynamic radius in mixtures with C₁₂mimBr. This was due to the more hydrophobic nature of NaDC that allowed its molecules to get deeply penetrated in the mixed micelles in comparison to NaC. NaC having three hydroxyl groups that preferred the polar environment resulted in the adsorption of the most of NaC molecules on the micellar surface. It has been observed that the solubilization was dependent on the

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hydrophobicity and the size of the micelles, the solubility of phenothiazine was increased in the order: NaC < NaDC < NaC + C₁₂mimBr < NaDC + C₁₂mimBr. Authors emphasized that these bile salt- C₁₂mimBr mixtures can be used for the solubilization of phenothiazine and its derivatives for the purpose of drug delivery.

Zheng and his co-workers employed conductivity and ITC studies to investigate the interactions of pluronics L64 and F68 with SAILs *viz.* N-alkyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium bromide (C_nMPB, n=12, 14, 16) and 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide (C_nmimBr, n = 8, 10, 12, 14, 16).⁸⁴ The ITC data showed the presence of the two different concentrations called as, *cac* and C₂ (saturation concentration). The dehydration of PPO segments resulted into the formation of aggregate complexes on the polymer chains beyond *cac*. The interaction of the polymer chains with surface of the SAIL micelles takes place through ion-dipole attractions at the time of the rearrangement of these complexes at reaching the concentration at C₂. The formation of free micelles began by the further increase in the concentration of SAIL. The interaction between L64 and SAILs was observed to be more efficient as compared to the interaction between F68 and SAILs because of higher hydrophobicity of L64 than that of F68. The smaller values of counter-ion binding (β) for SAILs described the repression of counterions to the polymer-SAIL aggregates in the presence of polymer as that of in its absence. It has been noted that, as the hydrophobic chain length of polymer increased, the binding strength of SAILs with polymer also increased, however the change in the head group did not show much effect.

Guo *et al.* used different techniques *viz.* DLS, surface tension, NMR and ITC measurements to study the micellization behaviour and interactions of pluronic F127 with ionic liquid based double tailed surfactant, 1,3-dioctylimidazolium bromide ([Doim][Br]).⁸⁵ Above *cmc*, the formation of aggregates by double tailed IL was observed in which hydrophobic core consisted the tail part whereas the imidazolium heads reside on micellar surface. The surface tension measurements showed the existence of interactions between the IL and F127 which was confirmed by the increase in *cmc* of [Doim][Br] in the presence of pluronic F127. The interaction of pluronic F127 with ionic liquid [Doim][Br] was also studied at distinct temperatures and [Doim][Br] concentrations. Upon increasing the temperature, an increase in the *cmc* values of

[Doim][Br] in the existence of F127, revealed the hydrophobic interplay between the ionic liquid and pluronic. At low temperatures, [Doim][Br] micelles adsorbed on the F127 chains but at the higher temperatures, the aggregation of F127 was promoted with the addition of [Doim][Br]. F127 micelles dissociated at considerably higher concentrations of [Doim][Br], and consequently the binding of F127 monomers to the [Doim][Br] micelles takes place.

Moulik *et al.* studied the pluronic L31 effect on the microstructure and aggregation behaviour of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) surfactant by employing DLS, cloud point (CP), NMR, ITC, SANS and electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) measurements.⁸⁶ The concentration of L31 determined the effect of SDS on the CP of L31 solution. The ITC measurements obtained from the L31-SDS interaction confirmed the existence of critical aggregation concentration, *cac* and extended critical micelle concentration, *cmc_e*. The pluronic L31 presence near the surface of SDS micelles was revealed by the EPR results. The adsorption and localization of pluronic L31 on the surface of SDS micelles resulted into the upfield shifts in case of SDS which was supported by the results obtained from EPR measurements. SANS results revealed that lack of micelle forming ability of pluronic L31 however in the presence of 5 mM SDS, the scattering was significantly increased indicating micelle formation. The size of the mixed aggregates increased as the concentration of SDS increased, moreover results into the shape change of aggregates from spherical to ellipsoidal. Authors concluded that by selecting the appropriate L31/SDS ratios, the morphologies of mixed micelles could be altered ranging from spherical to ellipsoid which might be useful in the drug delivery and nanotechnology applications.

Parmar and coworkers investigated the solution behaviour of P103 micelles in the presence of addition of ionic liquids (ILs) 1-alkyl-3-methyl imidazolium tetrafluoroborates (C_nmim BF₄ n=4, 6, 8) using various techniques *viz.* DLS, CP, SANS and NMR.⁸⁷ The CP of P103 increased drastically in the presence of ILs as observed from the CP measurements. This can be attributed to hydrogen-bonding between the hydrophilic PEO units of P103 and imidazolium cation of the ILs, and hydrophobic interactions between the hydrophobic PPO unit of P103 and the alkyl chain of the ILs. The DLS and SANS measurements revealed the alterations in size which confirmed the

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formation of mixed micellar aggregates involving both P103 and ILs. The selective nuclear overhauser effect spectroscopy (NOESY) revealed the hydrophobic interaction between the PPO blocks of P103 and the alkyl group of the ILs. The formation of mixed micelles was indicated by the partitioning of $C_n\text{mim BF}_4$ into micellar phase. The micelle size, CP, and aggregation number were significantly altered along with increase in dipolarity due to the presence of IL within the micelles.

Barron *et al.* demonstrated the microstructure and rheological properties of micellar solutions of pluronics (F127, P123 and L121) in deuterated ethylammonium nitrate (dEAN, a protic ionic liquid) by employing SANS and ultra SANS, fluorescence microscopy, and shear rheology measurements.⁸⁸ The effect of the relative balance of hydrophilic to hydrophobic block size on the self-assembled microstructure was analyzed by using different pluronics with similar PPO block length (F127, P123 and L121). In dEAN both F127 and P123 formed spherical shaped micelles that upon increasing temperature or concentration, assembled into body-centered and face-centered cubic supramolecular crystals, respectively. The conversion from disordered to crystalline (ordered) structures revealed as a sol-gel rheological transition. L121/dEAN system was observed by the richer phase diagram: L121 self-assembled into vesicles in the dilute regime (structures with low curvatures) due to its low solvophilicity in dEAN, at intermediate concentrations and low temperatures formed elongated (wormlike) micelles, multilamellar phases at high temperatures and a nematic phase in concentrated solutions. The self-assembly of entangled L121 wormlike micelles resulted in highly viscoelastic solutions. SANS and ultra SANS measurements were used to determine the structural length scales of the three pluronic/dEAN systems in the various mesophases.

Soni *et al.* studied micellization characteristics of pluronic P123 (15 % w/w) in the presence and absence of N-alkylpyridinium halide ILs employing SANS, DLS, and ^1H NMR techniques.⁸⁹ SANS measurements fitted with a model composed of a hard sphere structure factor of interaction and core-shell form factor demonstrated the structural parameters of micelles which were acquired as a function of changing concentrations of ILs, and alkyl chain length, anions. A decrease in the hard sphere radius, core of micelle, and aggregation number of P123 pluronic micelles upon addition of ILs was observed. The amount of solvent (D_2O + IL) present in the inner

core and the core-shell interface along with cationic head groups was determined from quantitative analysis. Moreover this further was supported by ^1H NMR spectroscopy data which demonstrated the interaction between polymer micelle and ILs.

Lodge *et al.* demonstrated pluronic P123 micelle shuttle between water and IL, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate [BMIM][PF₆] and its potential application in molecular transport in the biphasic system.⁹⁰ DLS measurements confirmed the formation of pluronic P123 micelles in both water and the IL solution, [BMIM][PF₆]. ^1H NMR results indicated that a simple temperature stimulus can lead to the transfer (reversible and repeatable) of P123 micelles between the water and the IL solution. By adding salt to the aqueous phase in the biphasic system the transfer temperature can be altered that determines the micelle partitioning. Authors tested the fully reversible transport of three different hydrophobic dyes to and out of water and facile extraction of a [BMIM][PF₆]-phobic polymer from [BMIM][PF₆] and emphasized that in the biphasic system, the various cargoes were being transported. So, this simple delivery system may be used in drug delivery system, separations and purification of product in reaction synthesis, and catalysis involving ionic liquids in biphasic system.

Dar *et al.* used spectrophotometric and steady-state, time-resolved fluorimetric techniques to study the solubilization of structurally different coumarins, viz., warfarin (WF; a 4- hydroxy coumarin) and coumarin 30 (C30, a 7-amino coumarin) individually and cosolubilization (mixed state) within the aqueous surfactant self-assemblies of varying architectures.⁹¹ To understand the effect of micelles on their photophysical phenomena and their use as competent FRET pair, the co-solubilization studies within micelles were performed when simultaneously present within these nanocarriers. The WF was found to be solubilized within CTAB micelles however Brij30 and SDS micelles were unable to solubilize the WF. Contrarily, C30 was found to be solubilized in the polar head group of CTAB micelles, between oxyethylene (OE) groups in Brij30 micelles and between negatively charged head groups in SDS micelles. The solubilization sites of C30 and WF were maintained during cosolubilization. In SDS and Brij30 micelles, fluorescence quenching of C30 molecules was observed due to an increase in WF, whereas in CTAB, an increased fluorescence of C30 was observed due

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to the increase in WF by excited WF molecules which indicated the FRET between the two molecules (WF and C30).

Sarkar *et al.* investigated the formation of niosome produced by the synergy of pluronic F127 with cholesterol and its interaction with sugar (sucrose) molecules.⁹² DLS and TEM measurements demonstrated the shape and size of F127-cholesterol based niosome in presence of sucrose. The DLS measurements and TEM images evidenced the significant increase in the size of niosome in presence of sucrose. Moreover, the dynamic heterogeneity of the systems was monitored by a detailed comparative fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) technique performed in these aggregates containing pluronic F127, comprising coumarin 153 (C153) as donor (D) and rhodamine 6G (R6G) as an acceptor (A). Apart from this, F127-cholesterol based niosome aggregates were studied for the rotational and lateral diffusion motion in these aggregates by employing time resolved anisotropy and fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (FCS) measurements using C153 and R6G respectively. FRET study showed the presence of multiple time constants of FRET inside the F127-cholesterol based niosomes as compared to the pluronic F127 micelle. The results confirmed the existence of more than one preferential donor-acceptor (D–A) distances in niosomes than in pluronic F127 micelle. The effect on the morphology of F127-cholesterol based niosome by the presence of sugar has also been examined by FRET study. In sucrose decorated niosome, the presence of sugar led to increase in the time constant of FRET as D-A distance increases. FRET studies revealed that change of excitation energy of donor molecule from 408 nm to 440 nm led to the enhanced benefaction of the faster rise component of the acceptor which clearly constituted the dynamics heterogeneity of both systems.

Yuk *et al.* used fast, simple, continuous and solvent-free process to prepare nanoparticles by a temperature-induced phase transition in a mixture of pluronic F68 and liquid PEG containing paclitaxel (PTX).⁹³ The pluronic F68 was used to encapsulate the drug PTX whereas the liquid PEG was used as solubilizer of PTX. The polymer mixture was changed to the liquid phase at the phase transition temperature and stirring of the liquid polymer mixture led to the formation of emulsions composed

of PEG containing PTX and liquidized pluronic F-68. On the nanometer scale, pluronic F-68 encapsulated the PEG containing PTX, cooled to 0°C to form pluronic nanoparticles. Field emission (FE) SEM and TEM study was performed to observe the morphology and size distribution of the prepared pluronic nanoparticles and the shape of paclitaxel-loaded pluronic nanoparticles in an aqueous state was analyzed using a particle size analyzer and cryo-TEM. The release study of PTX from the nanoformulation was also performed to observe the efficiency of this system as potential delivery system for cancer therapy. The PTX-loaded pluronic nanoparticles were injected to the tail veins of tumor bearing mice to monitor the tumor growth. PTX-loaded pluronic nanoparticles were also evaluated for their *in-vivo* biodistribution, time-dependent excretion profile, circulation time, and their tumor targeting ability by using non-invasive live animal imaging technology. The rapid release of loaded PTX was found within the 7h but afterwards the sustained release up to 48 h was observed. PTX loaded pluronic nanoparticles showed the higher anti-tumor activity than that of the PTX formulated in cremophor EL as evidenced by the *in-vivo* studies.

Wang *et al.* studied the encapsulation of PTX drug and superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SION) into pluronic F127 copolymer micelles and their impact on micellar structural properties.⁹⁴ NMR results evidenced the interaction of PTX with PPO in the micelle core whereas SION was present in both PEO and PPO blocks. The results of SAXS and cryo-TEM described that the PTX interaction with micelles did not alter the shape of the micelles. The drug concentration was responsible for the variation in the dimensions of core and corona region and encapsulation of drug resulted in the large core size. SAXS measurements were used to study the temperature effect on the structures of pluronic and pluronic-PTX. The results evidenced the agglomeration of micelles upon increasing the temperature from 37 to 50 °C and change in the shape from sphere to cylinder.

Dash *et al.* reported the interaction and mixed micellization behaviour of methylparaben and propylparaben with pluronic F127 and P123.⁹⁵ The UV studies revealed that mixed micelle of F127 and P123 with drug parabens showed intermediate spectral behaviour. The similar results were also obtained from the CP measurements. It

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was observed that the intensity of fluorescence spectra was significantly higher with the combination of mixed micelle-methylparaben and lower with combinations of the mixed micelle-propylparaben. When drug methylparaben and propylparaben combined with the mixed pluronic system, the static nature of quenching was observed. The dissociation constant (K_D) for methylparaben-mixed micelles and propylparaben-mixed micelles combinations were found to be $21.18 \times 10^{-3} \text{ L mol}^{-1}$ and $32.57 \times 10^{-3} \text{ L mol}^{-1}$ respectively. These results indicated that binding between methylparaben and mixed micelle was stronger as compared to propylparaben and mixed micelle. DLS studies indicated that the micellar aggregation and encapsulation efficiency for the drug was better and promoted by the addition of NaCl to the mixed micelle and parabens. SEM images showed the morphology changes when methylparaben and propylparaben molecules incorporated into the surface cavities of mixed micelle. Authors concluded that the enhancement of drug solubility can lead to the use of pluronic mixed micelles as better drug carrier for pharmaceutical applications.

Chitprasert *et al.* reported the mixed micelles of pluronic F127, P123 and Vitamin E TPGS (tocopheryl polyethylene glycol succinate) copolymers to encapsulate two phenolics drugs magniferin and quercetin with different polarities.⁹⁶ They used simplex-centroid mixture design for the optimization of formulations of mixed micelles (F127/P123/Vitamin E TPGS) for the loading of magniferin and quercetin with low *cmc* but high encapsulation efficiency and drug loading capacity. The optimal formulas for the mixed micelles were different for the phenolics, quercetin and magniferin. The highly hydrophobic drug quercetin was miscible in the binary mixed micelles of F127/P123, while magniferin favored the ternary mixed micelles of F127/P123/TPGS. *cmc* values of phenolics loaded mixed micelles were decreased as compare to pure micelles. Evidence of co-micellization of the mixed copolymers was confirmed by the monomodal size distribution of the nearly neutral charged mixed micelles. The hydrophobic backbone part of magniferin was favorably located in the core, while the polar glucoside moiety was placed in contact with the hydrophilic corona region of the mixed micelles. Most of quercetin was solubilized in the hydrophobic PPO core of mixed micelles due to the hydrophobic nature of this drug. Amorphous nature of the mixed micellar formulation loaded magniferin and quercetin enabled them for high

solubility and sustained release behaviour over 120 and 240 min of gastric and intestinal medium, respectively. Authors suggested that simplex-centroid mixture design can be successfully applied for multiresponse optimization mixed micellar formulations of magniferin and quercetin, and the most advantageous physicochemical merits of developed mixed micelles had potential application as nanoparticle-based oral drug delivery systems.

Dar *et al.* studied the solubilization and co-solubilization of calcium channel blocker drug nifedipine and antiepileptic drug carbamazepine in sodium cholate based binary and ternary mixed micelles with non-ionic polymers *viz.* Polysorbate- Tween20, Tween40 and polyoxyethylene surfactants- Brij30, Brij35, Brij56 and Brij58.⁹⁷ While mixing the different polymers and sodium cholate to obtained mixed micelles synergistic interaction played an important role resulted in the increase in aggregation number and decrease in polarity of palisade layer, which enhanced the solubilization of drugs in core with concomitant decrease of drug solubilization in palisade layer. The interaction between the surfactants in mixed micelles determined the solubilization of drugs. It increased with increase in interactions between the surfactants when the location of solubilization preferentially in the micelle core, and decreased with increase in surfactant interactions when the solubilization of drug was in the palisade layer of the micelle. During co-solubilization, because nifedipine was preferably solubilized within the micellar core, its solubility was increased and the solubilization of carbamazepine which mainly occurred in the palisade layer, was not favored.

Sosnik's group investigated the mixed micellization of linear and branched poly(ethylene oxide)-poly (propylene oxide) co-polymer for the effective loading of the anti-HIV drug efavirenz.⁹⁸ They studied the process of co-micellization of 10% binary systems mixing different weight ratios of a hydrophilic pluronic F127 and a hydrophobic tetronic T304 and T904 (poloxamine) using DLS, CP and electronic spin resonance experiments. The solubilization of drug efavirenz in these mixed micelles was found to be synergistic. Solubility of drug efavirenz increased 8430-fold from 4 µg/mL to 33 mg/mL. Efavirenz loaded mixed micelles exhibited the enhanced physical stability over time in comparison with pure poloxamine micelles. Authors emphasized that the poloxamer/poloxamine mixed micelles can act as trojan nanocarriers for drug

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encapsulation and release by the oral route because of its enormous versatility with enhanced stability and solubility enhancement.

Na *et al.* reported an intra-articularly injectable thermo-sensitive hydrogel system comprised of the hyaluronic acid (HA) and pluronic F127 in aqueous solution.⁹⁹ By simple physical mixing of high-molecular-weight HA (Mw~1000 kDa), authors were able to enhance the mechanical strength of hydrogel and elicited sustained drug release behaviour of drug piroxicam due to HA-assisted inter-micellar packing. A significant decrease of transmittance and increase in particle size (to~ 400 nm) was observed above a certain temperature (>30°C) as observed by light transmittance and DLS measurements respectively. Importantly, critical gelation temperature (*cgt*) value of the HP hydrogel was (~ 13 wt%) significantly lower than that of the pluronic F127 (~ 17 wt%) hydrogel. From *in vitro* and *in vivo* results, authors observed that the piroxicam-loaded hyaluronic acid (HA)-pluronic F127 hydrogel not only exhibited a superior mechanical-strength but also showed sustained drug release behaviour.

Araujo *et al.* investigated the structure of the binary mixture of pluronic F127 and pluronic L81, as hydrogels based delivery of hydrophilic anti-migraine drug sumatriptan.¹⁰⁰ Authors studied the drug-micelle interaction by DLS, DSC, sol-gel process by rheology, and SAXS. They extended their investigation to pharmaceutical formulation aspects *viz.* dissolution rate, release profile and cytotoxicity studies for apoptosis and necrosis in fibroblasts and neural cells. The mixed micelle formation was investigated by DLS and DSC studies and they observed that there was only one phase transition for all of the formulations even in the presence of sumatriptan. SAXS and *in vitro* dissolution/release results revealed a probable relationship between the transitions of the lamellar to hexagonal phase. They selected two concentration of F127 i.e. 18% w/v and 20 % w/v for the formulation design. Sol-gel transition temperatures for F127 i.e. 18% w/v and 20 % w/v were found to be 32 and 28 °C respectively in the absence of sumatriptan but after incorporation of sumatriptan, the sol-gel temperatures were found to be 34 and 30°C. Importantly, authors observed that the presence of pluronic L81 favored a shift to the hexagonal phase, indicated that this copolymer participates in the formation of micelles and the aggregation processes. Authors concluded that such supramolecular organization could facilitate incorporation of the sumatriptan drug into

intermicellar spaces. Sumatriptan drug possibly interacted with the hydrated micellar corona region due to its hydrophilic nature. These systems which have minimal pluronic concentration, could serve as a drug delivery carriers particularly for migraine treatment.

Hassan *et al.* developed the pluronic P123 stabilized Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles for delivery of hydrophobic anti-tumor drug curcumin. Functionalization of nanoparticles with P123 was confirmed from the FTIR, TGA, DLS, UV-visible and zeta-potential measurements.¹⁰¹ Pluronic stabilized Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles were developed by introducing amphiphilic triblock co-polymer, pluronic P123 onto the surface of hydrophobic magnetic nanoparticles. The addition of pluronic layer provides the hydrophobic interface for encapsulation of curcumin as well as results in the greater colloidal stability and biocompatibility. These pluronic stabilized Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles showed high curcumin loading capacity and its pH dependent release in to the tumor cells.

An exceptional study was reported by the Losic and co-workers in which they presented the stimulus-responsive drug delivery system.¹⁰² Authors used the titania nanotube arrays loaded with the hydrophobic drug indomethacin encapsulated pluronic F127 micelles and magnetic nanoparticles at the bottom of the nanotubes. A rapid triggered release (100% release) of the indomethacin drug from pluronic F127 micelles achieved by activating magnetic nanoparticles loaded at the bottom of these titania nanotubes. This strategy was quite useful for drug-releasing implants in bone surgery and orthopaedics where on-demand release was needed at the targeted sites for instant relief.

Dreiss *et al.* studied the solubilization of four different drugs *viz.* lidocaine, pentobarbital sodium, naproxen sodium, and sodium salicylate in pluronic F127 micelles and their protective effect against the demicellisation of F127 micelles, which was triggered by dimethylated β -cyclodextrin (DIMEB).¹⁰³ They examined two possible mechanisms of protection: Using a wide combination of techniques such as small-angle neutron scattering (SANS), 2D NOESY NMR, UV-visible spectroscopy, fluorescence spectroscopy, Dynamic and Static Light Scattering measurements (a) a stabilization of

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the micelles by the drugs, controlled by drug polymer interactions; **(b)** the role of drug/cyclodextrin inclusion complex formation (which leads to a lower effective amount of cyclodextrin molecules available to rupture the micelles). The results from the SANS data showed that the presence of these drugs in the aggregates impacted the size and structure of the loaded micelles in distinct manners: pentobarbital sodium exhibited the very little influence on micellar structure, while sodium salicylate and naproxen sodium decrease micellar size by forming intra-micellar electrostatic repulsions, and lidocaine led to the swelling of the micellar core. 2D NOESY NMR was employed to further relate these results with the drug structure and their solubilization locus within the aggregates. The solubilization of this drug at the core/corona interface was facilitated by a very superficial localization of pentobarbital sodium at the micellar surface. The localization of sodium salicylate could not be estimated because of very low partitioning, but adopted a similar locus than naproxen sodium at acidic pH; the localization of lidocaine was estimated in the hydrophobic environment, which was according with its partitioning within the hydrophobic core. The enhanced partitioning of all investigated drugs in pluronic micelles was evidenced but decrease in binding to DIMEB was observed at 37°C (physiological temperature). The micellar breakup due to DIMEB was markedly slower in the presence of investigated drugs (100s of seconds) than the pure pluronic micelles (<100 ms) as evidenced by Time-resolved SANS (TR-SANS). On the whole, this work provides insights into cyclodextrin-induced demicellization, the importance of drug solubilization locus within polymeric micelles, and inclusion complex formation between drugs and cyclodextrins. The results were highly relevant to the controlled delivery of active compounds from polymeric micelles or cyclodextrins, but also offer a fundamental understanding into competitive molecular processes that control interactions and thus equilibrium structures in multicomponent systems.

1.3 Justification and Objectives

Amphiphiles *viz.* pluronics, bile salts, and surface active ionic liquids (SAILs) have attracted considerable attention for decades due to their extensive applications in the field of research; biomedical and pharmaceutical industries; material chemistry and

supramolecular self-assembly for the development of more complex, hierarchical nanostructures. Incorporation of hydrophobic drug into pluronic co-polymeric amphiphilic micelles leads to increased solubility, metabolic stability and circulation time. Moreover mixed micelles manifest synergistic properties, such as increased micelle stability and drug loading efficiency, superior to those of the individual micelles. The present thesis aims to explore the drug solubilization capacity and drug release behaviour of pluronic micelles; factors affecting the solubilization capacity such as length of corona region or palisade layer; temperature and presence of different ionic and non-ionic surfactants for their potential use in drug formulations. The main objectives of this thesis are outlined as follows:

1. To compare the effect of corona region or palisade layer of different pluronic micelles on the solubilization capacity of hydrophobic drug molecules and probe the possible location of the drug in these micelles.
2. To evaluate the physicochemical aspects such as solubilization capacity, drug loading efficiency, average number of drug molecules solubilized per micelle (n_s), partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) of hydrophobic drug in mixed micellar system comprising pluronic and ionic bile salts.
3. To investigate the solubilization behaviour of hydrophobic drug in the mixed micelles of pluronic and surface active ionic liquids (SAILs) to enhance their aqueous solubility and cytotoxic effects on cancer cell lines.
4. To evaluate the effect of temperature on the morphology, solubilization and *in-vitro* release behaviour of hydrophobic drugs in different pluronic micelles.
5. To identify the mixed micellar system for the delivery of hydrophobic drugs and to enhance their antioxidant potential for their desired effects.

To achieve above mentioned objectives, the present work has been classified in five chapters (Chapter 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7), which are preceded by a detailed experimental (Chapter 2) including materials and techniques exploited to study the solubilization

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behaviour of hydrophobic drugs in different amphiphilic micelles. The brief description of each chapter is as given below:

- ❖ **Chapter 3** aims at studying the effect of corona length (PEO length) on the solubilization behaviour of hydrophobic drug oxcarbazepine (OXC) in different pluronic micelles *viz.* F108, F127 and P84. UV-visible spectroscopy has been employed to determine the solubilization capacity of different pluronic micelles. Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) and proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (^1H NMR) techniques have been employed to estimate the OXC locus of solubilization in pluronic micelles. Solubilization of OXC in pluronic micelles was further confirmed from dynamic light scattering (DLS) and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) techniques. *In vitro* dialysis method was used to find out the effect of locus of solubilization on the release behaviour of the encapsulated drug OXC in the pluronic micelles. Different kinetic models *viz.* Zero order release kinetics, First order release kinetics and Higuchi model kinetics were fitted on the drug release data to get further insights on the drug release behaviour.
- ❖ The solubilization behaviour of an atypical antipsychotic hydrophobic drug clozapine (CLZ) in mixed systems of anionic biosurfactant sodium deoxycholate (SDC) and pluronic F108, F127 and P84 has been explored in **Chapter 4** using UV-visible spectroscopy, DLS and small angle neutron scattering (SANS), fluorescence spectroscopy, powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements. Different solubilization behaviour parameters such as drug loading efficiency, average number of drug molecules solubilized per micelle (n_s), partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) have been computed. The morphological and structural changes taking place in pluronics in different concentration regimes of sodium deoxycholate (SDC) and with the addition of drug CLZ has been explored using DLS and SANS measurements. The micropolarity measurements have been performed to shed light on the locus of solubilization of the drug in pure and mixed micellar systems. The compatibility between CLZ and drug carriers (pluronic and SDC) was confirmed using powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) techniques. Besides, the prepared CLZ

loaded pluronic-SDC mixed micellar formulations were further tested for long term stability study for 3 months at room temperature.

- ❖ **Chapter 5** reports the systematic investigation on the solubilization of natural hydrophobic drug quercetin (QCT) in pluronic F108 and its mixed micelles with surface active ionic liquids (SAILs). SAILs which were used for this study include 1-dodecyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide [Mim]; N-dodecyl-N-methylpiperidinium bromide, [Pip]; N-dodecyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium bromide, [Pyr]. Employing UV-visible spectroscopy the solubility, loading efficiency and partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) of QCT was determined in pluronic F108 and F108-SAILs mixed micelles. The solubilization locus of QCT in F108 micelles and F108-SAIL mixed micelles has been adjudged with the help of differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and proton nuclear magnetic resonance ($^1\text{H NMR}$) measurements. *In vitro* drug release studies were performed to have an idea about the release behaviour of the drugs from the mixed systems. Cell viability assay (MTT assay) was performed for the prepared QCT-F108-SAILs mixed micellar formulations on triple negative breast cancer cell line MDA-MB-231 for the assessment of anticancer activity.
- ❖ **Chapter 6** deals with the solubilization of the hydrophobic antiepileptic drug lamotrigine (LAM) in five different pluronic micelles viz. P84, P85, F127, F108 and F68 at different temperatures 37°C, 47°C and 57°C. SANS measurements were employed to observe the morphological and structural changes taking place in pluronics as a function of temperature increase. The morphological conversions were further confirmed from Heat Transfer Method (HTM) measurements. For the first time, HTM was established for the analysis of morphological changes in the thermos-responsive pluronic micelles in real time manner. DLS measurements were used to find out the hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of the pluronic micelles before and after the solubilization of LAM at different temperatures. The rate of controlled release of LAM from five different pluronic micelles was accessed by different kinetic models to evaluate the *in vitro* release profile. The present work corroborate that how we can control the drug loading capacity, morphological

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structure of the drug carrier as well as drug release by simply changing the temperature of pluronic micellar media.

- ❖ **In chapter 7**, a comprehensive study on the solubilization of the hydrophobic drugs clozapine (CLZ) and oxcarbazepine (OXC) in the mixed micelles of low molecular weight pluronics (L64 and L35) and high molecular weight pluronics (P84, F127, F68 and P123) has been conducted using UV-visible spectroscopy, fluorescence spectroscopy, DLS and *in vitro* release. The solubility of the CLZ and OXC was found to be higher in pluronic L64/P84 (1:4) and L64/F127 (1:4) mixed micelles respectively. Fluorescence spectroscopy indicated that the critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) decreased with the formation of mixed micelles as compared to pure individual micelles. The formulations were also screened for their antioxidant activity to ameliorate the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by four different antioxidant assays *viz.* DPPH assay (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl free radical assay), reducing power assay, metal chelating activity and nitric oxide assay. The antioxidant activity was significantly enhanced in the pluronic mixed micelles, indicated that these mixed micellar formulations can be considered as an effective drug delivery candidate in the management of diseases of the central nervous system that are manifested by the increased production of ROS.

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Chapter 2

Experimental

2.1 Materials

The commercially available as well as synthesized compounds used in this thesis are represented in **Table 2.1** and **Table 2.2** respectively. For the preparation of solutions, double distilled water having conductivity in the range of 1-2 μScm^{-1} was used. Weighing of the compounds was done using sartorius analytical balance with a precision of ± 0.0001 g.

Table 2.1 Commercially available compounds

Name and Structure of the Compound	Molecular Formulae/ Molecular Weight	Purchased from	Purity
<u>Triblock Copolymers (Pluronics)</u>			
EO₁₁PO₁₆EO₁₁ Pluronic L35	C ₉₂ H ₁₈₆ O ₃₉ / 1916.40	Sigma Aldrich	99.0%
EO₁₃PO₃₀EO₁₃ Pluronic L64	C ₁₄₂ H ₂₈₆ O ₅₇ / 2905.70	Sigma Aldrich	99.0%
EO₁₉PO₄₃EO₁₉ Pluronic P84	C ₂₀₅ H ₅₁₂ O ₈₂ / 4290.12	Sigma Aldrich	99.0%
EO₂₆PO₄₀EO₂₆ Pluronic P85	C ₂₂₄ H ₄₅₀ O ₉₃ / 4872.04	Sigma Aldrich	99.0%
EO₂₀PO₇₀EO₂₀ Pluronic P123	C ₂₉₀ H ₅₈₂ O ₁₁₁ / 5845.55	Sigma Aldrich	99.0%
EO₇₇PO₂₉EO₇₇ Pluronic F68	C ₃₉₅ H ₇₉₂ O ₁₈₄ / 8486.25	Sigma Aldrich	99.0%
EO₁₀₀PO₆₅EO₁₀₀ Pluronic F127	C ₅₉₅ H ₁₁₉₂ O ₂₆₆ / 12603.44	Sigma Aldrich	99.0%

<p style="text-align: center;">EO₁₃₃PO₅₀EO₁₃₃ Pluronic F108</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">$C_{682}H_{1366}O_{317}/$ 14639.68</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Sigma Aldrich</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">99.0%</p>
<u>Hydrophobic Drugs</u>			
<div style="text-align: center;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Oxcarbazepine (OXC)</p> </div>	<p style="text-align: center;">$C_{15}H_{12}N_2O_2/$ 252.26</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Sigma Aldrich</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">≥ 98.0%</p>
<div style="text-align: center;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Clozapine (CLZ)</p> </div>	<p style="text-align: center;">$C_{18}H_{19}ClN_4/$ 326.82</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Sigma Aldrich</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">≥ 98.0%</p>
<div style="text-align: center;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Quercetin (QCT)</p> </div>	<p style="text-align: center;">$C_{15}H_{10}O_7/$ 302.23</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Sigma Aldrich</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">≥ 95.0%</p>

Experimental

<p>Lamotrigine (LAM)</p>	$C_9H_7Cl_2N_5$ / 256.09	Sigma Aldrich	$\geq 98.0\%$
<u>Ionic Surfactants</u>			
<p>Sodium deoxycholate (SDC, Bile Salt)</p>	$C_{24}H_{39}NaO_4$ / 414.56	Sigma Aldrich	$\geq 97.0\%$
<p>Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS)</p>	$NaC_{12}H_{25}SO_4$ / 288.372	Sigma Aldrich	$\geq 99.0\%$
<u>Others</u>			
<p>1-methylimidazole</p>	$C_4H_6N_2$ / 82.10	Sigma Aldrich	99.0%

 N-methylpiperidine	$C_6H_{13}N/$ 99.17	Sigma Aldrich	99.0%
 N-methylpyrrolidine	$C_5H_{11}N/$ 85.15	Sigma Aldrich	99.0%
 1-bromododecane	$C_{12}H_{25}Br/$ 249.23	Sigma Aldrich	97.0%
 Pyrene	$C_{16}H_{10}/$ 202.25	Sigma Aldrich	$\geq 98\%$
 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH free radical)	$C_{18}H_{12}N_5O_6/$ 394.32	Sigma Aldrich	$\geq 98\%$
 Ferozine	$C_{20}H_{12}N_4Na_2O_6S_2/$ 514.38	Himedia	$\geq 98.0\%$

Experimental

<p>N-(1-Naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride</p>	$C_{12}H_{16}Cl_2N_2/$ 256.17	Sigma Aldrich	$\geq 98.0\%$
<p>Sulfanilamide</p>	$C_6H_8N_2O_2S/$ 172.20	Sigma Aldrich	$\geq 98.0\%$
<p>Sodium nitroprusside</p>	$C_5FeN_6Na_2OH_2/$ 297.95	Sigma Aldrich	$\geq 98.0\%$
<p>Potassium ferricyanide</p>	$C_6N_6FeK_3/$ 329.24	Sigma Aldrich	99.0%

<p>Trichloroacetic acid</p>	$C_2HCl_3O_2/$ 168.38	TCI Chemicals	$\geq 99.0\%$
<p>Orthophosphoric Acid</p>	$H_3PO_4/$ 98.0	Merck	85%
<p>Acetonitrile</p>	$CH_3CN/$ 41.05	Sigma Aldrich	99.8%
<p>Dichloromethane (DCM)</p>	$CH_2Cl_2/$ 84.9	Sigma Aldrich	98%
<p>Deuterium oxide (D_2O)</p>	$D_2O/$ 20.03	Sigma Aldrich	99.9 atom% D
Sodium Chloride (NaCl)	$NaCl/$ 58.44	CDH Mumbai	99.0 %
Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)	$NaOH/$ 40.00	CDH Mumbai	99.0 %
Sodium dihydrogen phosphate (NaH_2PO_4)	$NaH_2PO_4/$ 119.98	CDH Mumbai	99.0 %
Disodium hydrogen phosphate (Na_2HPO_4)	$Na_2HPO_4/$ 141.96	CDH Mumbai	99.9 %

Experimental

Table 2.2 Synthesized compounds [Surface active ionic liquids (SAILs)]¹

Name and Structure of the Compound	Molecular Formulae/ Molecular weight
<p>1-dodecyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide</p>	C ₁₆ H ₃₁ N ₂ Br/ 331.39
<p>N-methyl-N-dodecylpiperidinium bromide</p>	C ₁₈ H ₃₈ NBr/ 348.405
<p>N-methyl-N-dodecylpyrrolidinium bromide</p>	C ₁₇ H ₃₆ NBr/ 334.378

2.2 Methods

UV-visible spectroscopy was employed to study the solubilization capacity and *in vitro* drug release from micelles of pure pluronics and mixed micelles of pluronics with other amphiphiles like bile salts and surface active ionic liquids (SAILs). Fluorescence was used to estimate the critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) values of pluronic and their mixtures. Solubilization locus of hydrophobic drugs in micelles was estimated by variety of techniques such as, proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR), isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Compatibility between the pluronic and drug molecules has been confirmed by fourier infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) techniques. The morphology of pure and mixed micelles of

pluronics, before and after the solubilization of drug was characterized using techniques such as small angle neutron scattering (SANS), dynamic light scattering (DLS) and Heat Transfer Method (HTM). Some pluronic micelle formulations were also screened for their *in vitro* anticancer activity by *in vitro* cell viability assay (MTT assay) and antioxidant activity using four different antioxidant assays: 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl free radical (DPPH•) assay, metal chelating activity, reducing power assay and nitric oxide (NO) scavenging assay. These techniques have been briefly described below:

2.2.1 UV-visible measurements

UV-1800 Shimadzu UV-visible spectrophotometer with a quartz cuvette of path length 1 cm was used to record the absorption spectra (**Figure 2.1**). UV-visible measurements were used in two ways **a)** to determine the amount of hydrophobic drug that is solubilized in pluronic and pluronic mixed micelles (**Section 2.2.1.1**) **b)** the quantification of amount of drug release from different pluronic micellar formulations (**Section 2.2.1.2**).

2.2.1.1 Solubilization study of hydrophobic drugs

Direct dissolution method was adopted to study the solubilization of various hydrophobic drugs in pure pluronic micelles and mixed micelles of pluronic with other surface active agents. Pre weighed amount of pluronics and other amphiphiles (Bile salt/SAILs) was dissolved in 5 mL double distilled water and then drug was added in excess to pluronics and mixed pluronic-amphiphiles solutions. These solutions were stirred at $37\pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$; following this, the samples were filtered using millipore filter (0.20 μm) to remove unloaded drug. The concentration of the solubilized drug in pluronic and pluronic-amphiphiles mixed micelles was determined using absorbance measurements made on Shimadzu (UV-1800) UV-visible double beam spectrophotometer. All experiments were performed in triplicates. The molar absorption coefficient of different drugs was determined using slope of calibration curve (absorbance versus concentration of drug). From the molar absorption coefficient value, concentration of loaded amount of drug was computed.

Experimental

Figure 2.1: Shimadzu UV-1800 UV-visible Spectrophotometer

2.2.1.2 *In vitro* release of different hydrophobic drugs

In vitro release profiles of different hydrophobic drugs from pure and mixed micelles of pluronics with amphiphiles were evaluated using dialysis release method. 2 mL solution of different drug loaded pluronic and pluronic mixed micellar solution was packed into a dialysis membrane bag (Himedia, molecular weight cut off between 12,000 to 14,000) and submerged into 100 mL of a phosphate buffered saline solution (pH=7.4) which acts as release medium to mimic biological conditions except oxcarbazepine (OXC) drug where 0.5 % w/v sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) was used as release medium. The dialysis release system was maintained at $37\pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ with constant stirring at 150 rpm. Samples were taken from release medium at regular specified time interval and media was replenished with same volume of fresh release media. The collected samples were filtered using $0.45\ \mu\text{m}$ filters prior to determining the amount of drug release using UV-visible spectrophotometer at their corresponding values of λ_{max} .

2.2.2 Fluorescence measurements

Hitachi F-4600 Fluorometer with quartz cuvette of path length 1 cm was employed for steady-state fluorescence measurements (**Figure 2.2**). Fluorescence measurements were performed to find out the *cmc* values and solubilization locus of drug in pure and mixed micelles of pluronics.

Figure 2.2: Hitachi F-4600 Fluorescence Spectrofluorometer

2.2.2.1 Determination of critical micellization concentration (*cmc*)

The *cmc* values of pure and mixed micelles of pluronics were determined using Hitachi F-4600 Fluorescence spectrophotometer at $37 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$. All the measurements were carried out by taking pyrene concentration equal to 10^{-6} mol/dm^3 . The excitation wavelength and the emission spectra for pyrene were recorded at 334 nm and wavelength range of 350-550 nm respectively. Variation in ratio of first and third vibronic peak (I_1/I_3) of pyrene with pluronic concentration was monitored as a function of micellar concentration. Fluorescence titrations were performed by successive addition of concentrated stock solutions to pyrene solution. The temperature was controlled using an automated thermostat from ORBIT RS with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$.

2.2.2.2 Drug location study by micropolarity measurements

Photoluminescence quenching of pyrene was exploited to find out the locus of hydrophobic drug solubilized in pure and mixed pluronic micelles. Blank micelles labelled with probe were titrated against hydrophobic drug loaded micelles.² The ratio of first to third vibronic peaks (I_1/I_3) of the pyrene emission spectrum sense the polarity of medium in which it is dissolved. It helps to find out the location of encapsulated hydrophobic drug.

Experimental

2.2.3 Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) measurements

ITC measurements were undertaken to find out the possible location of solubilized hydrophobic drug in different pluronic micelles. Besides, the enthalpy change assisting the titration of a pluronic copolymer stock solution in the absence and presence of OXC was monitored by MicroCal iTC200 calorimeter (**Figure 2.3**) at $37\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$. The titrations were performed by adding $2\ \mu\text{L}$ aliquots of pluronic stock solutions to $240\ \mu\text{L}$ of $0.004\ \text{mM}$ aqueous OXC drug solution using Hamilton syringe and repeated twice. Blank experiment was performed by titrating pluronics stock solution in water.

Figure 2.3: MicroCal iTC200 from GE Healthcare Life Sciences

2.2.4 Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR) measurements

^1H NMR experiments were performed using Bruker 500 MHz NMR spectrophotometer to find out the possible locus of hydrophobic drug in pure pluronic micelles and pluronic-SAILs mixed micelles (**Figure 2.4**). For this study, 5% w/v of all pluronics- D_2O solutions saturated with hydrophobic drug were used. Chemical shift of these solutions were recorded in δ (ppm) scale and tetramethylsilane (TMS) ($\delta=0.000$ ppm) scale was used as reference scale.

Figure 2.4: Bruker Ascend 500 NMR spectrometer

2.2.5 Dynamic light scattering (DLS) and Zeta (ζ) potential measurements

The hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of pluronics and pluronic mixed micelles in the presence and absence of drug was measured using a Malvern Zetasizer Nanoseries Nano-ZS instrument equipped with He-Ne laser ($\lambda = 632.8$ nm) at 37°C and scattering angle of 173° (**Figure 2.5**). The instrument temperature was controlled by in-built temperature controller having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$. All the samples were filtered with millipore 0.45 μm filter to avoid the interference of contaminants.

Figure 2.5: Zetasizer Nano Z from Malvern Instruments Ltd

Experimental

From DLS outputs, diffusion coefficients of the micelles in solution were obtained and corresponding D_h values were calculated using Stoke-Einstein relationship as per equation:

$$D = \frac{k_B T}{3\pi\eta D_h}$$

Where η is the viscosity of solvent, T is absolute temperature and k_B is the Boltzmann constant.

Long term stability and dilution stability

Change in D_h of CLZ loaded pluronic-sodium deoxycholate (SDC, bile salt) mixed micellar formulations and eye inspection method were employed for long term stability study. The dilution stability of CLZ loaded pluronic-SDC mixed micelles were investigated by incubating them in water in 30-480 fold dilutions at 37°C for 24 hours. The changes in D_h values were analyzed by employing the method mentioned in the DLS measurements.

2.2.6 Small-Angle neutron scattering (SANS) measurements

The SANS measurements were carried out to determine the size and shape of micelles formed by pure and mixed pluronic solutions before and after the solubilization of hydrophobic drugs. It is a diffraction experiment which involves the scattering of monochromatic beam of neutrons from the sample and measures the scattering angle. SANS measurements were performed on indigenously built SANS instrument operating at Dhruva reactor, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC), Mumbai, India (**Figure 2.6**). The incident neutron with a wavelength of 5.2Å (wavelength resolution ($\Delta\lambda/\lambda$) of approximately 15%) and linear position sensitive detector (angular range 0.5–15°) were used to impart Q-range of 0.018 and 0.32 Å⁻¹. All the sample measurements were carried out at 37±0.1°C. Standard operating procedure was used for data correction for background, empty cell contribution, sample transmission and normalized to absolute cross-section.

Figure 2.6: Dhruva reactor, BARC, Mumbai, India

2.2.7 Differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) measurements

Possible location of quercetin (QCT) in pluronic and pluronic-SAILs ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$) mixed micelles was estimated by using differential pulse voltammetric (DPV) measurements. DPV measurements were performed on a PC controlled CHI660D (Austin, USA) electrochemical workstation (**Figure 2.7**). The experiments were carried out using conventional three electrode system configuration consisting of glassy carbon (GC) electrode as working electrode, platinum wire as counter electrode and Ag/AgCl electrode as reference electrode. GC electrode was sequentially polished with slurry of alumina powder and rinsed with doubly distilled water prior to each measurement. All the measurements were performed thrice in acetic acid-sodium acetate (AcOH-NaAc) buffer (pH 5.0).

Figure 2.7: CHI660D Electrochemical Workstation

Experimental

2.2.8 Heat Transfer Method (HTM) measurements

For HTM measurements, <111> p-type silica electrodes from Sigma Aldrich (Gillingham, United Kingdom) were functionalized with 100 μL of micellar solution. Subsequently, these electrodes were dried at $50.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min and mounted in the 3D printed flow cell shown in **Figure 2.8** and flow cell design described in reference.³ After stabilizing for 30 min at 35°C in a phosphate buffer saline (PBS) solution, the temperature was increased to 70°C and subsequently cooled down to starting temperature using a constant heating or cooling rate of 11.67°C/h . Three of these temperature cycles were performed and after the final run, solution was kept at 35°C for 30 min.

Figure 2.8: Schematic lay-out of the 3D printed flow cell

2.2.9 High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) measurements

Shimadzu 2010HT HPLC consist of a low pressure gradient separation module with quaternary mobile phase delivery pump, column temperature controller and UV-visible detector (**Figure 2.9**) was used for determination of locus of solubilization of OXC drug. For the separation, Phenomenex C18 LC column with dimensions $4.6\text{ mm} \times 250\text{ mm}$ and $5.0\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ particle sizes was used. Isocratic mode was used with mobile phase consisting of a mixture of 40 volumes of phosphate buffer, 25 volumes of methanol, and 35 volumes of acetonitrile. The pH of mixture was adjusted to 4.0 with ortho-

phosphoric acid. The HPLC was operated with flow rate of 1 mL/minute and injection volume of 20 μ l was maintained at 37°C. The separation was carried out for 30 minutes.

Figure 2.9: Shimadzu 2010HT High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)

2.2.10 Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) measurements

PXRD patterns of pure pluronics, drug, SDC and their physical mixtures were collected on Rigaku miniflex powder diffractometer using a radiation CuK α with 1.54 \AA wavelength (40 mA- 45kV). Data was collected in the 2θ range from 2 $^\circ$ to 60 $^\circ$ (**Figure 2.10**). Smart lab Studio II software was applied to collect PXRD data of samples.

Figure 2.10: Rigaku miniflex powder diffractometer

Experimental

2.2.11 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements

The compatibility of CLZ with different pluronics (F108, F127 and P84) and SDC was investigated using FTIR. FTIR spectra of pure and physical mixtures of CLZ and polymers were recorded on ABB MB3000 FTIR Laboratory Spectrometer (**Figure 2.11**). To prepare pellets, which contained 100 mg of KBr and 1 mg of a sample (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), hydraulic press (Specac, Orpington, UK) was used. The background spectra for each measurement were taken with average of 16 scans.

Figure 2.11: ABB MB3000 FTIR Laboratory Spectrometer

2.2.12 *In vitro* cell viability assay

Cell viability or MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) is a colorimetric assay widely used to assess cell metabolic activity. The presence of number of viable cells is determined by a enzyme known as NAD(P)H-dependent cellular oxidoreductase. This enzyme is responsible for the reduction of MTT dye to a purple colored product, formazan which gives absorbance at 505nm. Only the viable cells are able to convert MTT dye to formazan and thus formation of purple color in this assay serves as a good marker of presence of viable cells. Therefore this cytotoxicity test (MTT) was performed to determine the effect of F108, F108-SAILs, free and micellar QCT on the viability of human breast carcinoma cell line MDA-MB-231. MDA-MB-231 cells (without drug treatment) were used as a disease control to confirm the cell viability. Cells were harvested in a 96 well plate and then were incubated for 24h prior to the addition of F108, F108-SAILs, free QCT and micellar QCT. The

concentration of 3 mM for pluronic F108, F108-SAILs and 100 μ g/ml for free QCT and micellar QCT was taken to investigate their potential cytotoxicity. MDA-MB-231 cells were incubated with above mentioned investigated formulations for a time period of 24h. The absorbance from the cells was measured at 550 nm using a Flex station III spectrophotometer (Sunnyvale, CA, U.S.A) and results were expressed as percentage cell viability, assuming the viability of control cells as 100% (**Figure 2.12**).

Figure 2.12: Flex station III spectrophotometer (Sunnyvale, CA, U.S.A)

2.2.13 DPPH free radical scavenging activity

To investigate the antioxidant activity of pure drugs CLZ and OXC, CLZ unloaded and loaded L64/P84 1:4 (% w/v) and OXC unloaded and loaded L64/F127 1:4 (% w/v) mixed micellar solution, 2,2-diphenyl-1-picryl-hydrazil free radical (DPPH $^{\bullet}$) scavenging assay was performed. DPPH $^{\bullet}$ is a nitrogen radical that is available commercially and can accept hydrogen from an antioxidant. The preparation of 0.1mM DPPH $^{\bullet}$ solution was carried out in methanol. 1 mL of solution was added to 3 mL of pure CLZ and OXC solution; empty mixed micellar solution of L64/P84 1:4 (% w/v) and L64/F127 1:4 (% w/v); CLZ and OXC loaded mixed micellar solution of L64/P84 1:4 (% w/v) and L64/F127 1:4 (% w/v) respectively at different concentrations of 200-1000 μ g/mL. The absorbance of DPPH $^{\bullet}$ was evaluated at 517 nm after 30 min. The color of solution changed from purple to yellow upon the absorption of hydrogen from an investigated formulation by DPPH $^{\bullet}$. The decrease in absorbance of reaction mixture depicts the increase in antioxidant activity. The DPPH $^{\bullet}$ solution serves as control. The

Experimental

potential of DPPH[•] scavenging activity was calculated from the given equation and expressed as a percentage.⁴

$$\text{DPPH scavenging activity (\%)} = (1 - A_s/A_c) \times 100$$

Where A_s is the absorbance of the test sample and A_c is the absorbance of control.

2.2.14 Metal chelating activity

The method of Dinis *et al.*⁵ was used to evaluate the ferrous ions chelating of pure drugs CLZ and OXC, CLZ unloaded and loaded L64/P84 1:4 (%w/v) and OXC unloaded and loaded L64/F127 1:4 (%w/v) mixed micellar solution. In short, the above mentioned drugs, unloaded and loaded mixed micellar formulations at a concentration range of 200-1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ were added to 2mmol/L solution of FeCl_2 (0.05 mL). Further, the addition of 5mmol/L ferrozine (0.2 mL) to above mixture initiated the reaction and mixture was shaken vigorously for 10 min at room temperature. The absorbance of solution was then determined using spectrophotometer at 562 nm. The reaction mixture without investigated formulation was taken as control. The percent inhibition of ferrozine- Fe^{2+} complex formation was calculated relative to control by the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = [(A_c - A_s)/A_c] \times 100$$

Where A_c and A_s stands for the absorbance of the control and test formulations respectively.

2.2.15 Reducing power assay

The method of Oyaizu⁶ was adopted to determine the reducing potential of pure drugs CLZ and OXC; empty mixed micelles of L64/P84 1:4 (% w/v) and L64/F127 1:4 (% w/v); CLZ and OXC loaded mixed micellaes of L64/P84 1:4 (% w/v) and L64/F127 1:4 (% w/v) respectively, in a concentration in dependent manner. This method is based on the reduction of ferricyanide. A mixture was prepared which contained 1 mL of different concentrations ranging from 200-1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of above mentioned test formulations and 2.5 mL of 0.2 M of sodium phosphate buffer (pH=6.6) containing 1% potassium ferricyanide [$\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$]. The above reaction mixture was then further incubated at 50°C for 20 min. After incubation, the reaction mixture was acidified by

adding 2.5 mL of trichloroacetic acid (10%). The acidified sample (2.5 mL) was then incubated with 2.5 mL of distilled water and 0.1% of FeCl₃ (0.5 mL). The absorbance was taken at 700 nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer. The increase in measured absorbance depicts the greater reduction potential of the reaction mixture.

2.2.16 Nitric oxide (NO) scavenging assay

The method of Garrat *et al.*⁷ has been used for the estimation of NO scavenging activity. This is based on the spontaneous decomposition of sodium nitroprusside in aqueous solution which leads to production of nitric oxide (NO) which further generates nitrite ions. Griess reagent (1% sulfanilamide in 2% phosphoric acid and 0.1% naphthylethylenediamine dihydrochloride in water) can be used to quantify these nitrite ions produced when NO reacts with oxygen under aerobic conditions. Scavengers of NO reduce the production of nitrite ions by competing with oxygen. The reaction mixture containing sodium nitroprusside (10 mM) in a PBS solution, pure drugs CLZ and OXC, CLZ and OXC unloaded and loaded L64/P84 1:4 (% w/v) and L64/F127 1:4 (% w/v) mixed micellar solutions respectively at different concentrations ranging from 200-1000 µg/mL was incubated at room temperature for 2h. On completion of incubation period, 0.5 mL of Griess reagent was added and the above reaction mixture without the formulation (blank) was taken as control. The absorbance of chromophore was determined at 546 nm. Suppression of nitrite formation by OXC/CLZ unloaded and loaded mixed micellar formulations and the drug alone was calculated relative to control.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = [(A_0 - A_1)/A_0] \times 100$$

Where A₀ and A₁ stand for the absorbance of control and test sample.

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Chapter 3

Solubilization and In Vitro Release of Hydrophobic Drug Oxcarbazepine (OXC) in Pluronic Micelles

3.1 Introduction

Hydrophobic drugs are common outcome of drug industries; often they have high therapeutic values but encounter a number of challenges to drug delivery.¹ Such hydrophobic drugs can be solubilized and delivered by different strategies such as polymeric micelles or polymeric micelles to which drug is covalently bound and polymer–drug conjugates, liposomes, β -cyclodextrin inclusion complexes, dendrimers and nanoemulsions.²⁻⁹ Solubilization of hydrophobic drug in triblock copolymers (polyethylene oxide-polypropylene oxide- polyethylene oxide, PEO-PPO-PEO), also known as pluronics, is an approachable alternative because they are non-ionic, highly surface-active, non-toxic and US-FDA approved with excellent biocompatibility and biodegradability.¹⁰⁻¹² They self assemble into spherical micelles at/or above their critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) and critical micelle temperature (*cmt*) in dilute aqueous solutions.¹³ These pluronic micelles consist of PEO units forming corona region and PPO units forming the hydrophobic core in both of which drug can be solubilized.¹⁴ The pluronics being capable of modulating the drug efflux transporter P-glycoprotein (P-gp) activity on the blood brain barrier (BBB), hence they enhance the BBB penetration of drugs. Moreover resistance of drugs also present many challenges in the treatment of brain disorders such as brain cancer, epilepsy, schizophrenia, depression and infection of the brain with HIV.¹⁵ Recent findings suggest that in the drug resistance these P-gp are over expressed and the pluronics can act as inhibitors of P-gp, which can be helpful as drug carrier for the treatment of multidrug resistant (MDR) diseases.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

Oxcarbazepine (OXC), chemically 10,11-dihydro-10-oxo-5H-dibenz[b,f]azepine-5-carboxamide is modern antiepileptic drug, classified as

biopharmaceutics classification system (BCS) Class II drug due to its lipophilic nature and has very low water solubility.¹⁹⁻²¹ The poor aqueous solubility of drugs becomes an obstacle *in vivo* because of alteration in its dissolution rate which controls the absorption and bioavailability parameters of oral drug delivery products.²² Thus to improve the therapeutic efficacy of OXC, its aqueous solubility needs to be improved for which the use of pluronic micelles may prove beneficial.

There are various studies comprising pluronics in which their hydrophobic core serves as a microenvironment to enhance the loading efficiency of hydrophobic drugs. Alexander *et al.* studied the solubilization of the hydrophobic drug flurbiprofen and its effect on micellar properties of the different pluronic (P103, P123, and L43) micelles using multiple techniques.²³ The aggregation behaviour of these pluronics is sensitive to the presence of the hydrophobic drug because of the formation of drug/micelle and drug/unimer complexes. The diffusion of pluronic P103 dispersions, with and without flurbiprofen, was studied using PFGSE-NMR. The data showed that P103 alone in D₂O/d₆-ethanol had a hydrodynamic radius of ~6 nm. For samples containing flurbiprofen, the percentage of drug interacting with the polymer micelles increased with the drug concentration and the hydrodynamic radius of the pluronic increased to ~15 nm with the highest drug content. The flurbiprofen attenuation signals in all cases could be fitted to a single diffusion coefficient, indicating that flurbiprofen is in fast exchange between the aqueous solution and the micelle or is fully solubilized. The effect of varying the P103 concentration with a fixed drug concentration was also examined. Flurbiprofen solubility showed a strong dependence on micelle concentration, with a substantial portion, up to 99%, of flurbiprofen solubilized with increased P103 concentration. The interaction between the drug and pluronic P123 was examined, and the result showed that larger pluronics are more appropriate as drug carriers.

Sarkar *et al.* investigated the interactions of curcumin with the pluronic P123/F127 micellar solution and vesicle solution of P123/5-methylsalicylic acid.²⁴ The

formation of vesicles comprising pluronic P123 and 5-methylsalicylic acid has been successfully characterized by light scattering measurement, optical spectroscopy, and eventually microscopic techniques. UV-Visible data in a time-dependent manner suggested that the micellar nanocavity degradation rate suppression by the pluronic micelles resulted in the stabilization of hydrophobic drug curcumin. However, the results of this study described the better efficiency of P123 micelles to agitate the excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT)-related nonradiative decay of curcumin as compared to pluronic F127. The lifespan and emission intensity for the rigid and confined microenvironment of P123/5-methylsalicylic acid vesicles increased as compared to P123 micelles. The whole data of the study indicated that interaction of curcumin with PEO and PPO unit of triblock copolymer is responsible for the modulation of photophysics of curcumin.

Mehta *et al.* studied the loading behaviour of nevirapine drug in mixed micelles of poloxamer 407 and pluronic P123.²⁵ At different weight ratios, the process of micellization has been found to be entropy dominant at low temperature (25°C) and enthalpy driven at high temperatures (30, 35, 40 and 45°C). Small size of the formulation with high zeta potential ensures stability against reticuloendothelial system uptake and aggregation. FTIR, DSC and XRD results indicate that nevirapine drug has sufficient compatibility with the pluronic excipients. The polymeric mixed micellar formulation in consideration confers high entrapment efficiency and sustained release even at lower polymer concentration in contrast to the earlier reports which use very high surfactant concentration. They concluded that these mixed micellar formulations show high entrapment efficiency and sustained release behaviour *in vitro*.

Bahadur and coworkers studied the effect of solubilization of hydrophobic alcohols viz. hexan-1-ol, octan-1-ol and decan-1-ol in different pluronics (P85 and P123) with different hydrophilic–lipophilic balances employing DLS, SANS, fluorescence and viscometry techniques.²⁶ Both these pluronic showed the morphological transitions from sphere to rod like micelles as the temperature increased. Moreover, the higher hydrophobicity and molecular weight of pluronic P123

significantly slowed down the dynamics of the micellar transition. The obtained results showed that the presence of these alcohols significantly influence the growth process rates and restructuring of pluronic micelles. A decrease in aqueous solubility of hydrophobic alcohols from hexan-1-ol to decan-1-ol and increasing alcohol solubilization limits the micellar growth rate. More effective dehydration of the micellar core by alcohols with higher levels of solubilization and hydrophobicity resulted in the decrease in rate of sphere to rod micellar growth. This report emphasized the specific role of additive to induce the dehydration of micellar cores, resulted in the restructuring and growth characteristics of both hydrophilic pluronic P85 and hydrophobic pluronic P123 micelles.

3.2 Present Work

The present work was focussed to enhance the solubility of oxcarbazepine (OXC) in different pluronics viz. F108 (PEO₁₃₃-PPO₅₀-PEO₁₃₃), F127 (PEO₁₀₀-PPO₆₅-PEO₁₀₀) and P84 (PEO₁₃-PPO₄₃-PEO₁₃) micelles and probed the effect of length of the corona on the solubilization of OXC in the core of different pluronic micelles. To the best of our knowledge, we hardly find any study in which solubilization of OXC is reported in any micellar media. The solubilization capacity of different pluronic micelles has been estimated using UV-visible spectroscopy technique. Different solubility parameters viz. Partition coefficient, Gibbs free energy of solubilization and drug loading efficiency has been calculated for all pluronic micellar formulations. Locus of solubilization has been adjudged by employing isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) and proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹H NMR) techniques. Solubilization of OXC in pluronic micelles is further confirmed from dynamic light scattering (DLS) and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) techniques. *In vitro* dialysis method was used to find out the effect of locus of solubilization on the release behaviour of the encapsulated drug OXC in the pluronic micelles. Different kinetic models viz. Zero order release kinetics, First order release kinetics and Higuchi model kinetics was fitted on the drug release data to get further insight on the drug release behaviour. The molecular structures of OXC and pluronics are shown in **Figure 3.1**.

Figure 3.1: Chemical structures (a) Oxcarbazepine (OXC) drug (b) Pluronic.

3.3 Results and Discussion

3.3.1 Solubilization of OXC

The amount of OXC solubilized in water and in different pluronic micelles (P84, F127, F108) was determined by UV-visible spectroscopy. The 40 mM stock solution of OXC was prepared in methanol and further diluted with water for obtaining the desired concentration range of 0.04 mM to 0.20 mM. The amount of the methanol was low enough for directly measuring the UV absorption spectrum and the experiment was performed in triplicate. The λ_{max} of OXC was found out to be 256 nm. The linear calibration curve for the absorbance versus concentration of OXC in water was plotted

and given in **Figure 3.2 (a)** ($r^2 = 0.99889$). The molar absorption coefficient was found to be $8.81 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ determined using slope of the calibration curve. OXC solutions with different pluronics were further diluted 30 times with water for determining the amount of OXC concentration using the molar absorption coefficient. The aqueous solubility of OXC is very low (only 0.435 mM) as obtained from UV absorption spectra shown in **Figure 3.2 (b)**. The representative UV absorption spectra of OXC solubilized in F127, F108 and P84 micelles in concentration range of 0.1% to 5% w/v have been presented in the **Figure 3.3 (a), (b) and (c)** respectively. The UV absorption of the OXC increased markedly in the pluronic solution indicating that the pluronic micelles are able to solubilize a larger amount of the OXC. The solubility pattern of drug in pluronics follows the order $\text{P84} > \text{F127} > \text{F108}$ at all % w/v as shown in **Table 3.1**. Surprisingly, the more amount of OXC solubilized in P84 micelles than the other two pluronics besides the fact that F127 has 65 PPO hydrophobic units and F108 has 50 PPO units in comparison to P84 which has only 43 PPO units. This can also be clearly evidenced visually from the presence of an intense yellow colour in the 5% w/v P84 after OXC solubilization as compared to 5% w/v F127 and F108 where the colour was comparatively less intense as shown in **Figure 3.3(d)**.

Figure 3.2: (a) Absorbance vs. Concentration of OXC drug at 256 nm, (b) UV spectra of OXC solubilized in water.

Table 3.1 Amount of OXC solubilized in micelles of various pluronics (0.1% to 5% w/v) at 37°C.

Amount of solubilized OXC drug (mM)						
Pluronic	0.1 % w/v	1 % w/v	2 % w/v	3 % w/v	4 % w/v	5% w/v
P84	0.980	1.38	1.75	2.45	3.77	7.08
F127	0.885	1.04	1.64	1.99	2.53	3.53
F108	0.824	0.936	1.20	1.67	1.90	2.28

Figure 3.3: UV spectra of OXC solubilized in the micelles of (a) F127 (b) F108 and (c) P84 at different concentrations (1) 0.1% w/v (2) 1% w/v (3) 2% w/v (4) 3% w/v (5) 4% w/v and (6) 5% w/v aqueous solutions at 37°C (d) Photographic images of OXC

loaded 5% w/v pluronics (A) P84 (B) F127 (C) F108 and schematic representation of proposed location of OXC in these pluronic micelles.

The higher solubility in case of P84 can be attributed to more hydrophobic nature of P84 due to its smaller PEO region (only 38 PEO units) which allows the transfer of OXC into the core region.²⁷ The lower solubilization in case of F127 and F108 can be attributed to their longer corona region acting as a barrier for the movement of OXC in the core resulting in higher solubilization of OXC in the corona region. Also, we observed that solubility was higher in F127 (200 PEO units) as compared to F108 (266 PEO units). Liveri *et al.* also reported that the thickness of the hydrophilic PEO corona region of the copolymers acts as a steric barrier and slows down the solubilization of tamoxifen drug into the core.²⁸ The intrication in solubility of OXC in pluronic aqueous solutions was also due to the polar nature of OXC, owing to the presence of its carboxamide substituent and hydrophobic nature is due to two phenyl moieties.^{29,30} The OXC has a structural analogy with carbamazepine drug, which is also a polar drug reported elsewhere.³¹ A study documented that polar hydrophobic molecules can interact with both core (PPO) as well as corona (PEO) regions of the pluronic micelles.^{32,33}

Drug loading efficiency is the percentage of solubilized OXC from the original OXC feed in different pluronic micelles and represented as (3.1)

$$\text{Drug loading efficiency} = \frac{\text{weight of drug in micelles}}{\text{weight of drug fed initially}} \times 100 \quad (3.1)$$

As presented in **Table 3.2** the drug loading efficiency of the pluronic P84 micelles was higher than other two pluronics at all % w/v indicating the higher drug loading efficiency of the pluronic P84 micelles.³⁴

Table 3.2: Drug loading efficiency of various pluronic micelles (0.1% to 5% w/v) at 37°C.

Drug loading efficiency (%)						
Pluronics	0.1 % w/v	1 % w/v	2 % w/v	3 % w/v	4 % w/v	5% w/v
P84	13.61	19.16	24.30	34.02	52.36	98.33
F127	12.29	14.44	22.17	27.63	35.13	49.02

F108	11.44	13.00	16.66	23.19	26.38	31.66
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The micellar/water partition coefficient can be calculated from UV-visible results and is defined as the ratio of drug concentration in the micelle to the drug concentration in water for a particular surfactant concentration and is given by relation (3.2)

$$P = \frac{S_{tot} - S_w}{S_w} \quad (3.2)$$

where S_{tot} and S_w is the total solubility of the drug and solubility of drug in water respectively. The partition coefficient have been calculated, compared and given in **Table 3.3 [Figure 3.4 (a)]** from where it was found that the value of partition coefficient increased by increasing the concentration of the pluronics. Among all the pluronics the highest value of partition coefficient was found in case of P84 which is due to its more hydrophobic microenvironment for solubilized OXC. On the other hand, the lower values of partition coefficient in case of F127 and F108 were due to more solubilization of OXC in the corona regions of the pluronics.

Another parameter called the standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) can be determined from the partition coefficient and is given by the following expression (3.3)

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln P \quad (3.3)$$

where R is the gas constant, T is the temperature (in Kelvin), and P is the partition coefficient between the micelle and the aqueous phase. The ΔG° value depicts the Gibbs free energy of transfer of one mole of the drug in the micellar phase. The ΔG° values were tabulated in **Table 3.3 [Figure 3.4 (b)]** and found to be negative, indicating the spontaneity of the solubilization and transfer of water molecules from the micellar core persuading a more hydrophobic environment and hence leading to spontaneous partition of OXC into the micelles.³⁵⁻³⁹ Higher negative value of ΔG° in the case of P84 was attributed to the more spontaneous solubilization of the OXC in P84 micellar medium. On the other hand in the case of F127 and F108 micellar medium the less negative values of ΔG° signifies that OXC solubilization process was less spontaneous in this case, which can be ascribed to the more amount of the OXC solubilized in the corona region of micelles.

Table 3.3: Values of Partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) in pluronic P84, F127 and F108 micelles (0.1% to 5% w/v) at 37°C.

%w/v)	Partition Coefficient (P)			ΔG° (kJmol ⁻¹)		
	P84	F127	F127	P84	F127	F127
0.1	1.25	1.03	0.89	-0.58	0.04	0.28
1	2.17	1.39	1.15	-2.00	-0.86	-0.36
2	3.48	2.77	1.75	-3.21	-2.85	-1.45
3	4.63	3.57	2.83	-3.95	-3.28	-2.69
4	7.66	4.81	3.36	-5.25	-3.61	-3.13
5	15.27	7.11	4.24	-7.029	-4.04	-3.72

Figure 3.4: Micellar/water Partition coefficient and (b) Standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) of different pluronics from the concentration range of 0.1% to 5% w/v [▲] F108, [●] F127 and [■] P84.

3.3.2 Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) measurement

Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) is a powerful and very sensitive technique extensively used to study interactions between molecules in dilute aqueous solutions.⁴⁰ We have exploited this technique for understanding the nature of interactions as well as the location of solubilization of OXC in the different pluronics micellar medium. The concentrated solutions of pluronics (5% w/v) were titrated into water and 0.004 mM

OXC solution. Since the experiments have been performed at 37°C, the enthalpograms which did not exhibit the sigmoidal shape are presented in **Figure 3.5**. Bouchemal *et al.* reported similar results in the case of pluronic F127 and they acceded that at higher temperature, the association of unimers into micelles occurred at very low concentrations of pluronics in the measurement cell. The *cmc* is thus attained from early injections from an abrupt change in the heat of micellization. Once the aggregation concentration of F127 is reached, no further dissociation of the micelles takes place and the small heat changes observed were only due to the dilution of micelles.⁴¹ The ITC experiment was used to determine the heat changes evolved during the interaction of different pluronics with the OXC at 37°C. As observed from the **Figure 3.5**, the enthalpogram for the titration of pluronics in OXC solutions show significant changes as compared to enthalpogram obtained from titration of respective pluronics into water, which can be attributed to the interactions between the pluronic and OXC.⁴²

It is worthy to mention that the enthalpy scale of three pluronics were different. The difference in the enthalpy scale arises due to the difference in the hydrophilicity of the pluronic micelles. The total enthalpy change increases with increase in pluronic hydrophilicity and F108 being more hydrophilic showed higher enthalpy change.⁴³ The enthalpogram obtained from dilution of the F127 shows exothermic heat flow referring to the endothermic enthalpy change. Compared to dilution curve, the addition of F127 to OXC drug solution shows less exothermic heat flow signifying less endothermic nature of the process. Similar results have been observed in case of titration of pluronic F108 in the OXC drug solution.

Thus it can be concluded that similar type of interactions are taking place between the OXC and the pluronics (F127 and F108) due to the presence of longer PEO region in them. The transfer of OXC into outer PEO regions or hydrated corona region and in hydrated PPO region to some extent can be held responsible for observed overall net exothermic process. Also the possibility of H-bonding between ether oxygen of pluronics and carboxamide moiety of drug can not be ruled out as it leads to exothermicity of process. Similar results have been suggested by the Danino *et al.* in the case of β -casein unstructured protein, its backbone peptide bond hydrogens can participate in H-bonding with PEO region of the Lutrol F127 block copolymer.⁴⁴ Thus,

it can be concluded various interactions such as hydrogen bonding or/and van der Waals interactions are involved in the solubilization of the OXC along with the hydrophobic forces which makes the overall process less endothermic in nature.⁴⁵ Conversely in pluronic P84, the enthalpy changes become more endothermic in presence of OXC as compared to enthalpy changes obtained in absence of OXC. In the case of hydrophobic pluronic P84, the observed endothermic enthalpy changes can be attributed to the dehydration of the PPO block copolymer micelle upon interaction with OXC indicating that hydrophobic interactions play a major role in the solubilization process rather than other forces of interactions.^{46, 47}

Figure 3.5: ITC curve of concentrated pluronic solution titrated in water and OXC solution at 37°C (a) F127 (b) P84 (c) F108.

The ITC results hence proved useful to find out the location of drug in the pluronic micelles that varies in PEO content. These results clearly highlighted the important difference in the mode of interactions operating between hydrophilic pluronics (F127 and F108) and hydrophobic pluronic (P84) with the OXC. The reason for this behaviour can also be accounted for slower restructuring of the hydrophilic pluronics F127 and F108 due to their larger size as compared to P84. This difficulty in the restructuring of the hydrophilic pluronics in turn, results in the larger interaction of drug with their corona region.⁴⁸ The higher solubilization of OXC in P84 was due to the more amount of the OXC solubilized in the core region formed by PPO through the predominance of hydrophobic interactions. On the other hand in hydrophilic F108 and F127, the less endothermic changes occurring due to interactions of OXC mainly with PEO region which confers that it was more solubilized in the corona region and complies with our UV-visible results.

3.3.3 Proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹H NMR) measurements

To scrutinize the information about the molecular interactions between the solubilized OXC within the pluronic micelles, proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹H NMR) measurements were employed. From the interpretation of the ¹H NMR spectrum of 5% w/v F127 in D₂O, the singlet at ~1.098 ppm is attributed to protons of PPO-CH₃ groups and the additional broad peaks at ~3.379 and ~3.479 ppm belong to the protons of PPO-CH groups and PPO-CH₂ groups respectively. A sharp peak at ~3.651 ppm belongs to the protons of PEO-CH₂ group. The signal ~4.70 ppm is the residual signal of HDO. It is well known that chemical shift in ¹H NMR spectra can be deployed to find out the locus of solubilization of drug in the micelles and penetration of protons into nonpolar or polar media would possibly leads to upfield or downfield shifts due to the change of the micro environment of the protons.⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ To interpret the locus of solubilization of OXC in the pluronic micelles, the chemical shift of PPO-CH₂, PEO-CH₂ and PPO-CH₃ signals have been determined. In the presence of OXC the protons of PEO-CH₂, PPO-CH₂, PPO-CH and PPO-CH₃ of pluronic P84 showed an upfield shift of 0.0268 ppm, 0.1296 ppm, 0.1547 and 0.0403 ppm respectively.

It is important to mention here that signals from the protons of OXC were absent, indicating that OXC was solubilized in pluronic micelles and their peaks are suppressed by the pluronics due to their restricted mobility.⁵² The observed chemical shifts in both PPO and PEO proton revealed that polar OXC interact with both PPO block forming core and PEO units forming corona. But the higher chemical shift in the PPO region confirms that more OXC is located in PPO region. While in case of pluronic F127 and F108, the PPO protons experienced a small upfield shift as compared to the P84 depicted in the **Table 3.4**. A large upfield shift in the PEO-CH₂ protons might be due to the dehydration of corona region on interaction with OXC as the interaction of the drug gives rise to competition between water and OXC to bind with the PEO-CH₂ of pluronics.⁵³ It is expected that the polar part of the OXC interacted with PEO-CH₂ due to which water moved from the corona region and hence an upfield shift occur in PEO-CH₂ protons. OXC penetrate into the hydrated PEO corona which will decrease the hydrophilicity of the micelles. The PPO protons showed an upfield shift on interaction with hydrophobic part of OXC. We observed higher chemical shift in PPO protons as compared to PEO protons which confirms stronger interaction of OXC with PPO block. As compared to F127, the PPO protons show higher chemical shift in P84 in the presence of OXC complying with our UV-visible results that more OXC located in core of P84 micelles. ¹H NMR data also supported these findings because there were small upfield shift in the PPO proton of F127 and F108 which revealed that more hydrophilic nature of these pluronics was responsible for less interaction of OXC with PPO region.

Table 3.4 ¹H NMR chemical shift values of PEO-CH₂, PPO-CH₂, PPO-CH and PPO-CH₃ of different pluronics in D₂O and in presence of OXC drug.

System	PEO-CH ₂ - signal (δ ppm)	PPO-CH ₂ - signal (δ ppm)	PPO-CH- signal (δ ppm)	PPO-CH ₃ - signal (δ ppm)
P84	3.6488	3.5788	3.4789	1.0989
P84+OXC	3.6220	3.4492	3.3242	1.0586
F127	3.6510	3.4798	3.3798	1.0987
F127+OXC	3.6468	3.4740	3.3731	1.0943
F108	3.6637	3.4951	3.3759	1.1024
F108+ OXC	3.6544	3.4953	3.3759	1.1062

After one week precipitation of OXC was observed in the case of both the hydrophilic pluronics F127 and F108, while P84 did not show OXC precipitation even after 3 months storage. So these observations complies well with our ^1H NMR results that PPO interactions (hydrophobic interactions) are very important for solubilization of OXC in the case of P84. But in the case of F127 and F108, OXC was solubilized in the corona region so it tends to precipitate out with time due to competition between the water and OXC to bind with the corona region.

3.3.4 High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) measurements

Immobilised artificial membranes (C-18 column) are largely exploited to determine the eluted peak retention time of drug and are proved to be fast and reliable method to study drug distribution systems and mimic the biological properties.⁵⁴ High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) chromatogram of pure OXC drug and after its solubilization in different pluronic medium was recorded to determine their interaction with artificial membranes. The chromatogram has been shown in **Figure 3.6** and it is clear from the figure that retention time of the drug without pluronics was 5.108 minutes which got increased after its solubilization in the pluronics i.e. 9.955, 9.960 and 9.962 minutes for P84, F127 and F108 respectively.

Figure 3.6: HPLC chromatogram of (a) Pure OXC drug (b) OXC drug in P84 micelles (c) OXC drug in F127 micelles (d) OXC drug in F108 micelles.

There is an accountable difference between eluted peak retention time of pure OXC drug and after its solubilization in different pluronic media indicating the presence of interactions between OXC and pluronic micelles which enhances the partitioning of the drug in the artificial membrane. Dar *et.al* reported similar results in case of co-solubilization of carbamazepine and nifedipine drug as the retention time was found to be increased after the co-solubilization of drugs in mixed surfactant media and they acceded that there are interactions between the drug and surfactant media.³¹ The small increased eluted peak retention time in case of hydrophilic pluronics, F108 and F127 may be attributed to the more solubilization of drug in corona region making it available to bind with hydrophobic C-18 column. However, in case of hydrophobic P84, as more amount of drug is present in the core it experiences lesser extent of hydrophobic interaction with C-18 column hence gets eluted little faster.

3.3.5 Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) is very versatile technique for the determination of size and change in the size of the colloidal particles.⁴⁸ Size of drug carrier is also important in drug delivery because it plays an important role in drug accumulation and penetration in cells i.e. the micelle size should be large enough for circulation as well as small enough for their penetration.⁵⁵ To understand the effect of drug solubilization on the micellar size of the pluronics, DLS studies were performed for loaded and empty micellar solutions. For the empty micelle, pluronics were dissolved in the aqueous medium, and for loaded micelles equilibrated pluronic OXC solutions were used. From the DLS measurements, it has been observed that there is no effect of concentration on the hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of the micelles, as with increase in the concentration of pluronics (F127, F108 and P84) from 0.1% to 5% w/v the D_h of micelle does not change. The intensity weighted size distribution plots of the empty and OXC loaded pluronic micelles were presented in **Figure 3.7**. The D_h value of empty micelles of P84, F127 and F108 was found to be 13.54, 21.04 and 24.36 \pm 0.1 nm respectively. The larger micellar size in F108 and F127 was due to the greater length of the dominating PEO regions. On the other hand after the solubilization of OXC in the pluronics the D_h of OXC loaded micelles were 15.69, 24.26 and 28.21 \pm 0.1 nm, respectively. So a

significant difference observed between the D_h of the unloaded and loaded micelles of different pluronics indicated that OXC has got solubilized in the micelles of the pluronics and it was responsible for swelling of the micelles.

Figure 3.7: Intensity weighted size distribution plot for 5% w/v pluronic micelles before and after loading OXC at 37°C (a) P84 (b) F127 (c) F108.

3.3.6 *In vitro* drug release

There is a great significance to determine the *in vitro* drug release from the micellar medium since it provides an idea about their behaviour *in vivo*.²⁵ Locus of solubilized

drug in the polymeric micelles significantly affected the drug release, as if drug is located in micellar core it will take more time to release than if it is present in the corona region.⁵⁶ To determine the effect of locus of OXC solubilization in different 5% w/v pluronics (F108, F127 and P84) on the *in vitro* release, the dialysis bag method has been employed. 0.5% w/v sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) solution was used to provide sink conditions for release of OXC from three different pluronics at 37°C. SDS, as an anionic surfactant, is usually added into dissolution (release) media to improve solubility of poorly water soluble drugs.⁵⁷ The cumulative % release was found to be significantly slowed down by the solubilization of OXC in the pluronics and were presented in **Figure 3.8**. It can be observed that the smaller sized P84 micelles (15.69 nm) showed the slower release in comparison to the larger pluronic F127 (21.04 ± 0.1 nm) and F108 (24.36 ± 0.1 nm) micelles despite the fact that larger size drug carrier results in slower release the drug and vice versa.⁵⁸

Figure 3.8: *In vitro* release of OXC from different pluronic micelles at 37°C each point represents average ± SD (n = 3).

The reason for obtaining such results can be ascribed to entrapment of OXC in the core region of P84 micelles resulting in slower release. Whereas higher OXC is being located in the outer corona region of F108 and F127, it showed a faster release rate due to the higher hydrophilicity of these pluronic micelles. Similar results were

reported by Fontana *et al* in the case of Amoxicillin-loaded polyethylcyanoacrylate nanoparticles, where they observed that by increasing the coating of PEG (Polyethylene glycol) on the nanoparticles resulted in faster release of amoxicillin drug. Absorption of PEG on nanoparticles resulted in the increased hydrophilicity of nanoparticles leading to faster release of drug.⁵⁹

The release profiles shows that initially there is a burst release of OXC i.e. 60%, 54% and 50% from pluronic micelles of F108, F127 and P84 respectively. After this burst release, the release profile of OXC slowed down and takes more time to be released. It indicated that OXC release followed sustained release behaviour from pluronic micelles which have been well documented in literature.⁶⁰ There are different kinetic models which are used for explaining drug release behaviour as described below.

3.3.6.1 Zero order release kinetics

Zero order release is the ideal method of drug release in order to achieve a pharmacological prolonged action. The pharmaceutical dosage forms following zero order release kinetics releases the same amount of drug by unit of time and is given by equation (3.4) as follows.

$$Q_t = Q_0 + K_0 t \quad (3.4)$$

Where Q_t is the cumulative amount of drug release at time “ t ”, Q_0 is the initial amount of drug and K_0 is the zero order release constant. It describes the systems where the drug release rate is independent of the concentration of the dissolved drug.⁶¹

3.3.6.2. First order release kinetics

The application of this model in drug dissolution studies was first explained by Gibaldi and Feldman in 1967 and they concluded that release of drug from pharmaceutical dosage forms depend upon the constant proportion of the drug concentration available at that time.⁶² The release of a drug which follows first order kinetics can be expressed by the equation (3.5):

$$\text{Log } Q_t = \text{Log } Q_0 - K_t 2.303 \quad (3.5)$$

Where Q_t is the cumulative amount of drug release at time “ t ”, Q_0 is the initial amount of drug and K_t is the first order release constant.

3.3.6.3. Higuchi model kinetics

The first example of a mathematical model aimed to describe drug release from matrix devices, where the drug loading exceeds the solubility in the matrix medium was proposed by Higuchi in 1961. The Higuchi equation suggests that the drug is released by diffusion.^{63,64} The release of the drug which follows Higuchi model kinetics can be expressed by the equation (3.6):

$$Q_t = K_H \cdot t^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3.6)$$

Where Q_t the cumulative amount of drug release at time “ t ” and K_H is the Higuchi release constant.

The drug release profiles were fitted to above described kinetic models and correlation coefficient (R^2) and rate constant (K) values were calculated for all three models and presented in **Table 3.5**. The most appropriate model was chosen based on the best goodness of fit. In the case of OXC release from the F127 and F108 micelles the R^2 values obtained from the Higuchi model are higher as compared to other models, suggesting that OXC release from these micelles follows Higuchi model and the process is diffusion controlled. In contrast, for P84 micelles the R^2 values are higher in case of first order kinetics than other two models indicating that the OXC release followed first order release kinetics.

Table 3.5 Rate constants and regression correlations using different kinetic model for the release behaviour of OXC from the different pluronic micelles.

System	Zero order kinetics		First order kinetics		Higuchi model kinetics	
	R^2	K_0 (h ⁻¹)	R^2	K_t (h ⁻¹)	R^2	K_H (h ⁻¹)
F108	0.9662	9.9303	0.9823	0.1942	0.9945	35.6740
F127	0.9452	9.6374	0.9766	0.1639	0.9908	35.9250
P84	0.8438	4.4698	0.9641	0.0620	0.9449	22.4550

3.4 Conclusions

In this work, we studied the solubilization of hydrophobic drug OXC in pluronic (P84, F127 and F108) micelles differing in their PEO content as well as the interactions present between the drug and the polymer using variety of techniques. From the obtained results, we concluded that by altering the length of corona region of pluronic micelles the solubilization capacity as well as its *in vitro* release behaviour of hydrophobic drug can be modulated. The results from UV-visible measurements revealed that P84 is the best solubilizer for the OXC among the investigated pluronics. This is attributed to its smaller PEO region of pluronic micelles that allows most of OXC to get solubilized in core. The difference between the ITC enthalpograms of hydrophilic pluronics (F127 and F108) and hydrophobic pluronic (P84) highlights the different mode of interaction of OXC with these pluronics. The chemical shift in the proton of pluronics was found to be very useful to find out the location of the OXC in the pluronic micelles and understand the reason behind the lesser solubilization of the drug in F108 and F127 micelles. *In vitro* drug release study evidenced that the locus of solubilization has a great impact on their drug release. The OXC being solubilized in the core of P84 micelles takes more time to release as compared to hydrophilic pluronics i.e. F127 and F108 where most of OXC is solubilized in the corona region. So we can use P84 pluronic micelles as nano drug carrier due to its high loading capacity and stable formulation even after 3 months. Thus, the present findings can prove useful in delivering such type of polar hydrophobic drugs in the different pluronic micelles as optimum size of the corona facilitates the solubilization of the polar hydrophobic drugs.

3.5 References

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Chapter 4

Sodium Deoxycholate Mediated Enhanced Solubilization and Stability of Hydrophobic Drug Clozapine in Pluronic Micelles

4.1 Introduction

Delivery of hydrophobic drugs via suitable means is still a challenge for drug industries as well as for pharmaceutical scientists because of unfavourable solubility, stability and toxicity that hinder the therapeutic efficacy.¹ Pluronic micelles have been extensively investigated for delivering a number of hydrophobic drugs and pluronic copolymers may play an important role in the innovative design of new nanomedicines in near future.^{2,3} Pluronics, the triblock copolymers are made up of poly (ethylene oxide) (PEO) and poly (propylene oxide) (PPO) blocks with the general formula $(\text{PEO})_n\text{-(PPO)}_m\text{-(PEO)}_n$.⁴ These polymers possess the ability to interact with hydrophobic surfaces and biological membranes; hence they are gaining increasing interest in the field of biomedicine. Due to amphiphilic nature, these triblock copolymers act as a surfactant. They self-assemble into micelles at/above the critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) or critical micelle temperature (*cmt*) in aqueous solutions. In addition to being non-toxic, biocompatible and biodegradable, the pluronic micelles possess distinct features such as smaller size, longer circulation times, steric and kinetic stability.⁵⁻¹⁰ These advantageous properties make them suitable for solubilizing and transporting drugs. Since the drug loaded micelles undergo significant dilution upon administration in blood stream this may lead to the dissociation of polymeric micelles which have higher *cmc*. Alternatively, the mixing of polymeric micelles with other polymers or surfactant result in mixed micelles with lower *cmc*, better loading efficiency and higher stability.

In this regard, there are number of reports in literature where pluronics in conjunction with other surfactants or solvents have been investigated for drug delivery

applications. Parmar *et al.* studied the solubilization of hydrochlorothiazide (HCT) in mixed micelles comprising pluronics *viz.* P103, P104 and P105 and cationic surfactant of the type alkyltrimethylammonium bromide (C_n TAB).¹¹ Pluronic-surfactant mixed micellar systems were found to be more efficient for HCT loading. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements revealed that hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of micelle decreased upon the addition of CTAB type cationic surfactant to micellar solution of pluronics. A decrease in size was attributed to the induction of charge on nonionic pluronic micelles by the presence of trace amounts of cationic surfactant. The efficiency of surfactants to decrease micellar size depends on the alkyl chain length of the surfactants. However, cloud point (CP) results showed a progressive increase in the cloud point of 5% pluronics solutions. The solubilization and release profiles of the poorly water soluble drug hydrochlorothiazide (HCT) were investigated in 5% pluronic P103 and in P103- C_{14} TAB systems. It was observed that the loading efficiency of HCT was better in case of pluronic-surfactant system than the pure pluronic and moreover their loading capacity can be tuned by altering the concentration and pH of the surfactant. A rate controlled release of HCT was observed in case of P103- C_{14} TAB mixed micellar system as compared to P103 and *in vitro* release profile was further explained by employing different kinetic models. Kabanov *et al.* prepared the mixed micelle formulations comprising hydrophobic pluronics (L121, L101, L81, and L61) and hydrophilic pluronics (F127, P105, F87, P85 and F68) for the solubilization of model water-insoluble dye, Sudan (III).¹² In most cases, pluronic mixtures were not stable, revealing formation of large aggregates and phase separation within 1-2 days. However, stable aqueous dispersions of the particles were obtained upon **(a)** sonication of the pluronic mixtures for 1 or 2 min or **(b)** heating at 70 °C for 30 min. Among all combinations, L121/F127 mixtures (1:1% weight ratio) formed stable dispersions with a small particle size. The mixed L121/F127 aggregates exhibited approximately 10-fold higher solubilization capacity for Sudan (III) dye as compared to that of F127 micelles. Authors concluded that, stable aqueous dispersions of nanoscale size were prepared from mixtures of hydrophobic and hydrophilic pluronics by using the external

input of energy. The prepared mixed aggregates can efficiently incorporate hydrophobic drug compounds for their application in drug delivery. But these above mentioned studies do not discuss stability of micellar formulations and effect of dilutions on micelles. However, loading capacity and stability of the drug-loaded systems represent a critical aspect in micellar drug delivery. There are some synthetic copolymers micellar formulations which are concerned with increasing the solubilization capacity and providing long term stability. In this context, Park *et al.* had synthesized hydrotropic polymers based on N, N-diethylnicotinamide, which exhibited a high drug loading capacity along with enhanced long-term stability.¹³ Jordan *et al.* have reported the poly-(2-oxazoline) based triblock copolymers used to solubilize paclitaxel drug which were found to be long-term stable for 6 months.¹⁴ But synthesis of the polymers is complicated and much effort is needed to design an efficient and highly stable drug carrier micelle. Understanding the physical chemistry behind the solubilization and stability of these mixed micellar systems may open the tremendous opportunities to design highly stable micellar drug formulations.

Bile salts, which represent another class of anionic surfactants, have been successfully utilized in drug delivery purposes.¹⁵ Bile salts (BS) are biosurfactants synthesized in the liver and secreted into the intestinal lumen where they solubilize cholesterol and other hydrophobic molecules hence facilitating their gastrointestinal absorption.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ In addition they are also proven to have potential for inhibiting precipitation.¹⁸ In order to be used as drug carriers, pluronic micelles require stabilization to prevent degradation caused by significant dilution *in vivo*.¹⁹ There are only few investigations pertaining to the study of mixed aggregates of pluronics and bile salts. Sarkar *et al.* studied the mixed supramolecular aggregate of pluronic P123 (PEO)₂₀-(PPO)₇₀-(PEO)₂₀ with different bile salts, sodium deoxycholate and sodium taurocholate employing dynamic light scattering (DLS) and other spectroscopic techniques DLS results showed that bile salts penetrated into the core–corona region of the P123 micelle and the bile salt–P123 aggregates were formed upon further addition of bile salts.²⁰ At higher molar ratios of bile salt-P123 (41:3), the presence of two types

of complexes was confirmed by CONTIN analysis. Moreover, the absorption-emission spectra of coumarin 153 (C 153) and coumarin 480 (C 480) in the bile salt-P123 aggregate showed that the polarity and hydration of the core-corona region of pluronic P123 micelle was increased upon addition of bile salt. The anisotropy and fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (FCS) measurements also showed the increase in polarity and hydration of the core-corona region in the mixed aggregates. It can be concluded by the temperature dependent anisotropy study that an increase in temperature is responsible for the decrease in microviscosity of both the bile salt-P123 mixed aggregates. Besides, FCS measurements have been conducted for the characterization of bile salt-P123 mixed aggregates using a neutral hydrophobic probe 4-(dicyanomethylene)-2-methyl-6- (p-dimethylamino-styryl)-4H-pyran (DCM) and a cationic probe rhodamine 6G perchlorate (R6G). The translational diffusion became fast in case of DCM due to the increased hydration in the core region of the bile salt-P123 mixed micelle. However, totally opposite results were observed in case of the cationic probe R6G because of its favorable electrostatic interaction with the negatively charged head groups in the bile salt-P123 mixed aggregate. From the results of the study, authors concluded that the bile salt-P123 mixed micelle is a stable confined system and can be applied in the pharmaceutical field in future.

Dar *et al.* have studied the effect of sodium cholate on the micellization and gelation characteristics of pluronic P123 in aqueous media using tensiometry, rheology, dynamic light scattering (DLS) and densitometry.²¹ The suppression of micellization as well as gelation of P123 was confirmed by the profound increase in *cmc*, *cmt* and *cgt* values upon addition of sodium cholate (NaC) to P123. Addition of NaC results in a drastic decrease in the viscosity of pluronic P123 as evidenced by the rheological studies. However, the results of DLS study also supported the rheological study data. DLS measurements showed that the addition of NaC upto 1.5 w/v% firstly decrease the size of mixed micellar aggregates followed by the formation of small and larger sized aggregates at higher concentration of NaC (2.5-10wt%). The aggregation characteristics of P123 micelles were altered by NaC which lead to the reduction in

their encapsulation capacity. Thus, the results clearly evidenced that the presence of biological amphiphiles significantly influenced the aggregation and transport characteristics of P123 formulations. The addition of NaC to P123 retards the achievement of *cmc* and *cmt* which clearly indicated the suppression of micellization as well as gelation of pluronic P123 results in decreased solubilization of pyrene and naproxen. Thus, a systematic investigation focused on developing new pluronic-bile salt mixed system needs to be carried out which may help in choosing appropriate pluronic for use in drug delivery applications from their larger panoply.

4.2 Present Work

In the present work, we have made an attempt to enhance the solubilization efficiency of pluronic micelles by preparing the mixed micelles of pluronics *viz.* P84 (PEO₁₉-PPO₄₃-PEO₁₉), F127 (PEO₁₀₀-PPO₆₅-PEO₁₀₀) and F108 (PEO₁₃₃-PPO₅₀-PEO₁₃₃) and bile salts, sodium deoxycholate (SDC). For this purpose, clozapine (CLZ) was chosen as a model hydrophobic drug which is an atypical antipsychotic with unparalleled efficacy against refractory schizophrenia. CLZ has been implicated with a number of serious risks many of which are potentially fatal *viz.* agranulocytosis, seizures, myocarditis and increased mortality in elderly patients, which limits its clinical use.²²⁻³⁰ Therefore to improve the patient compliance for CLZ, optimization of formulation for CLZ is important for drug delivery. UV-visible spectroscopy has been exploited to determine the solubilization capacity of the investigated micellar systems in terms of drug loading efficiency, average number of drug molecules solubilized per micelle (n_s), partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°). Mixed micelle formation and solubilization of CLZ in the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles was confirmed from dynamic light scattering (DLS) and small angle neutron scattering (SANS) measurements. Micropolarity measurements have been performed to find the locus of solubilization of CLZ in these micelles. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) patterns were recorded to find out any incompatibility between CLZ and drug carriers. Furthermore, the dilution and storage stability of pluronic-SDC mixed micellar formulations was investigated using

DLS technique. The aim of the present work is to develop mixed micellar formulations with increased encapsulation efficiency as well as excellent storage and dilution stability. The molecular structures of pluronics, SDC and CLZ are shown in **Figure 4.1**.

Figure 4.1: Molecular structure of (a) Pluronic, (b) Clozapine (CLZ) and (c) Sodium deoxycholate (SDC).

4.3 Results and Discussion

4.3.1 Clozapine (CLZ) drug solubilization study

CLZ is poorly soluble in water so in order to enhance their solubilization pluronic micellar solution at a concentration far above the *cmc* has been used at 37°C.³¹⁻³⁵ The yellow coloration of CLZ loaded pluronic solutions reveals that aqueous solubility of drug has been increased starkly in pluronic micelles due to solubilization. Further, the concentration of the solubilized CLZ in pluronic and pluronic-SDC mixed micelles was

determined using absorbance measurements made on Shimadzu (UV-1800) UV-visible double beam spectrophotometer. The 2 mM stock solution of CLZ was prepared in methanol and further diluted with water for obtaining the desired concentration range of 0.01 mM to 0.1 mM. The λ_{\max} of CLZ was found out to be 292 nm and amount of the methanol was low enough for directly measuring the UV absorption spectrum. The molar absorption coefficient of CLZ was found to be $10.54 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ determined using slope of the calibration curve (absorbance versus concentration of CLZ). From this molar absorption coefficient, concentration of loaded amount of CLZ was computed. At 12 % w/v of pluronic, the solubilization capacity of CLZ increases in the following order F108 < F127 < P84 (**Table 4.1**). This could be explained by the higher hydrophobicity and smaller length of corona region of pluronic P84 as compared to other two pluronics.³⁶ However, these pluronic formulations were not stable and phase separation (precipitation) was observed within 1-2 day(s) upon storage. To overcome this problem, we prepared mixed micelles comprising pluronic and biosurfactants sodium deoxycholate (SDC).

The solubilization study was performed in mixed micelles of 12% w/v pluronic + 20 mM SDC (pluronic-SDC mixed micelles). It was observed that mixed micellar formulations were able to solubilize significantly higher amounts of drug as compared to pure pluronic micelles as shown in **Figure 4.2**. The increase in solubility of CLZ in the pluronic-SDC was due to the change in the micro-environment of these micelles, we expected that the SDC molecules dehydrate the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles and also induces negative charge on these mixed micelles, which is responsible for the electrostatic repulsion between the micelles.³⁷ These assumptions were further confirmed from the micropolarity, SANS and DLS studies. Also, the mixed micellar formulations comprising P84 and SDC showed remarkable stability against precipitation. This could be explained by more density and loose core structure because of the steroid nucleus (4 fused hydrocarbon rings), which may responsible for stronger hydrophobic interaction between CLZ and most hydrophobic pluronic P84 than other two pluronics.³⁸

Table 4.1: Summarized different parameters computed from UV-visible measurements: amount of CLZ solubilized, loading efficiency, CLZ solubilized per micelles, partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°).

System	CLZ solubilized (mg/5 mL)	CLZ loading Efficiency (%)	Average number of CLZ solubilized per micelle	Partition coefficient (P)	ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)
12% w/v P84	11.17	55.85	108	182.27	- 13.42
12% w/v P84 + 20 mM SDC	18.41	92.05	191	301.14	- 14.71
12% w/v F127	6.088	30.44	56	98.89	- 11.84
12% w/v F127 + 20 mM SDC	10.93	49.36	176	178.30	- 13.36
12% w/v F108	4.794	23.97	30	77.65	- 11.22
12% w/v F108 + 20mM SDC	8.5137	42.56	118	138.67	- 12.71

Figure 4.2: UV spectra of CLZ solubilized in different 12% w/v pluronics and pluronic-SDC mixed micelles at 37°C.

Drug loading efficiency is the percentage of solubilized CLZ from the CLZ feed in different pluronic and pluronic-SDC mixed micelles and shown as Equation (4.1).

$$\text{Drug loading efficiency} = \frac{\text{weight of drug in micelles}}{\text{weight of drug fed initially}} \times 100 \quad (4.1)$$

The obtained values of CLZ loading efficiency is tabulated in **Table 4.1**. It has been observed that the CLZ loading efficiency of the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles was higher as compared to pure pluronic micelles proving the higher drug loading efficiency of the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles.¹⁴ Among the all pluronic-SDC mixed micelles, P84-SDC mixed micelles shows the higher drug loading efficiency due to the hydrophobic nature of P84 which allows the easy penetration of hydrophobic part of SDC molecules to form pluronic-SDC mixed micelles resulting in the better hydrophobic environment. The average number of drug molecules loaded per micelle (n_s), can be calculated by following relation:

$$n_s = \frac{(S_{tot} - S_w)N_A}{n_m} \quad (4.2)$$

Where S_{tot} and S_w is the total solubility of the drug and solubility of drug in water, respectively and n_m is the number of micelles per litre of solution, estimated as

$$n_m = \frac{(C_{polymer} - cmc)N_A}{N} \quad (4.3)$$

N_A is Avogadro number and N is the aggregation number, cmc is critical micelle concentration. The cmc values evaluated for pure pluronics as well as pluronic-SDC mixed micelles using fluorimetry is tabulated in **Table 4.2** and values of N are obtained from SANS measurements.³⁸ As seen from **Table 4.1**, the average number of CLZ molecules loaded per micelle is highest in case of P84-SDC mixed micelles supporting the fact that P84-SDC mixed micelles are able to solubilize greater amount of CLZ drug than other investigated pluronic-SDC mixtures.

Table 4.2: *cmc* values for pluronic and pluronic-SDC mixed micelles at 37°C.

System	<i>cmc</i> values (% w/v)
P84	0.0400
F127	0.0356
F108	0.0428
P84 + SDC	0.0356
F127 + SDC	0.0186
F108 + SDC	0.0399

One of the crucial properties constituting the ability of micellar systems as potential drug carrier is the partition coefficient.³⁹ The partition coefficient is defined as the ratio of the drug solubility in micellar phase to that in the aqueous phase for a particular surfactant concentration and is given by relation:

$$P = \frac{S_{tot} - S_w}{S_w} \quad (4.4)$$

Where S_{tot} and S_w is the total solubility of the drug and solubility of drug in water respectively. The partition coefficient (P) of CLZ between micellar phases and aqueous phases was determined using values of solubility in pluronic micelles and in water obtained from UV-visible studies and is tabulated in **Table 4.1**. The large P values observed in the case of all pluronic-SDC mixed micelles than pure Pluronic micelles indicated that CLZ had highly partitioned into the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles. Higher the partition coefficient values in case of pluronic-SDC mixed micelles reveals that the better hydrophobic microenvironment has been formed for solubilized CLZ.^{40,41}

The standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) indicates the spontaneity of the process and calculated from the following expression.

$$\Delta G^{\circ} = -RT \ln P \quad (4.5)$$

Where R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature and P is the partition coefficient. The values of ΔG° obtained from all pluronic-SDC mixed micelles were found to be negative than plain pluronic micelles demonstrating the higher spontaneity of CLZ solubilization in pluronic-SDC mixed micelles (**Table 4.1**).³⁶

4.3.2 Compatibility studies

4.3.2.1 Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) measurements

Since the presence of interactions between the drugs and excipients has a direct impact on the stability and bioavailability of drugs as well as on their therapeutic efficacy. Hence, it becomes indispensable to study the drug-excipient compatibility before the development of dosage forms. Powder X-ray diffraction provides the useful method for expeditious assessment of chemical interaction of drug with drug carriers.⁴² X-ray diffraction patterns recorded individually for CLZ, SDC, pluronics (P84, F127 and F108) and for the mixtures of CLZ-SDC, CLZ-P84, CLZ-F127 and CLZ-F108 are presented in **Figure 4.3 (a)** and **Figure 4.3 (b)** respectively, PXRD pattern of pure CLZ shows sharp peaks at $2\theta=10.4, 17.2, 19.2, 21.2, 23.7$ and 26.0 which complied well with the literature values reported previously for this drug.⁴³ SDC exhibited four sharp peaks at $2\theta = 12.5, 13.5, 15.2$ and 18.3 . Pluronic F127 and F108 show two sharp peaks at $19.02, 23.5$ and $19.02, 23.3$ respectively. The smaller difference in X-ray pattern of these two pluronics may be due to the crystalline characteristic nature of these pluronics and made up of same constituent blocks (PPO and PEO) that only differ in length. Pluronic P84 shows a broad peak which was attributed to amorphous nature of this polymer. The PXRD pattern of CLZ in combination with SDC and pluronics depicted in **Figure 4.3 (b)**, no new peaks in addition to those present in the PXRD patterns of individual CLZ and excipients. Although a decrease in the peak intensity of CLZ was observed. A decrease of peak intensity of CLZ by increasing pluronics and SDC concentration was probably due to the dilution effect. However, absence of any new peaks in the PXRD pattern of the CLZ mixture rules out the chances of any incompatibility between the drug and drug carrier.

Figure 4.3: Powder X-ray diffractogram of (a) Pure CLZ, pluronic F108, pluronic F127, pluronic P84 and SDC. (b) 1:1 physical blend as simple mixtures of pluronic F108 + CLZ, pluronic F127 + CLZ, pluronic P84 + CLZ and SDC + CLZ.

4.3.2.2 Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy measurements

FTIR has also been proved to be complementary tool for obtaining information regarding the possible interactions among the components of the formulations. The physical interaction between CLZ and the excipients have been evaluated by comparison of FTIR spectra of physical mixtures with the individual components as shown in **Figure 4.4**. Since FTIR experiment was performed in physical mixtures. It cannot takes into account the interactions present in solution form. Wave numbers of different functional groups of different surfactants (pluronic and SDC) and CLZ are tabulated in **Table 4.3** and **Table 4.4** respectively.⁴⁴ FTIR spectra of mixtures of drugs with excipients were observed to be similar to the individual ones with no observed shift or broadening of vibration bands. Thus, the FTIR results also confirmed the absence of any physical or chemical interaction between the drugs and the excipients.

Mehta *et al.* reported similar results in case of physical mixtures of nevirapine drug with poloxamer 407 and pluronic P123 and observed no major drug-excipient interactions in FTIR spectra, signifying that nevirapine drug is in harmony with the components of formulation.³¹

Figure 4.4: FTIR spectra of (a) Pure CLZ, pluronic F108, pluronic F127, pluronic P84 and SDC. (b) 1:1 physical blend as simple mixtures of pluronic F108 + CLZ, pluronic F127 + CLZ, pluronic P84 + CLZ and SDC+ CLZ.

Table 4.3: Assignment of FTIR peaks of Pluronic F127, F108 and P84 and Sodium Deoxycholate.

	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Bond
Sodium Deoxycholate	1548 cm ⁻¹	COO ⁻
Pluronic F127, F108, P84	1355 cm ⁻¹	In plane OH bend
	1124 cm ⁻¹	CO stretch

Table 4.4: Assignment of FTIR peaks of CLZ.

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Bond	Functional group
1594,1551 cm ⁻¹	C = N stretching	Aliphatic amine
1358 cm ⁻¹	C-N stretch	Aromatic secondary amine
777 cm ⁻¹	C-Cl stretch	Alkyl halide
999 cm ⁻¹	C-H bending	Alkene

4.3.3 Small angle neutron scattering (SANS) measurements

4.3.3.1 Characterization of pure pluronic micelles

SANS measurements were performed for all the pluronics (P84, F127 and F108) at a concentration of 12 % w/v and the scattering curves are presented in **Figure 4.5**. The SANS distribution curves obtained for pure pluronics shows the presence of correlation peaks which arises due to hard sphere repulsion between the particles. The typical scattering of these non-ionic micelles can be considered to be consisting of a spherical core-shell particle with differing scattering-length densities of the hydrophobic core and hydrophilic shell interacting via a hard sphere potential. The scattering data of pure 12 % w/v pluronics P84, F127 and F108 has been analyzed by considering $F(Q)$ for spherical micelles and $S(Q)$ for the hard sphere.⁴ **Table 4.5** lists the different parameters *viz.* core radius (R_c), polydispersity, hardsphere radius (R_{HS}), volume fraction (ϕ) and aggregation number (N_{agg}) obtained from model fitting of SANS data.

Figure 4.5: SANS data pattern (with error bars in experimental data) for 12 % w/v pluronic P84, F127 and F108 at 37°C.

Table 4.5: Various key model parameters: core radius (R_c), polydispersity, hard sphere radius (R_{HS}), volume fraction (ϕ) and aggregation number (N_{agg}) for 12% w/v P84, F127 and F108 before and after solubilization of CLZ at 37°C.

System	Core radius R_c (nm)	Polydispersity	Hard sphere radius R_{HS} (nm)	Volume fraction ϕ	Aggregation number N_{agg}
12% w/v P84	4.87	0.19	7.46	0.16	117
12% w/v F127	5.51	0.31	9.80	0.25	112
12% w/v F108	4.48	0.39	9.97	0.19	78
12% w/v P84 + CLZ	4.90	0.19	7.51	0.16	115
12% w/v F127 + CLZ	5.58	0.31	9.83	0.25	112
12% w/v F108 + CLZ	4.54	0.39	9.99	0.19	76

The values of core radius (R_c) was observed to be highest for F127 ($R_c=5.51$) micelles followed by F108 ($R_c=4.48$) and P84 ($R_c=4.87$) which is because of the presence of greater number of PPO units in F127 responsible for forming core of the micelles. In spite of having 50 PPO units in F108, core forming region is smaller than P84 which have only 43 PPO units. So from these results one thing is clear, PPO is not a parameter to form core but length of the PEO units i.e. forming corona is also responsible. In F108 there is larger corona forming PEO units (133), that responsible for the more D₂O penetration in the PPO region of F108 micelles than other two pluronic F127 (100 PEO units) and P84 (only 19 PEO units).

Higher values of volume fraction (ϕ) in case of F127 ($\phi = 0.25$) as compared to F108 ($\phi = 0.19$) and P84 ($\phi = 0.16$) signifies greater D₂O penetration in hydrophilic core. The hard sphere radii of P84 ($R_{HS}=7.46$) is less than F108 ($R_{HS}=9.97$) and F127

($R_{HS}=9.80$) because of shorter length of PEO chain of this pluronic. Furthermore, the values of hard sphere radius of all pluronics were observed to be greater than their respective core radii because the interaction radius also involves the shell of the PEO blocks. The value of aggregation number (N_{agg}) was found to decrease in the order P84 > F127 > F108. The least stability of hydrophobic P84 in aqueous medium was responsible for its higher N_{agg} as compared to other two hydrophilic pluronics.⁴⁵ Cosgrove *et al.* has also reported that aggregation number of pluronic micelles increases with decrease in the pluronic size, hydrophilicity and the volume fraction of solvent in the core decreases correspondingly results in the better formation of micelles.⁴⁶

4.3.3.2 Solubilization of CLZ in pure pluronic micelles

The SANS data were also recorded for the pluronic micelles in the presence of hydrophobic drug, CLZ. The various parameters obtained from the model fitting of SANS data are presented in **Table 4.5**. The scattering features of pluronics do not change in the presence of drug which implies that solubilization of drug has no impact on shape of the pluronic micelles, however, it do affects the micellar characteristics. Upon the solubilization of CLZ drug in these pluronic micelles, an increase in the core radius (R_c) as well as hard sphere radius (R_{HS}) of the pluronic micelle was observed which confirms the fact that CLZ has been solubilized in the pluronic micelles. But no major changes in the aggregation number of the pluronic micelles were seen. Only a small decrease in the aggregation number of pluronic P84 and pluronic F108 was observed. As depicted in **Figure 4.6** solubilization of CLZ drug leads to an increase in scattering intensity which revealed that the aggregation characteristics of these three pluronic micelles improve in the presence of CLZ drug. The same behaviour was observed by Ganguly *et al.* who studied the solubilization of three different hydrophobic alcohols in pluronic P123 and P85 micelles and observed that the addition of hydrophobic alcohols dehydrates the pluronic micelles.²

Figure 4.6: SANS data pattern (with error bars in experimental data) for (a) pluronic P84 (b) pluronic F127 and (c) pluronic F108, 12% w/v in the absence and presence of CLZ drug at 37°C.

4.3.3.3 Characterization of pluronic-SDC mixed micelles

As obtained from UV-visible results, pluronic-SDC mixed micelles show improved solubilization and stability of CLZ drug in pluronic P84-SDC mixed micelles. So we firstly characterize the P84-SDC mixed micelles by SANS measurements. **Figure 4.7** presents SANS distribution curves showing the effect of increasing concentration of SDC on 12% w/v P84 micelles. It reveals that as the concentration of SDC is increased, the scattering intensity decreased at low Q values followed by gradual increase in scattering at high Q region. Also, it was observed that the scattering cross section decreases and peak position shifts towards higher Q region. The various

parameters obtained from the fitting of SANS data are presented in **Table 4.6**. A perusal of **Table 4.6** reveals that the values of core radius and hardsphere radius decreased significantly with the addition of SDC until 40 mM. However, beyond 40 mM, the addition of SDC witnesses a decrease in hard sphere radius at a higher rate as compared to core radius. The decrease in core radius as well as hard sphere radius clearly indicates the formation of smaller P84-SDC mixed micelles. Effective packing of the hydrophobic part of the SDC in the micellar core decreases the size of the core radius and due to the hydrophobic interactions, water from the core is expelled out into corona results in dehydration of core.^{47,48}

Table 4.6: Various key model parameters: core radius (R_c), polydispersity, hard sphere radius (R_{HS}), volume fraction (ϕ) and aggregation number (N_{agg}) for 12% w/v P84 at 37°C with varying concentration of SDC (20-100mM).

System	Core radius R_c (nm)	Polydispersity	Hard sphere radius R_{HS} (nm)	Volume fraction ϕ	Aggregation number N_{agg}	
					Pluronic	SDC
12% w/v P84	4.87	0.19	7.46	0.16	117	----
12% w/v P84 + 20 mM SDC	4.28	0.17	7.22	0.25	73	45
12% w/v P84 + 40 mM SDC	3.99	0.17	6.34	0.26	54	67
12% w/v P84 + 60 mM SDC	3.85	0.18	5.71	0.25	45	84
12% w/v P84 + 80 mM SDC	3.66	0.19	5.25	0.22	36	90
12% w/v P84 + 100 mM SDC	3.65	0.21	4.81	0.21	34	104

Figure 4.7: SANS data pattern (with error bars in experimental data) for 12 % w/v pluronic P84 with different concentrations of SDC (20 mM -100 mM) at 37°C.

As the charged head groups of SDC resides on the core-corona interface, this leads to hydration of the corona region resulting in the increase in the volume fraction of the micelles.¹⁸ In the presence of 20 mM SDC, the aggregation number of the 12 % w/v pluronic P84, F127 and F108 decreases from 117, 112 and 78 to 73, 69 and 57 respectively. These values clearly signify that SDC molecules associate with the pluronic micelles and form smaller pluronic-SDC mixed micelles. Smaller pluronic-SDC mixed micelles are formed in the presence of SDC mainly because of head group repulsion from charged head groups and effective packing of the hydrophobic part of the SDC in the micellar core.^{49,12}

4.3.3.4 Solubilization of CLZ in pluronic-SDC mixed micelles

The SANS distribution curves for 12% w/v pluronic P84, F127 and F108 with 20 mM SDC solutions in the presence of CLZ are presented in **Figure 4.8 (a), (b) and (c)** respectively. The various parameters obtained from the fitting of data are core radius, polydispersity, hardsphere radius, volume fraction and aggregation number. As tabulated in **Table 4.7** solubilization of CLZ results in the increase in the aggregation number of pluronic and SDC molecules, core radius (R_C) and hard sphere radius (R_{HS}) of the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles. These results confirm that CLZ was solubilized in the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles results in the large radius of both core and hard sphere. As

shown in **Figure 4.8**, increase in the scattering intensity at low Q values may be due to the combined effect of decrease in the electrostatic repulsion interaction and size growth of the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles.¹⁸ These results reveal that CLZ increases the driving force for aggregation of the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles. Similar results were suggested by Alexander *et al.* in case of solubilization of flubriprofen in the pluronic micelles.⁵⁰ If we compare the results of solubilization of CLZ in pure pluronic micelles with the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles, it is clear that aggregation behaviour has improved in the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles. This is the main reason of greater solubility. The reason for the stability of the CLZ loaded pluronic-SDC mixed micelles is assigned to the repulsive electrostatic repulsions between the micelles which prevent the self-aggregation of CLZ loaded micelles driven by the hydrophobic-hydrophobic interactions between the core of pluronic and SDC micelles.⁵¹

Table 4.7: Various key model parameters: core radius (R_c), polydispersity, hard sphere radius (R_{HS}), volume fraction (ϕ) and aggregation number (N_{agg}) for 12% w/v P84 + 20 mM SDC, F127 + 20 mM SDC and F108 + 20 mM SDC before and after solubilization of CLZ at 37°C.

System	Core radius R_c (nm)	Polydispersity	Hard sphere radius R_{HS} (nm)	Volume fraction ϕ	Aggregation number N_{agg}	
					Pluronic	SDC
12% w/v P84 + 20 mM SDC	4.28	0.17	7.22	0.25	73	45
12% w/v F127 + 20 mM SDC	4.95	0.26	8.77	0.31	69	127
12% w/v F108 + 20 mM SDC	4.36	0.30	8.61	0.23	57	121
12% w/v P84 + 20 mM SDC + CLZ	4.44	0.17	7.37	0.25	83	51
12% w/v F127 + 20 mM SDC + CLZ	5.13	0.26	8.98	0.30	73	135
12% w/v F108 + 20 mM SDC + CLZ	4.41	0.32	9.11	0.23	57	12

Figure 4.8: SANS data pattern (with error bars in experimental data) for 12 % w/v pluronic in presence of 20 mM SDC and after solubilization of CLZ at 37°C (a) P84, (b) F127 and (c) F108

4.3.4 Micropolarity measurements

Further, to gain insights into the location of drug in the micellar systems, we have used the hydrophobic probe pyrene to monitor the changes in microenvironment of pluronic micelles and pluronic-SDC mixed micelles with increasing concentration of CLZ drug at 37°C. It is well established that the fluorescence emission spectrum of pyrene is very sensitive to environmental polarity.⁵² The ratio of the first (373 nm) and third (384 nm)

vibronic peak intensities (I_1/I_3) in pyrene emission spectrum senses the polarity of the medium in the immediate vicinity of the probe, hence the term micropolarity. The variation in the I_1/I_3 ratio of pyrene in pluronic micelles and pluronic-SDC mixed micelles with increasing concentrations of CLZ drug is shown in **Figure 4.9** and **4.10** respectively. For P84 and P84-SDC mixed micelles shown in **Figure 4.9 (a)** and **4.9 (b)** respectively, an increase in CLZ concentration resulted in a continuous decrease in I_1/I_3 ratio towards much lower value (~ 0.6). The decrease in I_1/I_3 ratio clearly suggests that pyrene is experiencing more hydrophobic environment in the presence of CLZ drug and reveals that CLZ drug is solubilized in the inner core of these micelles.

Figure 4.9: Variation of micropolarity ratio (I_1/I_3) as a function of CLZ to determine its location in different pluronic and pluronic-SDC mixed micelles at 37°C **(a)** 12 % w/v P84, **(b)** 12 % w/v P84 + 20 mM SDC. Each point represents average \pm SD ($n = 3$)

However, in case of pure pluronic F127 and F108 micelles shown in **Figure 4.10 (a)** and **4.10 (c)** respectively, it was observed that as the CLZ drug concentration was increased the I_1/I_3 ratio decreases and eventually reaches a plateau. The I_1/I_3 values for F108 and F127 micelles are more or less similar (~ 1.01) and indicate that pyrene experiences less hydrophobic environment in these micelles as compared to P84 micelles. This kind of behaviour is assigned to the water penetration in hydrophilic pluronic F127 and F108 micelles and also to the solubilization of CLZ drug in the outer

corona of micelles. **Figure 4.10 (b) and 4.10 (d)** depicts that for F127-SDC and F108-SDC mixed micelles, the I_1/I_3 ratio decreases continuously as a function of increasing drug concentration indicating the solubilization of hydrophobic drug which causes the pyrene to experiences more hydrophobic environment.⁵³ The micropolarity ratio in mixed micelles is nearly ~ 0.7 which is much lower as compared to the value (1.01) observed in pure pluronic micelles. These results confirmed that SDC dehydrate the pluronic micelles and creates more hydrophobic environment for better solubilization of CLZ drug.

Figure 4.10: Variation of micropolarity ratio (I_1/I_3) as a function of CLZ to determine its location in different pluronic and pluronic-SDC mixed micelles at 37°C. **(a)** 12 % w/v F127, **(b)** 12 % w/v F127 + 20 mM SDC, **(c)** 12 % w/v F108, **(d)** 12 % w/v F108 + 20 mM SDC.

4.3.5 Dynamic light scattering (DLS) Measurements

4.3.5.1 Characterization of pluronic-SDC mixed micelles

We have determined the variation of micellar size of pluronic micelles upon addition of SDC using DLS measurements at 37°C. The hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of P84, F127 and F108 micelles at 12 % w/v concentration was found to be 13.5 nm, 28.2 nm and 50.7 nm. The variation of D_h of 12 % w/v P84 as a function of increasing concentration of SDC is presented in **Figure 4.11 (a)**. The micellar size was observed to decrease with increasing concentration of SDC which revealed that addition of SDC results in the formation of pluronic-SDC mixed micelles.⁵⁴ At very low SDC concentrations (2-8 mM), the D_h of P84 micelles remained invariable. After the addition of 10-14 mM SDC, the D_h of P84 reduced from 13.5 nm to 10.1 nm indicating the formation of mixed micelles. Further apparent change in the D_h of the P84 was observed at 20 mM concentration of the SDC. **Figure 4.11 (b)** presents the D_h for pure 12 % w/v F127 and F108 as well as in the presence of 20 mM SDC. Similar decrease in size of the F108 and F127 micelles was observed with the difference that the size distribution in the presence of SDC showed polydispersity. The size distribution of P84-SDC mixed micelles was found to be monodisperse. The reduction in the size of P84-SDC mixed micelles was attributed to the repulsive interactions of charged mixed micelles.^{55,56} The reduction of the D_h after addition of SDC might be related to the increase in the amount of negatively charged COO⁻ head groups in the P84 micelle due to the necessity of SDC molecules to avoid direct contact with water due to their hydrophobicity.^{57,58} Among all three pluronics (P84, F127 and F108), P84 is defearer for solubilization of CLZ in pure system as well as in mixed micellar system. Therefore, study on the long term stability and effect of dilution on P84 and P84-SDC mixed micellar formulations becomes necessity to exploit as a potential drug carriers. DLS measurements have been performed to explore these studies at physiological temperature. All the performed DLS experiments have been divided into three sections as discussed below:

Figure 4.11: Intensity weighted size histograms for (a) 12% w/v pluronic P84 micelles before and after addition of varying concentration of SDC (2-20 mM) at 37°C, (b) 12% w/v pluronic F127 and F108 micelles before and after addition of 20 mM SDC at 37°C.

4.3.5.2 Effect of CLZ solubilization in the P84 and P84-SDC mixed micelles

To understand the effect of CLZ solubilization on the hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of the P84 and P84-SDC mixed micelles, DLS studies were performed for empty and loaded micellar solutions at 37°C. The intensity weighted size distribution plots of the empty and CLZ loaded P84 and P84-SDC mixed micelles are presented in **Figure 4.12(a)**. The size of empty P84 and P84-SDC mixed micelles was found to be 13.54 nm and 5.61 nm, respectively. However, after the CLZ loading D_h values were observed to be 18.16 nm and 7.53 nm, respectively. Significant differences observed between the D_h of the unloaded and loaded micelles of P84 and P84-SDC mixed micelles indicated that CLZ has got solubilized in these micelles.

4.3.5.3 Long Term stability study of the P84-SDC mixed micelles

The pluronic and pluronic-SDC mixed micellar formulations were examined by eye inspection for precipitation of CLZ as well as by DLS measurements to determine the

development of aggregate sizes and polydispersity with time.¹⁴ The DLS measurements demonstrated that P84-SDC mixed micellar formulations remained quite stable and no significant changes in the micellar size, particle dispersity and precipitation were observed even after 3 months. After 3 months, the P84-SDC mixed micellar formulations become slightly heterodisperse but no noticeable precipitation was observed. The other mixed micellar formulations F127-SDC and F108-SDC were found to be heterodisperse so DLS measurements were not performed for these formulations. In addition, these micellar formulations showed precipitation after 1 week. CLZ loaded P84-SDC mixed micelle formulations showed excellent stability. Therefore, the results {shown in **Figure 4.12 (b)**} from P84-SDC mixed micelles encourage for drug delivery of such hydrophobic drugs with excellent stability.

Figure 4.12: (a) Intensity weighted size distribution histograms for 12% w/v pluronic P84 micelles, P84-SDC (12% w/v pluronic P84+20 mM SDC) mixed micelles before and after solubilization of CLZ drug at 37°C (b) Size distribution histograms for CLZ loaded P84-SDC formulation during storage at 25°C.

4.3.5.4 Dilution stability

While micelles allow a great depth of tissue penetration for drug delivery, they usually disintegrate rapidly in the body. Thus, sustained drug delivery from micellar nano carriers is a biggest challenge.⁵⁹ The dilution stability of CLZ loaded P84-SDC mixed micelles was investigated at physiological temperature 37°C and the results shown in **Figure 4.13**. The results from dilution stability reveal that when the formulation was diluted 30 times, its size increased from 7.53 nm to 18.51 nm. Since the increased size of the formulation after dilution is equal to the size of CLZ loaded P84 micelles, hence it can be anticipated that concentration of SDC becomes very less even below its *cmc*. However, when the formulation was subjected to 480 fold dilutions, the size remained unchanged and the formulation remained stable till the end of the study. No significant precipitation was observed during the course of the studies. Therefore, from the above results we concluded that SDC molecules penetration in P84 micelles provides significant formulation stability but when it enters the body its act as only P84 micelles.

Figure 4.13: Size distribution histograms showing effect of dilution (30-480 times) on CLZ loaded P84-SDC (12% w/v pluronic P84+20 mM SDC) formulation at 37°C.

4.4 Conclusions

The main objective of the present work is to develop a long-term stable aqueous nano-micellar clozapine (CLZ) formulation which may allow preparation of liquid formulations that are ready to be used without freeze-drying and subsequent reconstitution. We have studied the solubilization of hydrophobic drug CLZ in pluronic micelles as well as in pluronic-bile salt sodium deoxycholate (SDC) mixed micelles. The formation of mixed micelles between pluronics and SDC has been confirmed from dynamic light scattering (DLS) and small angle neutron scattering (SANS) measurements. The effect of drug on the structure of pluronic micelles and mixed micelles was also investigated and the results revealed that solubilization of CLZ improve aggregation behaviour of pluronic-SDC mixed micelles. The results from micropolarity measurements indicated that CLZ experiences better hydrophobic environment in case of pluronic-SDC mixed micelles as compared to pure pluronic micelles. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) and fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy techniques confirm that there is good compatibility between CLZ and components of formulation. The results indicated that P84 is defeater for CLZ solubilization than other two investigated pluronics in both pure pluronic and pluronic-SDC mixed micelles. Since a good drug carrier must possess long term stability and should be resistant to subsequent dilutions. Therefore, CLZ loaded P84-SDC mixed micelles were further tested for long term stability and effect of dilution. The results of long term stability indicated that CLZ loaded P84-SDC mixed micellar formulations remained stable for 3 months at 25°C. Surprisingly, during the course of dilution study it was revealed that when the formulation was diluted 30 folds, CLZ loaded P84-SDC mixed micelles are converted into CLZ loaded pure P84 micelles. On further diluting the formulation even up to 480 times, the hydrodynamic size remained stable and no drug precipitation occurred. Thus, the results obtained from the present study can facilitate the optimization of concentration of surfactant that stabilized the formulation but did not interfered with the polymeric micelles when they enter the body.

4.5 References

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Chapter 5

Mixed Micelles of Pluronic-Surface Active Ionic Liquids (SAILs) as Efficient Hydrophobic Quercetin Drug Carriers

5.1 Introduction

Flavonoids are a broad class of low molecular weight, secondary plant phenolics identified by the flavan nucleus. They are widely distributed in leaves, seeds, bark and flowers of plants, over 4,000 flavonoids have been identified till date.¹ Among these, quercetin (QCT) is one of the most abundant natural flavanoid that is widely distributed in various fruits and vegetables and is important because of its pharmacological and therapeutic effects.² QCT exhibits anti-inflammatory, anti-neoplastic and cardioprotective activities.³ QCT is anticipated to be one of the next antineoplastic drugs with extremely high efficacy.^{4,5} QCT is a hydrophobic drug and encounter bioavailability problems. An extensive amount of work has been done to solubilize and deliver the QCT by different means such as beta-cyclodextrin inclusion complexes, liposomes, ethyl acetate in water emulsions, solidified self-nanoemulsifying system, controlled-release packaging films and different individual micelles.³

Pluronic, the tri-block copolymers are composed of polypropylene oxide (PPO)-polyethylene oxide (PEO)-polypropylene oxide (PPO) units. They are amphiphilic in nature and aggregate to form micelles having core region made of PPO and corona region consisting of PEO units.⁴ Pluronic micelles have raised growing interest for the innovative design of drug delivery systems due to their excellent biocompatibility and non toxicity.⁵ Recent reports suggest that, these polymers are able to sensitize multidrug resistant (MDR) cancer cells leading to enhanced drug transport across cellular barriers.⁶

There are numerous reports published in literature dealing with solubilization of hydrophobic drugs in pluronic micelles.^{7,8} These reports mainly focus on use of single pluronics. However, high critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) values of these polymers may be disadvantageous as loaded micelles undergo significant dilution on

administration resulting in low stability of micelles.⁹ It has been well established in literature that as compared to single surfactant solution, mixing of different type of surfactant solutions exhibit synergism in terms of better surface activities and lower *cmc* values. Mixed micelles also offer significant advantages in terms of higher thermodynamic and kinetic stability as well as higher drug loading capacities.¹⁰ Fortunately, in recent years, ionic liquids (ILs) have evolved as a new class of environmentally benign and tunable designer solvents. They are used as solvents and/or materials in the fields of pharmaceutical drug delivery and active pharmaceutical ingredient formulation because of their unique and tunable physicochemical and biological properties. The ILs having long chain cations are amphiphilic and are known as surface active ionic liquids (SAILs).¹¹⁻¹³ There are few reports in which ILs are used for delivering hydrophobic drugs and bio-macromolecules.

Recently, Goto *et al.* studied the solubility of poorly water soluble drug acyclovir in the IL/oil microemulsion for transdermal drug delivery.¹⁴ They tested the solubility of acyclovir in imidazolium based IL (dimethylimidazolium dimethylphosphate, [C₁mim][(MeO)₂PO₂]/ Tween-80/ Span-20/ isopropyl Myristate containing IL/oil microemulsions and observed that drug molecules are loaded in the IL core. Authors developed IL droplets in an isopropyl myristate (IPM) continuous phase with a nontoxic surfactant, polyoxyethylene sorbitan monooleate (Tween-80), and a cosurfactant, sorbitan laurate (span-20), both of which have been extensively used in formulating drug delivery carriers. Phase behaviour studies of IL/Tween-80/ Span-20/IPM four-component systems revealed the formation of transparent and thermodynamically stable IL/oil microemulsions with a wide range of IL content. They hypothesized that dissolution of IL in the micellar core was attributed to the electrostatic attraction between the positively charged imidazolium cation of ILs and the electronegative oxygen atoms of oxyethylene units of Tween-80. Span-20 was found to facilitate microemulsion formation. They concluded that an IL-assisted microemulsion was shown to be effective as a transdermal drug delivery (TDD) carrier for sparingly soluble pharmaceuticals

Mahajan *et al.* previously reported the binding ability of SAIL (C₁₄mimBr) for the drugs dopamine hydrochloride (DH) and acetylcholine chloride (AC).¹⁵ The results have been compared with that of conventional cationic surfactant,

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tetradecyltrimethylammonium bromide (TTAB). DH binds more strongly with the investigated SAILs than AC due to cation- π interactions between the aromatic region of DH and the positive charge of the surfactant molecules. The greater binding constant values were found for DH-C₁₄mimBr than DH-TTAB has been due to π - π interactions of the π system of DH and imidazolium ring of C₁₄mimBr. These results are encouraging for exploiting the SAILs as drug carrier than conventional surfactant.

Kumar *et al.* investigated self-assembling behaviour of SAIL cholinium dodecylbenzenesulfonate (Cho[DBS]), their interaction with the enzyme cellulase and ecotoxicity.¹⁶ They converted conventional surfactant sodium dodecylbenzenesulfonate (NaDBS) into an efficient and nontoxic anionic surface-active ionic liquid, cholinium dodecylbenzenesulfonate (Cho[DBS]). Dynamic light scattering (DLS), isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC), conductometry and tensiometry measurements were employed to determine the surface-active properties at the air-liquid interface and the aggregation behaviour of Cho[DBS] in water. The aggregation behaviour study indicated its superior surface-active properties and low *cmc* value as compared to those of its competitor (NaDBS and other choline-based SAILs). The enzyme activity was enhanced in the presence of Cho[DBS] which indicated its excellent compatibility with cellulase. The results evidenced that the electrostatic and noncovalent interactions were involved through which Cho[DBS] interact with cellulase. The functional enzyme activity was increased significantly upon the exposure of the active sites of cellulase in Cho[DBS] micellar solutions during the interaction. The slightly modified structure of cellulase after the interaction with Cho[DBS] was stabilized in the postmicellar regime. The study on microalgae was conducted to check the nontoxic effect of Cho[DBS], revealed its excellent environmental friendly property and less toxicity for freshwater microalgae (*Synedasmus* sp.). The study concluded that cellulase enzyme in combination with Cho[DBS] is stable and can be used for enzyme-surfactant formulations.

5.2 Present work

The present work reports a systematic investigation on the solubilization of hydrophobic drug quercetin (QCT) in pluronic F108 and its mixed micelles with surface

active ionic liquids (SAILs) having same alkyl chain length but different hydrophobic head groups viz. 1-dodecyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide [Mim]; N-dodecyl-Nmethylpiperidinium bromide, [Pip]; N-dodecyl-Nmethylpyrrolidinium bromide, [Pyr]. Since SAILs are known to exhibit low toxicity there is no report about the solubilization of hydrophobic drug in the pluronic-SAILs mixed system. So this work engenders the keen interest for how SAILs micelles modify the properties of pluronic micelles in the mixed micellar media for solubilizing the poorly water soluble drug QCT. In the present work from the UV-visible measurements, the solubilization behaviour of QCT in pluronic F108 (PEO₁₃₃PPO₅₀PEO₁₃₃) and binary mixtures of F108 with SAILs have been studied. The hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of the loaded and unloaded micelles has been studied using dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements. Further, the solubilization locus of QCT in F108 micelles and F108-SAIL mixed micelles has been adjudged with the help of differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) measurements. *In vitro* drug release studies were performed to have an idea about the release behaviour of the drugs from the mixed systems. *In vitro* cell viability assays were performed to compare the anticancer effects between free QCT and prepared QCT micellar formulations. The molecular structures of QCT, F108 and SAILs are shown in **Figure 5.1**.

Figure 5.1: (a) Quercetin [QCT] (b) Pluronic F108 (c) 1-dodecyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide [Mim] (d) N-dodecyl-N-methylpiperidinium bromide [Pip] (e) N-dodecyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium bromide [Pyr].

5.3 Results and Discussion

5.3.1 Quercetin (QCT) drug solubilization study

At first the UV-visible spectrae of QCT at various concentrations were recorded in methanolic solution and λ_{\max} of QCT was found to be 370 nm as shown in **Figure 5.2**. The linear calibration curve for the absorbance versus concentration of QCT was plotted. The molar absorption coefficient was found to be $14.80 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ determined using slope of the calibration curve. The aqueous solubility of QCT in the presence of pluronic F108 and different SAILs viz. 1-dodecyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide [Mim]; N-dodecyl-Nmethylpiperidinium bromide, [Pip]; N-dodecyl-Nmethylpyrrolidinium bromide, [Pyr] were analysed.

Figure 5.2 UV spectra of QCT in methanolic solutions at various concentrations. Inset of figure shows calibration curve for QCT at λ_{\max} 367 nm.

The aqueous solubility of the QCT is very low in water *i.e.* only 0.01127 mg/mL which is well supported with literature value.¹⁷ However after the addition of increasing concentration of pluronic F108 and SAILs aqueous solubility of QCT was increased. These results reveal that F108 and investigated SAILs can solubilize the QCT but loading efficiency of these investigated SAILs and F108 was low (listed in **Table 5.1**).

It is well documented in the literature that mixed micelles improved the solubilization as well as loading efficiency of many drugs so we choose the mixed

micelles of pluronic F108 and SAILs for solubilization of QCT.¹⁸⁻²¹ For solubilization study 3 different mole fractions of F108 and SAILs (0.1, 0.5, 0.9) were chosen and *cmc* values of these mixed systems are tabulated in the **Table 5.2**.

Table 5.1: Amount of QCT solubilized in pure pluronic F108 and different SAILs micelles at $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.

System	Amount of QCT solubilized (mg/5mL)	Loading efficiency (%)
Pure F108 micelles	4.283 ± 0.102	38.94 ± 0.930
Pure Mim micelles	1.621 ± 0.072	14.73 ± 0.655
Pure Pip Micelles	1.140 ± 0.061	10.36 ± 0.558
Pure Pyr micelles	1.006 ± 0.012	9.12 ± 0.112

Table 5.2: Critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) values for pluronic F108-SAILs mixed micelles at various mole fractions of pluronic F108 (α_{F108}).

α_{F108}	<i>cmc</i> (mM)		
	F108-Mim	F108-Pip	F108-Pyr
0	10.3	12.57	15.04
0.1	0.98	1.35	1.65
0.5	0.37	0.58	0.49
0.9	0.12	0.38	0.09
1	2.58	2.58	2.58

We observed that solubilization of QCT in these mixed micellar system got enhanced drastically with excellent loading efficiency. UV-visible absorption spectrae of these systems has been presented in **Figure 5.3**. Among the three investigated F108-SAILs mixed micelles *viz.* F108-Mim, F108-Pip and F108-Pyr; F108-Mim showed higher solubilization [**Table 5.3, Figure 5.4 (a)**] and loading efficiency [**Figure 5.4 (b)**] of QCT at all mole fractions of F108 (α_{F108}). There are mainly three reasons behind the

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higher solubilization and loading efficiency for F108-Mim micelles. The orientation of QCT is linear and unfavourable interactions of hydrophobic part of QCT with water makes QCT closer to Mim and other two SAILs (Pip and Pyr). In case of Mim positively charged ring interacts with electro-donating groups of QCT rather than other two SAILs where positive charge is hindered and only limited to nitrogen so there are greater chances of hydrogen bonding between Mim and QCT than other two SAILs. Due to the more interactions, mainly hydrogen bonding between positively charged Mim head group and electro-donating hydroxyl group of QCT, Mim and QCT are in close proximity to each other. In concert with H-bonding, π -type interactions are also play key role because the electron rich conjugated π -system of QCT molecule interact with electron deficient π system of Mim.²²⁻²⁵

Figure 5.3: UV spectra of QCT solubilized in different mole fractions of pluronic F108-SAILs mixed micelles at 37°C for (a) Mim, (b) Pip and (c) Pyr.

Table 5.3: Amount of QCT solubilized in pluronic F108-SAILs mixed micelles at different mole fractions of F108 (α_{F108}) at temperature $37 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$.

Amount of QCT solubilized (mg/mL)			
	F108+Pyr	F108+Pip	F108+Mim
$\alpha_{F108}=0.1$	4.440 ± 0.162	5.157 ± 0.487	7.754 ± 0.092
$\alpha_{F108}=0.5$	9.712 ± 0.958	10.217 ± 0.110	10.668 ± 0.950
$\alpha_{F108}=0.9$	7.193 ± 0.067	7.992 ± 0.019	8.313 ± 0.100

Figure 5.4: (a) Amount of QCT solubilized and (b) Drug loading efficiency of various mole fractions of pluronic F108-SAILs mixed micelles at 37°C .

Proper orientation of SAILs to form mixed micelles, hydrates the core-corona interface by which surface charge density is increased that enhances the solubility of the PEO blocks resulting in the dehydration of core of F108-Mim mixed micelles which creates better hydrophobic environment for solubilization of QCT.²⁰ Here we observed that solubilization and loading efficiency was low in both SAIL rich micelles ($\alpha_{F108}=0.1$) and F108 rich micelles ($\alpha_{F108}=0.9$) as compared to F108-SAILs (equi molar) mixed micelles ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$) which confers that equal moles of both SAILs and F108 provide better synergistic effect for solubilization of QCT in all investigated SAILs. It

is important to notice that lower *cmc* value of any mixed micellar system is not an appreciable selecting criterion for drug solubilization. The amount of QCT solubilized in the different F108-SAILs mixed micelles is tabulated in **Table 5.3**. F108-Mim mixed micelles ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$) show greater solubility which is approximately 200 times greater than QCT solubilized in water showing excellent potential of these mixed micellar system for QCT solubilization. This approach could be extended to solubilize other hydrophobic flavnoids drugs such as kaempferol, myricetin, fisetin and isorhamnetin.

The drug loading efficiency is percentage of solubilized QCT from original QCT feed in F108-SAILs mixed micelles during solubilization process and can be calculated from following equation (5.1).

$$\text{Drug loading efficiency} = \frac{\text{weight of drug in micelles}}{\text{weight of drug fed initially}} \times 100 \quad (5.1)$$

Drug loading efficiency of F108-Mim mixed micelles was greater than other two investigated F108-SAILs mixed micelles represented in **Figure 5.4 (b)** indicating higher drug loading efficiency of F108-Mim mixed micelles.²⁵

5.3.1.1 Partition coefficient (*P*)

Partition coefficient is one of the crucial property for assessment of micellar systems as potential drug carrier.²⁶ In every micellar system containing drug solubilizate, there is always a dynamic exchange between drug molecules incorporated in micelle and those dissolved in the external solution, a process called ‘partitioning’. If the rate of transfer of drug molecules from micelles to solution equals the rate of transfer of these drug molecules from the solution to micelles, i.e. equilibrium is reached, then the partitioning is characterized by a thermodynamic constant, called the ‘partition coefficient’, *P*.²⁷

The micellar/water partition coefficient can be calculated from UV-visible results and is defined as the ratio of drug concentration in micelle to drug concentration in water for a particular polymer/surfactant concentration and is given by relation (5.2).

$$P = \frac{S_{tot} - S_w}{S_w} \quad (5.2)$$

Where S_{tot} is total solubility of drug and S_w is solubility of drug in water. The partition coefficient have been calculated and given in **Figure 5.5 (a)** from where it was found that value of partition coefficient firstly increased by increasing the mole fraction of F108 *i.e.* 0.5 and then decreased among all investigated SAILs. The highest value of partition coefficient was found in case of F108-Mim mixed micelles at all mole fractions revealing better partitioning of solubilized QCT in these micelles than other two investigated SAILs. Higher partitioning of QCT in case F108-Mim mixed micelles at all mole fractions reveals that higher drug solubilization in core of mixed micelles persuading more hydrophobic environment than other two investigated F108-SAILs mixed micelles. Kadam *et al.* reported that higher partition coefficient of carbamazepine in pluronic micelles corresponds to better hydrophobic microenvironment formed by pluronic micelles.²⁸

5.3.1.2 Standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°)

As described in the partition coefficient section from thermodynamics point of view, solubilization can be considered as a normal partitioning of drug between micelle and aqueous phases, and the standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) can be represented by following expression (5.3)

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln P \quad (5.3)$$

Where R is the gas constant, T is temperature (in Kelvin), and P is partition coefficient. The ΔG° value depicts Gibbs free energy of transfer of one mole of drug in micellar phase. As depicted in the **Figure 5.5 (b)**, the values of ΔG° found to be negative showing that process of QCT solubilization in these F108-SAILs mixed micelles is spontaneous and transfer of water molecules from the micellar core persuading a more hydrophobic environment.²⁹⁻³² Higher negative value of ΔG° was observed in case of F108-Mim mixed micelles reveals that more spontaneous solubilization of QCT in F108-Mim mixed micelles than other two investigated F108-SAILs mixed micelles.

Figure 5.5: (a) Micellar/water partition coefficient (P) and (b) Standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) of pluronic F108-SAILs mixed micelles at 37°C for [▲] F108-Mim, [•] F108-Pip and [■]F108-Pyr.

5.3.2 Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) is used to determine the effect of the addition of SAILs on pluronic F108 micelles as well as effect of QCT solubilization on micellar size of F108-SAILs mixed micelles. The hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) value of pure F108 micelles was found to be 50.7 nm, but in different F108-SAILs (Mim/Pip/Pyr) mixed micelles at $\alpha_{F108} = 0.9, 0.5$ and 0.1 size decreased gradually as shown in **Table 5.4**. A remarkable decrease in the D_h of F108 micelles after addition of SAILs confirms that there is formation of mixed micelles. The shifting of micellar peak towards a lower value of D_h confirms the formation of mixed micelles of F108-SAILs due to repulsive interactions of charged mixed micelles.^{33,34} It has been found that the addition of SAILs to the F108 micellar solution forms a supra-molecular assembly where hydrophobic long chain of the SAILs molecule gets merged in core of F108 micelles.³⁵ The charged head group of SAILs molecules resides at interface of core and corona of the micelle. The size also decreases due to intercalation of charged head groups of SAILs in non-ionic F108 micelles which increase repulsive interactions of charged mixed micelles.³⁶ **Figure 5.6** revealed that the highest reduction in D_h at all α_{F108} was observed in the case

of F108-Mim supporting the UV-visible results that Mim hydrates core-corona interface by virtue of increasing surface charge density and dehydrates core more efficiently.

Figure 5.6: Intensity weighed size distribution profiles for pluronic F108 micelles at various mole fractions of F108-Mim mixed micelles at 37°C.

Table 5.4: Values of D_h (hydrodynamic diameter) for different pluronic F108-SAILs mixed micelles before and after solubilization of QCT at 37°C.

System	D_h (hydrodynamic diameter)		
	$\alpha_{F108} 0.1$	$\alpha_{F108} 0.5$	$\alpha_{F108} 0.9$
F108-Mim	21.0 nm	28.2 nm	32.6 nm
F108-Mim + QCT	24.0 nm	42.8 nm	40.8 nm
F108-Pip	24.3 nm	32.6 nm	37.8 nm
F108-Pip + QCT	28.2 nm	37.8 nm	43.8 nm
F108-Pyr	23.5 nm	28.2 nm	37.8 nm
F108-Pyr + QCT	27.5 nm	32.6 nm	43.8 nm

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Figure 5.7: Intensity weighed size distribution profiles for empty and QCT loaded pluronic F108-SAILs ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$) mixed micelles at 37°C **(a)** Mim, **(b)** Pip and **(c)** Pyr measured from dynamic light scattering.

The size of micelles play very important role in micellar formulations as well as in the *in-vivo* performance. Small sizes of the drug loaded micelles may be sterilized simply by a filtration process and the micelles may be easily delivered to the blood stream through intravenous Injection.³⁷ Appropriate size of drug loaded micelles plays important role in drug accumulation and penetration in cells so the size of micelle should be large enough for circulation as well as small enough for their penetration.

Figure 5.8 Intensity weighed size distribution plot for empty and QCT loaded F108-SAILs ($\alpha_{F108}=0.1$) mixed micelles at 37°C (a) Mim, (b) Pip and (c) Pyr.

The intensity weighted size distribution plots of the empty and QCT loaded F108-SAILs *viz.* Mim, Pyr and Pip ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$) mixed micelles are presented in **Figure 5.7** and the plots for mixed micelles at mole fraction $\alpha_{F108}=0.1$ and 0.9 are presented in **Figure 5.8** and **Figure 5.9** respectively. From DLS measurements it has been observed that incorporation of QCT in F108-SAILs mixed micelles is responsible for change in the D_h of the these micelles. The shifting of peak towards a higher D_h value indicate the solubilization of QCT in these micelles. As shown in **Figure 5.7 (a)**, a sharp increase in D_h of F108-Mim mixed micelles was observed ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$) *i.e.* from 28.2 nm to 42.8 nm after QCT solubilization which is greater than other two investigated SAILs at same mole fraction. This is attributed due to the higher solubilization of QCT in core of F108-

Mim mixed micelles.³⁷ These results also supported from SANS measurements of many pluronics micellar formulations.³⁸ Alexander *et al.* reported that upon addition of flurbiprofen, pluronic P103 showed an increase in aggregation number, the fraction of polymer micellized and core radius. The volume fraction of solvent in core decreases on addition of drug, indicating the uptake of the drug mainly by hydrophobic PPO core gives rise to larger core radius.³⁸

Figure 5.9: Intensity weighed size distribution plot for empty and QCT loaded pluronic F108-SAILs ($\alpha_{F108}=0.9$) mixed micelles at 37°C (a) Mim, (b) Pip and (c) Pyr.

5.3.3 Possible location of QCT in pluronic and pluronic-SAILs mixed micelles

Location of QCT in pluronic micelles as well as in pluronic-SAILs mixed micelles have been scrutinized with the help of differential pulse voltammetry (DPV). Mahajan *et al.*

also used differential pulse voltammetry technique to find out location of QCT in different surfactant media.³⁹ Typical differential pulse voltammograms of QCT at the glassy carbon electrode (immersed in AcOH-NaAc aqueous buffer of pH 5.0) has been shown in **Figure 5.10**. Under this condition, QCT shows anodic peak at oxidation potential (E_p)= 0.280 V corresponding to oxidation of 3'-OH and 4'-OH groups on the B-ring.³⁹ The oxidation of QCT is $2e^-$ and $2H^+$ transfer process.

Figure 5.10: Differential pulse voltammograms of QCT at the glassy carbon electrode immersed in AcOH-NaAc buffer of pH 5.0.

As shown in **Figure 5.11 (a)** upon the first addition of the pluronic solution (where F108 is in form of monomers) the oxidant peak of QCT moves towards a higher potential (0.284 V) with decreased peak current ($-2.35 \mu\text{A}$). But with increasing addition of F108 there is no longer change in potential of QCT which implies that the environment of QCT do not change and it get solubilized in micelles. This is further confirmed from the fact that saturation occurs near *cmc* value. These results reveals that QCT gets solubilized into hydrophobic region of F108 micelle i.e. core-corona interface and core of F108 micelles.⁴⁰⁻⁴¹ The electro-active B ring of QCT is no longer available there by making the oxidation process more difficult and hence, the peak current decreases. On the other hand in SAILs, upon addition of Mim micelles [shown in **Figure 5.11 (b)**], the oxidation peak of QCT moves towards lower potential and then to

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higher potential with decreased current. These results reveal that when SAIL is in form of monomers the interaction of the A ring of QCT become dominant with SAILs that exposes the B ring and facilitates the oxidation of B ring. However, as the concentration of SAILs is increased, B ring of QCT also interacts with the SAILs micelles because more SAILs molecules are available to interact with both of rings. If we compare **Figure 5.11 (c)** of F108-SAILs ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$) mixed micelles the potential first decreases and then increases to certain value followed by a plateau at a potential value of 0.292 V [voltammogram shown in **Figure 5.11 (d)**].

Figure 5.11: Variation of oxidation potential (E_p) vs. [surfactant] for (a) F108 + QCT, (b) Mim + QCT (c) F108-Mim ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$) + QCT. Inset to each figure shows the variation of peak current (I_p) of QCT vs. concentration of pluronic F108/ Mim/ F108-Mim, (d) DPV curves of QCT in the presence of increasing concentration of F108-Mim mixed micelles.

These results indicate that interaction of SAILs and F108 both play an important role in the solubilization of QCT. When both SAILs and F108 are in form of monomers, a decrease in potential of QCT is due to interaction of A ring of QCT with SAILs because interaction of SAILs is predominant than F108. The higher availability of SAILs and F108 leads to interaction of B ring of QCT becoming predominant in the solubilization of QCT and hence the potential of QCT become harder. Similar results have been observed in case of other two mixed micellar systems i.e. F108-Pip and F108-Pyr and voltamograms of these systems are presented in **Figure 5.12**.

Figure 5.12 Variation of oxidation potential (E_p) vs. [Pluronic-SAILs ($\alpha_{F108}=0.1$)] (for **(a)** F108-Pip + QCT, **(b)** F108-Pyr + QCT, Inset to each figure shows the variation of peak current (i_p) of QCT vs. concentration of pluronic F108-Pip/ F108-Pyr.

Benesi-Hildebrand (B-H) equation is used for the determination of binding constant K and stoichiometry of non-bonding interactions occurs in the charge-transfer complexes or host-guest molecular complexation. The B-H equation is given as equation (5.4).

$$\frac{1}{\Delta I_p} = \frac{1}{K_a \Delta I_{p \max} [\text{surf}]} + \frac{1}{\Delta I_{p \max}} \quad (5.4)$$

Where ΔI_p represents the change in peak current of QCT on addition of F108-SAILs solution with respect to QCT solutions at zero concentration of F108-SAILs. As shown in **Figure 5.13**, the double reciprocal B-H plots of $1/\Delta I_p$ versus $1/[F108-SAILs]^n$ gives linear relationship when $n = 1$ and indicates 1:1 stoichiometry of these QCT/F108-SAILs system. The binding constant (K) is determined from the intercept to slope ratio

of B-H plots and is given in **Table 5.5**. It can be observed that the difference in the head group of SAILs gave different binding constant values with QCT confirms that imidazolium ring plays an important role in solubility of Mim to QCT. This may be attributed to the cation- π interactions between positive charge of SAILs and π -electron system of QCT. Moreover, among these F108-SAILs, QCT has a higher value of binding constant with F108-Mim than F108-Pip and F108-Pyr indicating that in addition to the cation- π interactions, some other types of interactions are also playing their role. As speculated from UV-visible measurements π - π interactions between π -electron system of QCT and imidazolium ring of Mim may be responsible for the higher values of binding constant in this system.

Figure 5.13 Binding constant determination using changes in the peak current of QCT for (a) F108-Mim (b) F108-Pip (c) F108-Pyr at $\alpha_{F108}=0.5$.

The Gibbs free energy change (ΔG) for these F108-SAILs + QCT complexes can be calculated by using the following equation.

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K \quad (5.5)$$

As shown in **Table 5.5**, values of ΔG were found to be negative indicating that binding of QCT with SAILs and F108 is a spontaneous process. A higher negative ΔG value may be attributed to enhanced interaction of QCT with F108-Mim micelles as compared to F108-Pyr and F108-Pip mixed micelles.

Table 5.5: Estimated values of binding constant (K), free energy change of binding (ΔG), the correlation coefficients (R^2) for 1:1 complex formation between F108-SAILs mixed micelles and QCT.

System	$K/10^4$ (M^{-1})	ΔG ($kJ\ mol^{-1}$)	R^2
F108-Mim + QCT	5.262	-4.28177	0.98337
F108-Pip + QCT	1.690	-1.35306	0.99545
F108-Pyr + QCT	1.645	-1.28347	0.97567

5.3.4 Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (1H NMR) measurements

To get detailed information regarding the interactions between the QCT and investigated F108-SAILs mixed system 1H NMR measurements were performed. Interpretation of 1H NMR spectrum of 15 mM F108 in D_2O - H_2O mixture shows singlet at ~ 1.003 ppm which is attributed to protons of PPO- CH_3 groups and additional broad peaks at ~ 3.383 and ~ 3.333 ppm belong to protons of PPO-CH groups and PPO- CH_2 groups, respectively. A sharp peak at ~ 3.651 ppm belongs to protons of PEO- CH_2 group.

Table 5.6: 1H NMR chemical shift values of PEO- CH_2 , PPO- CH_2 , PPO-CH and PPO- CH_3 of pluronic F108 in D_2O in the absence and presence of different SAILs and QCT.

System	PEO- CH_2 - signal (δppm)	PPO- CH_2 - signal (δppm)	PPO-CH- signal (δppm)	PPO- CH_3 - signal (δppm)
F108	3.552	3.383	3.333	1.003
F108 +Mim	3.515	3.666	3.324	0.998
F108 +Mim + QCT	3.555	3.363	3.180	0.985
F108 + Pip	3.550	3.399	3.379	1.000
F108 +Pip + QCT	3.551	3.370	3.350	0.998
F108 + Pyr	3.354	3.373	3.155	0.992
F108 + Pyr + QCT	3.553	3.365	3.000	0.986

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To interpret the locus of solubilization of QCT in pluronic micelles, the chemical shift of PEO-CH₂, PPO-CH₂, PPO-CH and PPO-CH₃ signals have been determined. After addition of Mim, PEO-CH₂, PPO-CH₂, PPO-CH and PPO-CH₃ protons of F108 showed an upfield shift of 0.037 ppm, 0.017 ppm, 0.010 and 0.005 ppm, respectively depicted in **Table 5.6**. These results revealed that Mim forms mixed micelles with F108 micelles resulting in the shift of the F108 protons. The head group of Mim *i.e.* imidazolium resides at core-corona interfaces and interacts with PEO region resulting in upfield shift in the protons of PEO-CH₂. The reason behind upfield shift is attributed to the interaction of positive charged imidazolium head group of Mim with the PEO-corona region. An upfield shift in PPO protons refer to dehydration of this region due to penetration of the tail of Mim in core of the F108 micelles.^{42,13} Surprisingly, after solubilization of QCT in these F108-Mim mixed micellar system, the protons of PEO-CH₂ show an downfield shift of 0.040 due to binding of QCT drug with imidazolium head group of Mim which result in the no longer shielding of PEO-CH₃ protons of the F108. On the other hand after QCT solubilization, PPO-CH₂, PPO-CH and PPO-CH₃ protons show upfield shift of 0.030, 0.143 and 0.013 respectively. These results reveal that most of QCT drug is solubilized in core of micelles and binding of the QCT drug with imidazolium head group of Mim facilitate the penetration of the drug in core and at core-corona interface.²⁹ However, contrasting results were observed in the case of F108-Pip and F108-Pyr mixed micelles. After addition of Pip or Pyr in the F108 micelles no major changes in the PEO protons were observed and a small downfield shift in case of PPO-CH₂, PPO-CH and PPO-CH₃ signals reveals that interactions of these SAILs with pluronics are different than Mim and they hydrate core to some extent. After addition of QCT, very minute changes in PEO-CH₂ protons as well as upfield shift in PPO-CH₂, PPO-CH protons confirmed the solubilization of QCT in core.⁴³

5.3.5 *In vitro* QCT release from F108-SAILs mixed micelles

In vitro drug release is important product performance test, which provides better *in vitro/ in vivo* correlations of drug delivery system.¹⁰ As shown in **Figure 5.14**, the

cumulative % QCT release from F108-Mim, F108-Pyr and F108-Pip mixed micelles was 10.25, 11.02 and 14.32 % respectively after 8 hours. But after 24 h, burst release observed from QCT loaded F108-Pip mixed micelles was 56%, while only 35.25 % and 41.20% QCT was released from F108-Mim and F108-Pyr mixed micelles, respectively. In case of F108-Pip mixed micelles almost 95% QCT was released after 56 hours, while to release this amount of QCT from F108-Pyr and F108-Mim mixed micelles, it took 116 and 124 hours respectively.

Figure 5.14: *In vitro* release of QCT from pluronic-SAILs mixed micelles ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$) at 37°C. Each point represents average \pm SD (n = 3).

These results indicated that interaction of head group of SAILs play an important role in drug release of QCT from these F108-SAILs mixed micellar system. The π - π interactions between π -electron system of QCT and imidazolium ring of Mim are responsible for slower release of QCT from F108-Mim mixed micelles.^{44,45} Further to elucidate the release mechanism from F108-SAILs mixed micelles different kinetic models viz. Zero order release kinetics, first order release kinetics, Higuchi model kinetics and Korsmeyer-Peppas (KP) model have been applied. As tabulated in **Table 5.7**, R^2 values obtained from Higuchi model are higher as compared to other three

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kinetic models signifying that QCT release from F108-Mim and F108-Pyr mixed micelles follows Higuchi model and the process is diffusion controlled. On the other hand for F108-Pip mixed micelles, the R^2 values are higher for Korsmeyer-Peppas (KP) model revealing that QCT release followed this model. The value of diffusional coefficient (n) in KP model indicates anomalous or non-Fickian release ($0.5 < n < 1$) suggesting a coupled erosion–diffusion mechanism. So value of n observed in best fitted F108-Pip mixed micelles is higher than 0.5 suggested that release is coupled erosion-diffusion controlled.⁴⁶

Table 5.7: Rate constants and regression correlations using different kinetic model for the release behaviour of QCT from pluronic F108-SAILs mixed micelles at $\alpha_{F108}=0.5$.

System	Zero order kinetics		First order kinetics		Higuchi kinetics		KP Model		
	R^2	$K_0 (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K_1 (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K_H (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K_H (h^{-1})$	n
F108-Mim	0.9414	0.7373	0.9586	-0.0086	0.9938	9.2019	0.9903	0.4864	0.7268
F108-Pip	0.9686	1.7868	0.7938	0.02619	0.9777	14.7566	0.9871	0.5602	0.8269
F108-Pyr	0.6292	0.0131	0.8932	-0.8403	0.9826	10.2436	0.9770	0.0940	0.9810

5.3.6 *In vitro* cell viability assay

The effects of F108, SAILs, F108-SAILs mixed micelles, QCT loaded mixed micelles on MDA-MB-231 cell viability was determined by MTT assay. As shown in **Figure 5.15**, in case of pluronic F108, the obtained cell viability was 82.40% indicating its excellent cytocompatibility in accordance with the published literature. In case of SAILs, the cell viability decreased in the following order Pyr (63.28 %) <Pip (72.21%) <Mim (73.64%). These results indicate that in the investigated SAILs, Pyr showed higher cytotoxicity than Pip and Mim may be due to its hydrophobic nature. Further, F108-SAILs mixed micelles show less cytotoxicity than the individual components because charged head group of the SAILs get dissolved in the biocompatible hydrophilic corona of pluronic F108 micelles.⁴⁷ A look into **Figure 5.15** revealed that significant cell death was observed in micellar QCT as compared to free QCT. Higher cytotoxicity in case of

QCT formulations can be ascribed to the synergistic effect of F108-SAILs with QCT; F108 allows the increased transport of QCT into cells and hence leads to higher cytotoxic effect. The cytotoxicity order of QCT loaded F108-SAILs micelles are F108-Mim (cell viability is 20.12 %) > F108-Pyr (cell viability is 24.26 %) > F108-Pip (cell viability is 24.95%). Higher cytotoxicity in case of QCT loaded F108-Mim and F108-Pyr mixed micelles is due to the higher synergistic effect than QCT loaded F108-Pip mixed micelles. Similar results were reported in the literature in which cytotoxicity of chemotherapeutic drugs were increased by two to three orders of magnitude after loading into pluronic micelles.⁴⁸ Thus, the cytotoxicity results of the investigated QCT mixed micellar formulations encourages the use of the prepared formulations for the treatment of breast cancer but *in vivo* and clinical results are still required to investigate for the potential effects.

Figure 5.15: Results of MTT cell viability assay one day ($t = 24$ h) after completion of cell treatment with pluronic F108 and different SAILs with and without QCT. Indicate significant difference between cytotoxic effect on MDA-MB-231 cells treated with similar dose of QCT with and without pluronic F108 and F108-SAILs mixed micelles.

5.4 Conclusions

In the present study, we investigated the potential of pluronic- Surface active ionic liquids (SAILs) mixed micelles for solubilization of hydrophobic drug quercetin (QCT). The investigated SAILs have similar dodecyl chain length and different headgroups *viz.* imidazolium (Mim), piperidinium (Pip) and pyrrolidinium (Pyr). The solubility as well as loading efficiency of pluronic F108-SAILs mixed micelles were observed to be significantly higher as compared to individual F108 and SAILs micelles. In addition, we observed that the composition of mixed micelles has a profound effect on solubilization capacity as maximum solubility was observed at equimolar concentration ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$). Amongst all investigated F108-SAILs mixed micelles, F108-Mim mixed micelles showed higher solubilization capacity which is ascribed to presence of the π - π interactions between the π -electron system of imidazolium ring of Mim and QCT. From dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements, we observed an increment in size of mixed micelles after QCT loading which also indicates the solubilization of QCT in mixed micelles. Differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) measurements revealed that binding of QCT with F108-Mim mixed micelles was relatively stronger than other investigated F108-SAILs. This kind of behaviour can be justified due to presence of stronger cation- π interactions along with the π - π interactions between π -electron rich system of QCT and π -electron deficient cloud of imidazolium ring of Mim. *In vitro* drug release study evidenced that interactions of the QCT with the head group of SAILs have a great impact on their drug release behaviour. The presence of stronger cation- π interactions as well as π - π interactions between QCT and Mim is responsible for slower release than other two investigated SAILs systems (Pip and Pyr). The results demonstrated that composition of mixed micelles had a profound effect on solubilization capacity and the drug release behaviour from F108-SAILs mixed micelles can be easily tuned by changing the head group of SAILs. Moreover, higher cytotoxicity was observed in the case of micellar QCT than free QCT confers the anticancer efficiency of the formulations. From these results we concluded that pluronic

F108-Mim mixed micellar system are proved to be better drug delivery vehicles for QCT than pure pluronic micelles and among investigated pluronic F108-SAILs (F108-Pip and F108-Pyr) mixed micellar system.

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Chapter 6

Temperature Dependent Solubilization of Hydrophobic Antiepileptic Drug Lamotrigine in Different Pluronic Micelles

6.1 Introduction

Poor water-solubility of drugs is the most important hurdle in the pharmaceutical industry and research. The development of better formulations of approved drugs is one of the most successful scientific and industrial strategies.¹⁻³ In this context, delivery of hydrophobic drugs via pluronic micelles is an interesting alternative. Pluronic, tri-block copolymers are US-FDA approved excipients for many marketed formulations and are currently used in parenteral injections. Pluronic consist of hydrophilic block poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) and hydrophobic block poly(propylene oxide) (PPO) in a tri-block structure of PEO-PPO-PEO. The hydrophilic PEO block of the pluronic micelle is effective against serum protein adsorption, which improves the stability of nano-micellar system and increases the drug delivery. Pluronic play a significant role in pharmaceutical performance to increase the solubility, bioavailability, release and stability of hydrophobic drug molecules.⁴⁻⁸ Pluronic modulate the drug efflux transporter P-glycoprotein on the blood brain barrier (BBB) results and enhances the BBB penetration of pluronic loaded hydrophobic drugs. According to recent findings, in the drug resistance, P-glycoprotein are over-expressed and pluronic can act as modulators of P-glycoprotein, so as a drug carrier for the treatment of multidrug resistant (MDR) diseases, pluronic micellar formulation can be useful.⁹⁻¹³

Lamotrigine (LAM), 3,5-diamino-6-(2,3-dichlorophenyl)-1,2,4-triazine, is a novel antiepileptic drug, it is also used in the treatment of primary and secondary tonic-clonic seizures, and seizures associated with Lennox-Gastaut syndrome. Antiepileptic effect of LAM is due to the stabilizing pre-synaptic neuronal membranes, besides LAM inhibits sodium currents by selectively binding with the inactivated state of sodium channel and leads to repression in release of excitatory amino acid (such as, glutamate and aspartate).^{14,15} LAM belongs to the BCS (biopharmaceutical classification system)

class II drug with a pKa of 5.70. It is practically insoluble in ethanol and solubility of LAM in water is only 0.17 mg/mL at 25°C.¹⁶ Therefore, dissolution of LAM is the rate-limiting step for its efficient absorption and bioavailability in the body. Different research scientists have attempted to increase the water solubility and dissolution of LAM in order to improve its therapeutic effects. The following strategies have been employed: use of β -cyclodextrin inclusion complexes, LAM salts, and solid dispersions of LAM.¹⁷⁻²⁰ To enhance the therapeutic efficacy of LAM, its aqueous solubility needs to be improved. In order to achieve this goal, we have prepared the five different pluronic micellar formulations at three different temperatures to optimise the solubility of LAM.

There are very limited reports in literature corroborating the effect of temperature on solubilization of hydrophobic drugs in the pluronic micelles. Bandyopadhyay *et al.* described the encapsulation of three drug molecules erythromycin, ibuprofen and aspirin in pluronic F127 micelles using DLS, cryo-SEM and fluorescence measurements.²¹ Cryo-SEM imaging showed that globular structures were present even after drug encapsulation. The stability of micellar phase was enhanced over a broad temperature range after the addition of drug molecule above a specific threshold concentration. DLS measurements were used to determine changes in hydrodynamic radii and micellar polydispersities of drug-encapsulated micellar system. They observed that average hydrodynamic radii (D_h) and polydispersity of the pluronic F127 micelles were increased after the drug incorporation. However, an increase in hydrodynamic radii of micelles was found with decrease in temperature. Pyrene fluorescence spectra confirmed an increase in hydration of micellar core, accompanied with an increase in micellar sizes observed with decrease in temperature. The more compact micelles were formed upon increasing the temperature which resulted in exclusion of the solvent from the micellar core due to enhanced core hydrophobicity. The drug-encapsulated micelles also showed a strong dependence on pH. The ionization of drug molecules resulted to the formation of larger micelles when pH was increased from 4.65 to 6.1. However upon increasing the pH to 11.36, it triggered the release of drug molecules in the solvent. Authors suggested the application of drug-incorporated F127 micelles as drug carriers in the area of nanomedicine.

Kadam *et al.* reported the solubilization of hydrophobic drug carbamazepine in pluronic micelles (P103, P123, P84 and F127) at two different temperatures using UV-

visible spectroscopy and dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements.²² UV-visible spectroscopy was employed to determine drug solubility and micelle-water partition coefficient (P) whereas the size and polydispersity of nanoaggregates were determined by DLS measurements. They observed that solubilization capacity of carbamazepine in pluronic micelles increased with the increase in temperature (30°C to 37°C) and concentration of pluronics but no significant increase was observed after the addition of NaCl salt. From a thermodynamics viewpoint, the standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) was considered to describe the solubilization process. The spontaneity of the solubilization process was indicated by negative values of the solubilization free energy for carbamazepine. The comparison studies were conducted for an appropriate selection of a specific pluronic copolymer for a desired application purpose.

Pillai *et al.* studied the micellar behaviour of aqueous solutions of six pluronics *viz.* P84, F88, P103, P105, P123 and F127 and studied the solubility of three poorly water soluble anticancer drugs genistein, paclitaxel, and quercetin, at three different temperatures (25, 37 and 50°C) using UV-visible spectroscopy, high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and DLS.²³ All these investigated drugs showed improved solubility in pluronic P123 and P103 micelles with increase in temperature and salt concentration. *In vitro* drug release profiles of these formulations demonstrated slower release of drugs in pluronic micelles. The *in vitro* cytotoxicity of drug loaded pluronic micelles was also studied on MCF-7 breast cancer cell line, which showed higher anticancer activity as compared to bare drug. These results suggested that pluronics can serve as promising candidates for anticancer drug delivery.

6.2 Present work

Pluronic (tri-block copolymers) have a significant role in the pharmaceutical industry and are being used to enhance solubility and delivery of hydrophobic drugs in different marketed formulations. However the instability and unsatisfactory drug loading capacity are the major weak spots of these pluronic micelles. The present research work designed to solve the existing issues by solubilization study of hydrophobic drugs in different pluronic micelles at variable temperatures. The solubilization of hydrophobic antiepileptic drug lamotrigine (LAM) was investigated in five different pluronic micelles *viz.* P84 (PEO₁₉PPO₄₃PEO₁₉), P85 (PEO₂₆PPO₄₀PEO₂₆), F127 (PEO₁₀₀PPO₆₅PEO₁₀₀), F108

(PEO₁₃₃PPO₅₀PEO₁₃₃) and F68 (PEO₇₇PPO₂₉PEO₇₇) with 40, 50, 70, 80 and 80 % PEO content respectively at three different temperatures (37°C, 47°C and 57°C) using UV-visible spectroscopy. Hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of loaded and unloaded micelles has been studied by employing dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements. Furthermore, the effect of temperature and LAM solubilization in the investigated different pluronic micelles has been adjudged by indigenously built small angle neutron scattering (SANS) and the Heat Transfer Method (HTM).²⁴⁻²⁶ This is first report in which HTM measurements are established for the analysis of morphological changes in the thermo-responsive pluronic micelles in real time manner. *In vitro* drug release studies were performed to evaluate the relation of LAM release from these micelles with respect to increase in temperature. The rate of controlled release of LAM from five different pluronic micelles was accessed by using different kinetic models to evaluate the *in vitro* drug release profile. The present work corroborate that how we can control the drug loading capacity, morphological structure of drug carrier as well as drug release by simply changing the temperature of pluronic micellar media. The molecular structures of LAM and different pluronics are presented in **Figure 6.1**.

- (a) Pluronic P84 (m=19, n=43)
 Pluronic P85 (m=26, n=40)
 Pluronic F127 (m=100, n=65)
 Pluronic F108 (m=133, n=50)
 Pluronic F68 (m=77, n=29)

(b)

Lamotrigine (LAM)

Figure 6.1: Molecular structure of (a) Pluronics (b) Lamotrigine (LAM).

6.3 Results and Discussion

6.3.1 Solubilization of lamotrigine (LAM)

6.3.1.1 Effect of concentration

The solubilization of LAM in different pluronic F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84 micellar solutions was determined by UV-visible spectroscopy. The UV absorption spectra of LAM solubilized in P84, P85, F127 and F108 micelles was measured in the concentration range of 1% to 5% w/v at 37°C depicted in **Figure 6.2 (a), (b), (c) and (d)**. The UV absorption of LAM increased significantly in all the studied pluronic solutions except for pluronic F68, implying that pluronic micelles are able to solubilize LAM. The difference in behaviour of the pluronic F68 has been ascribed to its inability to self-assemble at studied concentration and temperature, thereby making it difficult to solubilize the drug.^{27,28} The results for solubilization capacities of the different pluronics (concentration range of 1% to 5% w/v at 37°C) for LAM are summarized in **Figure 6.3 (a)**. The solubility pattern of the drug in the different pluronics follow the order P84>P85>F127>F108>F68 at all % w/v. These results can be explained by taking into consideration the effect of PEO and PPO region of the different pluronics. Pluronic P84 show higher solubilization than pluronic P85 irrespective of the presence of almost similar PPO units (43 and 40 PPO units in P84 and P85 respectively) and differing in the presence of hydrophilic PEO units (2 x 19 and 2 x 26 PEO units in P84 and P85, respectively). On the other hand, pluronics F127 and F108 with small difference in PPO units (65 and 50 PPO units in F127 and F108, respectively) and relatively larger difference in the PEO units (2 x 100 and 2 x 133 PEO units in F127 and F108, respectively) exhibited higher solubilization in F127 as compared to F108. The results are a clear indication that solubilization capacity of pluronic micelles decreases as the PEO units forming the corona region increases. Our results are in agreement with work of Alexandridis *et al.*, which states that the micellization of pluronics decreases as the length of corona increases.²⁷

Figure 6.2: UV spectra of LAM solubilized in different pluronic micelles at various concentrations (1 to 5 % w/v) at 37°C **(a)** P84 **(b)** P85 **(c)** F127 and **(d)** F108.

Figure 6.3: **(a)** Amount of LAM solubilized in pluronic (F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84) micelles at various concentrations (1 to 5 % w/v) at 37°C **(b)** Amount of LAM solubilized in 5 % w/v pluronic (F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84) at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C.

6.3.1.2 Effect of temperature

The solubilization of LAM has been studied at different temperatures *i.e.* 37°C, 47°C and 57°C, in different pluronics (P85, P84, F108, F127 and F68) solutions. We noticed that the solubilization trend at 47°C and 57°C was same as observed at 37°C (increased in the following order P84> P85> F127> F108> F68). However, the amount of LAM solubilized in pluronic micellar system increased remarkably as the temperature increased [Figure 6.3 (b)]. UV absorption spectra of LAM solubilised in 5% w/v F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84 micelles at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C are shown in Figure 6.4 (a), (b) and (c) respectively. This was attributed to the increase in area for solubilization of LAM in pluronic micelles due to the thermal agitation, in addition to the fact that LAM solubility in water also increases with increase in temperature.²⁹⁻³¹ Alkhamis *et al.* reported similar results in case of solubilization of drug gliclazide as a function of concentration of different amphiphiles at variable temperatures 25°C and 37°C; all the investigated ionic surfactants showed higher solubilization of drugs at 37°C as compare to 25°C. The influence of temperature on the amount of drug loading also depends on whether drug molecules solubilized inside in the PEO forming hydrophilic corona or a PPO forming hydrophobic core region of pluronic micelles.³² In one report, in PEO based surfactants micelles, a decrease in solubilization of hydrophobic steroidal drugs was observed as the temperature was increased from 10°C to 50°C. The solubilization of drug in PEO corona region of micelles is the reason behind the decrease in solubility of drugs. Upon increasing the temperature, there was the dehydration of the PEO region and this leads to a decrease in the solubilizing area available for the drug. The micellar growth of pluronic micelles obtained as a result of increased temperature is the driving force for solubilization of hydrophobic drugs that especially prefer the core region of micelles.³³ In our case, solubility was increased with increase in temperature and therefore it can be concluded that most of LAM drug has been solubilized in the core region of pluronics. This micellar growth has been confirmed by the SANS measurements (Section 6.3.3). It is also important to mention that the *cmt* (Critical micelle temperature) value of pluronic P84, P85, F127, F108 and F68 (at 5% w/v) is 23,

25, 19.5, 24.5 and 40°C respectively.²⁷ Pluronic F127 have the lowest *cmt* value instead of that, drug solubilization capacity of this pluronic is lower than pluronic P85 and P84, that have the high *cmt* values. From these results it was concluded that solubility of drugs is not only depend on the *cmts* of pluronic. Other important molecular characteristic such as PEO content also plays important role in solubilization of drugs. The compilation of hydrophobic drug LAM solubilization data for a wide range of pluronic block copolymers at different temperatures presented in this chapter is, to the best of our knowledge, the most complete in literature.

Figure 6.4: UV spectra of LAM solubilized in different pluronic micelles (F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84) at (a) 37°C (b) 47°C and (c) 57°C.

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Figure 6.5: (a) Drug loading efficiency of different pluronic micelles (F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84) micelles at various concentrations (1 to 5 % w/v) at 37°C (b) Drug loading efficiency of 5 % w/v pluronic (F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84) solubilized at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C.

The drug loading efficiency is the percentage of solubilized LAM from the LAM fed in pluronic micelles during solubilization process and can be calculated from the following equation (6.1).

$$\text{Drug loading efficiency} = \frac{\text{weight of drug in micelles}}{\text{weight of drug fed initially}} \times 100 \quad (6.1)$$

The values of drug loading efficiency of 1 to 5% w/v pluronics at 37°C and 5% w/v pluronics at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C are depicted in **Figure 6.5 (a)** and **(b)** respectively (values are tabulated in **Table 6.1** and **Table 6.2**). The drug loading efficiency of P84 is higher as compared to different pluronics under study at all the concentrations and temperatures by virtue of its hydrophobicity. It is well established that hydrophobicity of pluronics can be improved by increasing the PPO content. Accordingly, P84 having a 60 % PPO content which is relatively higher than other pluronics under study, displayed the highest drug loading efficiency.^{34,35}

The partition coefficient is a crucial parameter used for the assessment of the micellar systems as potential drug carriers.³⁶ The micellar/water partition coefficient can be calculated from the photo-spectrometric results and is defined as the ratio of

amount of drug solubilized in the micelle and the drug present in water at a particular amphiphilic concentration (equation 6.2).

$$P = \frac{S_{tot} - S_w}{S_w} \quad (6.2)$$

where S_{tot} and S_w is the total solubility of LAM and solubility of LAM in water respectively. The partition coefficients have been computed, depicted in **Figure 6.6 (a)** for pluronic F108, F127, P85 and P84 micelles in the concentration range of 1% to 5% w/v at 37°C (**Table 6.1**) and are shown in **Figure 6.6 (b)** for 5% F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84 at different temperature *viz.* 37°C, 47°C and 57°C (**Table 6.2**).

Table 6.1: Loading efficiency, partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) of pluronic P84, P85, F127 and F108 micelles at various concentrations (1 to 5 % w/v) at 37°C.

	Parameters	P84	P85	F127	F108
1% (w/v)	Loading efficiency(%)	18.81	17.31	16.36	14.73
	Partition coefficient (P)	0.314	0.209	0.143	0.0291
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	2.986	4.035	5.012	9.12
2% (w/v)	Loading efficiency(%)	26.95	20.30	19.56	17.75
	Partition coefficient (P)	0.882	0.417	0.366	0.239
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	0.322	2.253	2.591	3.689
3% (w/v)	Loading efficiency(%)	32.51	23.63	22.88	22.01
	Partition coefficient (P)	1.271	0.65	0.598	0.537
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-0.616	1.108	1.325	1.601
4% (w/v)	Loading efficiency(%)	33.9	25.76	25.01	24.91
	Partition coefficient (P)	1.367	0.799	0.747	0.740
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-0.804	0.577	0.750	0.776
5% (w/v)	Loading efficiency(%)	55.10	51.33	35.5	32.41
	Partition coefficient (P)	2.848	2.585	1.479	1.264
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-2.697	-2.447	-1.008	-0.603

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Figure 6.6: (a) Micellar/water Partition coefficient (P) of different pluronic (F108, F127, P85 and P84) micelles at various concentrations (1 to 5 % w/v) solubilized at 37°C (b) Micellar/water Partition coefficient (P) of 5 % w/v pluronic micelles (F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84) solubilized at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C.

Table 6.2: Loading efficiency, partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) of 5 % w/v pluronic P84, P85, F127, F108 and F68 at three different temperatures (37°C, 47°C, 57°C).

	Parameters	5%(w/v)	5%(w/v)	5%(w/v)	5%(w/v)	5%(w/v)
		P84	P85	F127	F108	F68
37°C	Loading efficiency(%)	33.16	30.80	21.30	18.29	9.56
	Partition coefficient (P)	3.00	2.71	1.57	1.20	0.153
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-2.83	-2.57	-1.16	0.58	4.83
47°C	Loading efficiency(%)	57.83	50.06	44.16	25.35	11.74
	Partition coefficient (P)	5.97	5.04	4.12	2.05	0.41
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-4.73	-4.30	-3.77	-1.92	2.32
57°C	Loading efficiency(%)	98.67	89.88	67.33	32.16	20.21
	Partition coefficient (P)	10.90	9.84	7.12	2.88	1.43
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-6.55	-6.27	-5.38	-2.90	-0.99

It was observed that the value of partition coefficient increased by increasing the temperature among all pluronics. The highest value of partition coefficient was noted in P84 micelles at all temperatures, confirming the better partitioning of solubilized LAM

in these micelles compared to other investigated pluronic micelles. Higher partitioning of LAM in P84 micelles at all temperatures revealed the higher drug solubilization in the core of these micelles by inducing a favourable hydrophobic environment compared to other investigated pluronic micelles.³⁷

The standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) can be calculated from the partition coefficient and is represented by the following expression (6.3)

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln P \quad (6.3)$$

Where R denotes the gas constant (J/mol), T is the temperature (in Kelvin), and P is the partition coefficient. The ΔG° value depicts the Gibbs free energy of transfer of one mole of the drug in the micellar phase. The ΔG° values are depicted in the **Figure 6.7 (a)** for pluronic F108, F127, P85 and P84 micelles in the concentration range of 1% to 5% w/v at 37°C (**Table 6.1**) and shown in **Figure 6.7 (b)** for 5% w/v F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84 at different temperature *viz.* 37°C, 47°C and 57°C (**Table 6.2**). **Figure 6.7 (b)** reveals that the values of ΔG° are negative except pluronic F68 at 37°C, 47°C, showing that the process of LAM solubilization in pluronic micelles is spontaneous and transfer of water molecules from the micellar core inducing a more hydrophobic environment.³⁸⁻⁴⁰ The positive ΔG° values of pluronic F68 might be due to inability of F68 to form the micelles at the concentration and temperature (37°C and 47°C) being studied.

Figure 6.7 (a) Gibbs free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) of different pluronic (F108, F127, P85 and P84) at various concentrations 1 to 5 % w/v solubilized at 37°C. **(b)** Gibbs free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) of 5 % w/v pluronic micelles (F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84) solubilized at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C.

6.3.2 Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements

DLS experiments were performed to find out the hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of pluronic micelles as a function of temperature increase as depicted in **Figure 6.8 (a) and (b)** for aqueous solutions of 5% w/v P84 and F127 respectively at increasing temperatures 37°C, 47°C and 57°C. D_h of aqueous solutions of 5 % w/v P85, 5% w/v F108 and F68 at increasing temperatures 37°C, 47°C and 57°C are presented in the **Figure 6.8 (c), (d) and (e)** respectively. In the case of hydrophobic pluronics *viz.* P84, P85 the micellar size was observed to increase with increasing the temperature, which revealed that aggregation is stimulated by increase in the temperature. At 37°C the D_h of P84 micelles is 13.54 nm, but at the temperature 47°C and 57°C D_h of P84 micelles increased from 13.54 nm to 18.16 nm and 37.84 nm respectively; hydrophobic pluronic P85 exhibit similar increase in D_h of micelles.

Pluronic F127 and F108 formed loosely packed micelles involving few monomers, so an increase in temperature results in the removal of water and formation of more closely packed micelles with altogether decrease in the D_h of micelles. In the case of very hydrophilic pluronic F68 different peaks correlate to micelles, clusters and unimers are present at 37°C. Increase in temperature, decreases the polydispersity and disappearance of the unimers and clusters, which results in single micellar peak. D_h of LAM loaded and unloaded micelles of P84 and F127 at 5% w/v in aqueous solution at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C were measured and are depicted in **Figure 6.9 (a) and (b)** respectively. DLS plots of P85, F108 and F68 are depicted in **Figure 6.10 (a), (b) and (c)**. The micelle size of P84 at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C was 13.54, 18.16 and 37.84 nm respectively but after incorporation of LAM it increases to 14.44, 21.07 and 43.82 nm respectively. The micelle size of F127 at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C was 21.02, 18.38 and 16.89 nm respectively but after incorporation of LAM it increases to 23.22, 20.81 and 18.86 nm respectively. The micelle size of P85 at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C was 11.83, 13.76 and 15.12 nm respectively but after incorporation of LAM it increases to 13.36, 16.13 and 17.59 nm respectively. The micelle size of F108 at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C was 32.67, 29.33 and 27.44 nm respectively but after incorporation of LAM it increases to 35.39, 32.53 and 32.05 nm respectively. The micelle size of F68 at 47°C and 57°C was 8.66 and 8.99 nm respectively but after incorporation of LAM it increases to 9.98 and 10.10 nm respectively.

Figure 6.8: Intensity weighted size distribution profiles of pluronic micelles at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C (a) P84 and (b) F127 (c) P85 (d) F108 and (e) F68.

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Figure 6.9: Intensity weighed size distribution profiles for empty and LAM loaded pluronic micelles **(a)** P84 and **(b)** F127 measured from dynamic light scattering.

Figure 6.10: Intensity weighed size distribution profiles for empty and LAM loaded pluronic micelles at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C (a) P85 (b) F108 and (c) F68 measured from dynamic light scattering.

6.3.3 Small angle neutron scattering (SANS) measurements

In the SANS measurement, the differential scattering cross-section per unit volume ($d\Sigma/d\Omega$) as measured for a system of monodisperse particles in a medium can be expressed as ^{41,42}

$$\left(\frac{d\Sigma}{d\Omega}\right)(Q) = nV^2 (\rho_p - \rho_s)^2 P(Q)S(Q) + B, \quad (6.4)$$

Where n denotes the number density of particles, ρ_p and ρ_s are, respectively, the scattering length densities of particle and solvent and V is the volume of the particle. $P(Q)$ is the intraparticle structure factor and $S(Q)$ is the interparticle structure factor. B is a constant term representing incoherent background, which is mainly due to the hydrogen present in the sample.

Intraparticle structure factor $P(Q)$ is decided by the shape and size of the particle and is the square of single-particle form factor $F(Q)$ as determined by

$$P(Q) = \langle |F(Q)|^2 \rangle \quad (6.5)$$

For a spherical particle of radius R , $F(Q)$ is given by

$$F(Q) = 3 \left[\frac{\sin(QR) - QR \cos(QR)}{(QR)^3} \right]. \quad (6.6)$$

The interparticle structure factor $S(Q)$ depends on the spatial distribution of the micelles. The scattering function shows a correlation peak which indicates significant micelle–micelle interactions. The structure factor $S(Q)$ is given by⁴³

$$S(Q) = 1 + 4\pi n \int (g(r) - 1) \frac{\sin(Qr)}{Qr} r^2 dr \quad (6.7)$$

Where $g(r)$ is the radial distribution function describing the arrangement of the micelles. If one assumes a hard-sphere nearest neighbour interaction potential between the micelles and the Percus–Yevick approximation for describing the direct correlation between two scattering objects, then the analytical form of the structure factor can be written as⁴⁴

$$S(Q) = \frac{1}{1 + 24\phi G(2QR_{hs}, \phi) / (2QR_{hs})} \quad (6.8)$$

Where R_{hs} , the hard sphere micellar radius and is the physical size of the micelle. ϕ is the hard sphere volume fraction of the micelles in the solution. G is a function of $x = 2QR_{hs}$ and ϕ .

Due to the presence of large amount of D_2O in the outer PEO corona, the scattering contrast between the hydrated corona and the solvent shell expected to be poor. So we assume that $P(Q)$ depends only on the hydrophobic core radius. Thus, to fit the experimental neutron scattering data, three unknown parameters, core radius, R_c , hard sphere interaction radius, R_{hs} and volume fraction of the micelles, ϕ have been considered as fitting parameters in the analysis. The aggregation number, N_{agg} , then can be obtained from the knowledge of the core size

$$N_{agg} = \frac{4\pi(R_c^3)}{3nV_{PO}} \quad (6.9)$$

Where n is the number of PPO units in the hydrophobic block, R_c is the radius of the anhydrous core and V_{PO} is the volume of one PO unit ($96.3 \times 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^3$).

The polydispersity in size distribution of particle is incorporated using the following integration⁴⁵

$$\frac{d\Sigma}{d\Omega}(Q) = \int \frac{d\Sigma}{d\Omega}(Q, R) f(R) dR + B, \quad (6.10)$$

Where $f(R)$ is the particle size distribution and usually accounted by a log-normal distribution as given by

$$f(R) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}R\sigma} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}\left(\ln\frac{R}{R_{med}}\right)^2\right], \quad (6.11)$$

Where R_{med} is the median value and σ is the standard deviation (polydispersity) of the distribution. The mean radius (R_m) is given by $R_m = R_{med}\exp(\sigma^2/2)$. The data have been analyzed by comparing the scattering from different models to the experimental data. Throughout the data analysis, corrections were made for instrumental smearing, where the calculated scattering profiles smeared by the appropriate resolution function to compare with the measured data.⁴⁶ The fitted parameters in the analysis were optimized using nonlinear least-square fitting program to the model scattering. Micellar structure of 5 % w/v pluronics *viz.* F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84 were obtained from SANS measurements at different temperatures 37°C, 47°C, 57°C. Scattering curves of pluronics P84 and F68 are presented in **Figure 6.11(a)** and **6.11(b)** respectively and pluronic P85, F127 and F108 are presented in **Figure 6.12 (a), (b)** and **(c)** respectively. At 37°C, the SANS distribution curves of all pluronics show the existence of correlation peaks which arise due to the hard sphere repulsion between the micelles except pluronic F68.⁴⁷ The presence of unimers was only observed in the pluronic F68 at 37°C due to the high *cmt* value of F68 (5% w/v F68=40°C).⁴⁸ The value of aggregation number (N_{agg}) is higher in the pluronic P84 than P85, F127 and F108. The higher N_{agg} value of hydrophobic pluronic P84 is attributed to the minimal stability of this pluronic in water as compared to other investigated pluronics.⁴⁹ The higher aggregation number of P84 is responsible for its larger hard sphere radii ($R_{HS}=82.0$) than P85 ($R_{HS}=71.9$). Conversely,

the hard sphere radius values are higher in hydrophilic pluronics F108 ($R_{HS}=102.5$) and F127 ($R_{HS}=102.0$) than Pluronic P84, which signifies the more inter-micellar interaction of F108 and micelles than P84 due to the longer corona region. Volume fraction (ϕ) values of hydrophilic pluronics F127 ($\phi = 0.158$) and F108 ($\phi=0.142$) are higher as compared to the hydrophobic pluronics P84 ($\phi=0.089$) and P85 ($\phi=0.098$) signifies the greater D₂O penetration in the hydrophilic corona and core region of these hydrophilic pluronics (F108 and F127).⁵⁰ Various key parameters from the model for the SANS measurements viz. core radius (R_c), polydispersity, hard sphere radius (R_{HS}), volume fraction (ϕ) and aggregation number (N_{agg}) are tabulated in **Table 6.3**. The increase in temperature from 37°C to 47°C and 57°C persuades the increase of the core radius (R_c) and the aggregation number (N_{agg}). There is evidence to suggest a decrease in the hard sphere radius of hydrophilic pluronic (F108 and F127) when temperatures increased from 37°C to 57°C, conferring the removal of water from the corona region. Increase in the hard sphere radius of the hydrophobic pluronics (P84 and P85) as increase in the temperature (37°C to 57°C) is due to the increase in the aggregation numbers of these hydrophobic pluronics. In the case of pluronic P84 volume fraction (ϕ) decreases as the temperature is increased. At 37°C the volume fraction (ϕ) was 0.089 and this fall to (ϕ)=0.081 at 47°C and (ϕ) =0.060 at 57°C. A similar decrease was also observed in the

Figure 6.11: SANS data pattern (with error bars in experimental data) for (a) 5 % w/v pluronic P84 (b) 5 % w/v pluronic F68 at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C.

Figure 6.12: SANS data pattern (with error bars in experimental data) for (a) 5 % w/v pluronic P85 (b) 5 % w/v pluronic F127 (c) 5 % w/v pluronic F108 at 37°C, 47°C and 57°C.

other investigated pluronics except F68. The unimers of F68 converted in to the micelle with volume fraction is $(\phi) = 0.065$ at 47°C, and at 57°C aggregation of these micelles were increased but volume fraction was also increased from $(\phi) = 0.065$ to 0.140. The volume fraction of F68 micelles increases instead of the dehydrating effects of rise of temperature can be ascribed to the transformation of remaining F68 unimers to contribute to form more micelles.⁵¹ At 57°C, pluronic P84 with 40% PEO content converted from spherical micelles to prolate ellipsoidal micelles. The correlation peak tends to be weak in the scattering curve at 57°C and cannot be explained employing a spherical shape micelles based model.^{52,53} At higher temperature, the aggregation

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Table 6.3: Various key model parameters: core radius (R_c), polydispersity, hard sphere radius (R_{HS}), volume fraction (ϕ) and aggregation number (N_{agg}) for 5 % w/v pluronic (F68, F108, F127, P85 and P84) at 37, 47 and 57°C before and after solubilization of LAM.

System	Temperature	Core Radius R_c (nm)	Polydispersity Σ	Hard Sphere Radius R_{HS} (nm)	Volume fraction ϕ	Aggregation Number N_{agg}
5% w/v P84	37 °C	5.21	0.19	8.20	0.089	159
	47 °C	5.65	0.19	8.82	0.081	203
	57 °C	a=13.5 b=5.15	0.19	8.90	0.060	403
5% w/v P84 + LAM Drug	37 °C	5.18	0.19	8.30	0.095	156
	47 °C	5.54	0.19	8.85	0.093	191
	57 °C	a=12.8 b=5.13	0.19	8.95	0.065	360
5% w/v P85	37 °C	4.47	0.18	7.19	0.098	98
	47 °C	4.82	0.18	7.52	0.097	122
	57 °C	5.10	0.18	7.90	0.094	145
5% w/v P85 + LAM Drug	37 °C	4.45	0.18	7.23	0.098	96
	47 °C	4.79	0.18	7.63	0.098	120
	57 °C	5.04	0.18	7.95	0.094	140
5% w/v F127	37 °C	5.44	0.38	10.20	0.158	108
	47 °C	5.78	0.34	10.10	0.151	130
	57 °C	5.94	0.31	10.10	0.138	141
5% w/v F127 + LAM Drug	37 °C	5.42	0.38	10.25	0.158	107
	47 °C	5.76	0.34	10.20	0.151	129
	57 °C	5.90	0.30	10.15	0.138	138
5% w/v F108	37 °C	4.79	0.49	10.25	0.142	96
	47 °C	5.33	0.46	10.20	0.140	132
	57 °C	5.82	0.40	10.10	0.130	173
5% w/v F108 + LAM Drug	37 °C	4.67	0.48	10.30	0.145	89
	47 °C	5.24	0.44	10.30	0.143	126
	57 °C	5.66	0.39	10.20	0.140	159
5% w/v F68	37 °C	Rg = 2.11 nm (unimer)				
	47 °C	1.98	0.55	7.35	0.065	11
	57 °C	3.88	0.49	7.10	0.130	88
5% w/v F68 + LAM Drug	37 °C	Rg = 2.08 nm (unimer)				
	47 °C	2.13	0.56	7.40	0.082	14
	57 °C	3.37	0.46	7.25	0.140	57

number (N_{agg}) increases, $N_{agg} \approx 159$ at 37°C to $N_{agg} \approx 203$ at 47°C and $N_{agg} \approx 403$ at 57°C, leading to an increase in the micelle core radius. The length of core region when exceeds the stretched length of PEO corona region of the pluronic micelles, tends to the shape conversion from spherical to prolate ellipsoidal micelles. It is reported in the literature that when the temperature increases the aspect ratio also increases, which results in anisotropic growth and change in morphology of micelles to worm like and cylindrical structures.^{54,55}

Another important reason behind this kind of behaviour is change in PEO region into a less polar form with increase in temperature; moreover PEO region of P84 micelle interacts less favourably with water molecules. A weak interaction between PEO region and water molecules at 57°C results in the higher packing density at the PEO-PPO-PEO interface, which favours the morphological conversion of spherical pluronic micelles to prolate ellipsoidal micelles.⁵³ The results showed the no structural transformations of other pluronics due to insignificant increase in the aggregation number (N_{agg}). In case of Pluronic P85 with 50% PEO content, $N_{agg} \approx 98$ at 37°C to $N_{agg} \approx 122$ at 47°C and $N_{agg} \approx 145$ at 57°C, in Pluronic F127 with 70% PEO content, $N_{agg} \approx 108$ at 37°C to $N_{agg} \approx 130$ at 47°C and $N_{agg} \approx 141$ at 57°C, in Pluronic F108 with 80% PEO content $N_{agg} \approx 96$ at 37°C to $N_{agg} \approx 132$ at 47°C and $N_{agg} \approx 173$ at 57°C, in Pluronic F68 with 80% PEO content $N_{agg} \approx 11$ at 47°C to $N_{agg} \approx 88$ at 57°C. A decrease in the interactions between the water and pluronic P84 on increase in temperature was the main reason for the increase in aggregation number. Instead of the longer corona region of the other investigated micelles enable to retain the interactions of pluronics with water.

Scattering curves of pluronics P84 and F68 in the presence of LAM are shown in **Figure 6.13 (a)** and **6.13 (b)** respectively; pluronic P85, F127 and F108 in the presence of LAM are presented in **Figure 6.14 (a), (b) and (c)** respectively. The scattering data from solutions of all pluronic micelles show features that are observed in the absence of LAM drug. The SANS results evidenced the no change in the scattering features in the presence of LAM. However in the absence of LAM, the scattering intensity decreased at low values of q region when compared to data from pluronic micelles was observed. These observations indicate that the drug affects the either aggregation number or size but does not affect the shape of pluronic micelles. SANS

experiments on micellar solutions in the presence of LAM suggest that the number density of micelles increases as the pluronic micelle aggregation number decreases. This may be attributed to the rise in the micellar volume fraction due to the presence of the hydrophobic drug LAM.⁵⁶ Upon the addition of LAM, the size of cores and the coronas of the micelles increased, values are tabulated in **Table 6.3**. A significant decrease in the aggregation number of the pluronic micelles indicates that in the presence of LAM drug, micelle formation occurred even at lesser pluronic monomers. The concentration of pluronic F108, F127, P85 and P84 are above the *cmc* values, in fact the remaining monomers of pluronics participate in the formation of new micelles. Prescott *et al.* also explored the effect of addition of flurbiprofen drug, cosolvent, and temperature on the pluronic micellization using SANS measurements.⁵⁷ The scattering pattern obtained from SANS measurements revealed the attractive interactions in the micelles and/or the morphological change in the micelles at the higher flurbiprofen concentrations (1% w/v). These results demonstrate that these important factors must be considered carefully for clinical or industrial applications such as effect of various environmental conditions including the presence of cosolvent, temperature and hydrophobic species such as drug molecules, impurities, and hydrophobicity of the pluronics on micellization of pluronics.

Figure 6.13: SANS data pattern (with error bars in experimental data) for (a) P84 and (b) F68, 5 % w/v in the absence and presence of LAM drug 37°C, 47°C and 57°C.

Figure 6.14: SANS data pattern (with error bars in experimental data) for (a) P85 (b) F127 (c) F108, 5 % w/v in the absence and presence of LAM drug 37°C, 47°C and 57°C.

6.3.4 Heat Transfer Method (HTM) measurements

The working temperature range (35°C to 70°C) was chosen on the basis of the morphological transitions observed in pluronic micelles with SANS measurements. The heat transfer resistance R_{th} was calculated using equation (6.12) given below:

$$R_{th} = \frac{T_1 - T_2}{P} \quad (6.12)$$

Here T_1 and T_2 is the temperature of the copper block and temperature measured by the thermocouple that is placed in the liquid at 1.7 mm above the copper block respectively,

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P is the power applied. R_{th} measurements of pluronic P84 and pluronic F127 are displayed in **Figure 6.15 (a)** and **(b)** respectively.

The noise in the R_{th} signal is due to small fluctuations of the power input related to the PID controller. Noteworthy, irreversible changes on the electrode surface are observed as a decrease in the R_{th} upon heating. Moreover, the temperatures at which the R_{th} drops are detected correspond well to the main phase transition temperature observed by SANS measurement: the pre-transitional behaviour starts at 55.0°C and the transition is finished at 58°C [**Figure 6.15 (a)**], intimating that the modification in R_{th} correlate to a phase change between spherical micelles and the prolate ellipsoidal micellar states upon heating (R_{th} Value).

Figure 6.15: Resistance vs Temperature profiles of pluronic micelles at variable temperature **(a)** P84 and **(b)** F127 **(c)** P84 in the presence of LAM drug **(d)** F127 in the presence of LAM drug.

At the temperature where morphological changes occur (spherical micelles to prolate ellipsoidal micelles), there is decrease in the surface area of the micelles due to the elongated structure that increase the movement of the current resulting in the decrease in the thermal resistance value. There are no additional morphological changes observed in the next temperature cycle. Schematic presentation of morphological changes of spherical Pluronic P84 micelles (at 37°C) into prolate ellipsoidal micelles after reaching the temperature 55°C represented by heat flow in **Figure 6.16**.

Figure 6.16: Schematic presentation of morphological changes of spherical P84 micelles (left side, before heating) into prolate ellipsoidal micelles after reaching the temperature 55°C (right side) represented by heat flow.

In the case of pluronic F127, there is a continuous decrease in the R_{th} upon heating while the R_{th} increased to the same value upon cooling [**Figure 6.15 (b)**]. In this case there is no drop in the R_{th} value, confirming there are no morphological changes occurring on the surface. LAM loaded pluronic P84 micelles shown in **Figure 6.15 (c)** demonstrate a drop in the R_{th} starting at 52°C in the first heating cycle that ends at 58°C, which is not observed in any later heating and cooling cycles. When comparing the temperature of transition starts between the LAM loaded pluronic P84 micelles and unloaded pluronic P84 there is a difference of three degrees Celsius, favouring the morphological changes to occur at a lower transition temperature in the presence of LAM. LAM loaded F127 micelles [**Figure 6.15 (d)**] also does not show any significant difference in the R_{th} value which corresponds to a consistent morphology of the micelles.

6.3.5 *In vitro* drug release

The release of LAM from pluronic formulations at 37°C and 57°C is presented in **Figure 6.17 (a)** and **(b)** respectively. The figure depicts that the drug release starts with an initial burst followed by a slow release of LAM from the formulations prepared at 37°C was 2, 1, 0.5 and 0.5 hour faster than formulations prepared at 57°C in pluronic P84, P85, F127 and F108 respectively. LAM loaded hydrophilic pluronics of F108 and F127 that are prepared at 37°C showed 100% drug release in 2 and 2.5 h, respectively. However, a slower release rate was seen in the case of loaded hydrophobic pluronics P84 and P85 as they showed 90% LAM release in 4.5 and 5 h, respectively because most of LAM was solubilized in the core of these micelles. Five different models *viz.* zero-order kinetics, first-order kinetics, Higuchi kinetics, Hixson-Crowell model and the Korsmeyer-Peppas (KP) model were used to evaluate the data of drug release.⁵⁸ The most fitted model was selected based on comparing the coefficient of determination. To find out the release phenomenon of LAM from the pluronic micelles, correlation coefficient and rate constant were computed for all five models. From the R² values, it was ascertained that LAM release profiles of formulations solubilized at 37°C, the best fit model was the Hixson model for all pluronic micelles except the F108 micelle, for which the best fitted model was KP model, values are tabulated in **Table 6.4**. According to the KP equation, $0.5 \leq n$ (diffusional coefficient) is described with a Fickian diffusion mechanism, $0.5 < n < 1.0$ anomalous (non-Fickian) diffusion, $1.0 = n$ Case II transport, $n > 1.0$ with super case II transport.^{59,60} The diffusional coefficient (n) value less than 0.5 in case of F108 suggested that the release follows the Fickian diffusion. While in case of formulations solubilized at 57°C, the best-fitted model was Korsmeyer-Peppas (KP) for all pluronic micelles except F127 micelles, which followed Hixson model (values are tabulated in **Table 6.5**. The value of n observed in best fitted model for F68, F108, P85 and P84 pluronic micelles was observed to be more than 0.5, indicating anomalous (non-Fickian) diffusion.

Figure 6.17: *In vitro* release of LAM from different pluronic micelles (a) Formulations solubilized at 37°C (b) Formulations solubilized at 57°C.

Table 6.4: Rate constants and correlation coefficient using different kinetic model for the release behaviour of LAM from different pluronic formulations solubilized at temperature of 37°C.

System	Zero order kinetics		First order kinetics		Higuchi kinetics		Hixson-Crowell model		KP model		
	R^2	$K_0 (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K_H (-h^{-1})$	R^2	$K (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K_H (h^{-1})$	n
P84	0.871	30.72	0.795	2.099	0.958	12.86	0.965	0.251	0.948	1.675	0.544
P85	0.858	33.05	0.771	2.168	0.955	11.98	0.972	0.229	0.960	1.730	0.519
F127	0.911	23.88	0.783	2.239	0.950	7.423	0.957	-0.012	0.857	1.808	0.658
F108	0.967	39.51	0.743	2.122	0.951	4.992	0.900	0.144	0.968	1.902	0.365

Table 6.5: Rate constants and correlation coefficient using different kinetic model for the release behaviour of LAM from different pluronic formulation solubilized at lowest temperature (57°C).

System	Zero order Kinetics		First order Kinetics		Higuchi kinetics		Hixson-Crowell Model		KP model		
	R^2	$K_0 (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K_H (-h^{-1})$	R^2	$K (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K_H (h^{-1})$	n
P84	0.950	16.40	0.838	2.176	0.969	11.98	0.982	-0.052	0.986	1.388	0.742
P85	0.949	18.60	0.898	2.225	0.953	9.620	0.988	-0.098	0.990	1.546	0.700
F127	0.916	16.43	0.933	2.291	0.968	5.365	0.990	-0.207	0.957	1.616	0.963
F108	0.980	16.87	0.823	2.263	0.989	6.686	0.960	-0.298	0.997	1.761	0.692
F68	0.961	30.53	0.802	2.239	0.990	5.785	0.958	-0.079	0.992	1.853	0.522

6.4 Conclusions

In summary, we have presented the lamotrigine (LAM) solubilization in five different pluronics *viz.* P84, P85, F127, F108 and F68, using UV-visible spectroscopy at different temperatures (37°C, 47°C and 57°C). The solubilization in all pluronics was enhanced by increasing the temperature, which changes the polarity of the micelles leading to dehydration and an increase in the aggregation number. Different solubilization parameters such as the drug loading capacity, partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) were determined. Among all the investigated pluronics, P84 has the best solubilization capacity in the temperature range 37°C-57°C. Small angle neutron scattering (SANS) experiments revealed that pluronic P84 micelles converted in prolate ellipsoidal micelles from spherical micelles at 57°C. This was confirmed by dynamic light scattering (DLS) and Heat Transfer Method (HTM) and is due to higher hydrophobicity of P84 compared to other investigated pluronics. SANS results showed that the aggregation number increases in hydrophobic pluronic P84 as the temperature is increased and that is the driving force for the morphological changes in the micelles. HTM results revealed that the conversion of the spherical micelles to prolate ellipsoidal micelles starts at 55°C and ends at 58°C. Instead, the hydrophilic pluronic F127 does not show any significant change in the R_{th} value confirming that no morphological changes occur as a function of temperature. *In vitro* drug release revealed that release behaviour of LAM can be modulated by simply changing the temperature for preparation of pluronic micelle formulation. Therefore, this work opens many new areas to modulate the drug loading capacity of the hydrophobic drug in the different pluronic micelles by varying the temperature and drug release behaviour. For the first time, we have reported the use of HTM to determine morphological changes of thermos-responsive micelles.

6.5 References

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Temperature Dependent Solubilization of the Hydrophobic Antiepileptic Drug Lamotrigine in Different Pluronic Micelles

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Chapter 7

Solubilization of Hydrophobic Drugs Clozapine and Oxcarbazepine in the Lower and Higher Molecular Weight Pluronic Mixed Micelles

7.1 Introduction

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are continuously generated when oxygen is consumed for different physiological processes. ROS are comprised of free radicals and are generated under normal physiological conditions and removed by the body's antioxidant defence mechanism.¹ An imbalance between ROS and the antioxidant defence mechanism leads to oxidative stress. ROS can initiate the oxidative damage to amines, proteins, lipids, nucleic acid etc.² If these radicals are not scavenged properly, they can cause damage leading to abnormal conditions. Many diseases are the manifestation of reactive oxygen species like cancer, neuropathic pain, heart diseases, stroke, and various mental disorders like schizophrenia.³⁻⁵ Thus the abolition of free radicals generation is linked to the decrease in chronic diseases, DNA damage and pathogenic bacterial growth inhibition. Moreover, the protection against oxidative stress by the agents that can scavenge free radical or metal ion chelating agents is well known and has been associated with reduction of cellular damage.⁴

Schizophrenia and epilepsy are among the most severe and chronic forms of mental disorders but their etiopathogenesis illness is not clear.⁵ Various evidences suggest that oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation, and nitrosative stress contribute to the pathogenesis of schizophrenia and epilepsy.⁶ Clozapine [8-chloro-11-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-5H-dibenzodiazepine (CLZ)] is the drug of choice for the treatment of refractory schizophrenia and for treatment-resistant patients.^{7,8} The aqueous solubility of CLZ is 0.1889mg/mL at 25 °C. The drug has been associated with a number of side effects viz. agranulocytosis, myocarditis and seizures, therefore limiting its clinical use.⁹ Oxcarbazepine (OXC), chemically 10, 11-dihydro-10-oxo-5H-dibenz[b,f]azepine-5-

carboxamide, an antiepileptic drug has been used alone or in combination with other antiepileptic drugs as treatment therapy for partial seizures in adults and children.^{10,11} The melting point of this neutral lipophilic compound (molecular weight 252.3g/mol) is 215–216°C, has poor water solubility (0.084 mg/mL at 25 °C) and belongs to Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS), Class II drug.¹² To enhance the adsorption and bioavailability of hydrophobic drugs, many different approaches have been implied.^{13,14} Among these approaches, amphiphilic copolymers have gained attention due to its capability to enhance water solubility of poorly water soluble drugs. One specific class of amphiphilic triblock copolymers, polyethylene oxide (PEO)-polypropylene oxide (PPO)-polyethylene oxide (PEO) block copolymers known as pluronics. Pluronic have been proved to be potential drug carrier for controlled drug release and moreover can encapsulate the hydrophobic drugs. Pluronic tri-block copolymers are US FDA approved commercially available non-ionic surface active agents.¹⁵⁻¹⁹ Pluronic micelles are able to accommodate the hydrophobic drugs in the hydrophobic core made up of a PPO region and some polar drugs may solubilized in the PEO corona region. Copolymer systems provide target specific delivery and moreover long circulation time because of their small micelles/ particle sizes (less than 100 nm).²⁰⁻²³ Poor drug loading capacity, large size distribution and stability issues are often associated with micelles formed from a single pluronic. However, mixed micelles composed of different pluronics show synergistic properties compared to those composed of a single pluronic, which include improved micelle stability and increased solubilization capacity.²⁴⁻²⁷ The anticancer drug doxorubicin in the mixed micelles made up of pluronics L61 and F127, was the first anti-cancer drug containing micellar formulation to reach the clinic and is currently undergoing Phase II clinical trials.^{28,29} There are a number of studies in which pluronics serve as drug delivery carriers.

Zhai *et al.* reported the solubilisation of curcumin in mixed micelles of pluronics P123 and F68 using UV-visible spectroscopy, fluorescence spectroscopy, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), dynamic light scattering (DLS), zeta potential, central composite design (CDD), MTT assay and *in vitro* release techniques.³⁰ The optimization of the preparation process was done with the help of central composite design (CCD). The mixed pluronic micelles, comprising pluronic P123 and F68 with

the ratio at 2.05:1, exhibited higher entrapment efficiency and drug loading efficiency for curcumin. The average size of the curcumin loaded mixed micelles was 68.2 nm. The curcumin-pluronic mixed micellar formulations showed the sustained-release property as that of curcumin in propylene glycol solution. The *in vitro* cytotoxicity assay evidenced the higher cytotoxic effect of curcumin-pluronic mixed micellar formulations on MCF-7 and MCF-7/ADR cell lines. The results demonstrated the improved solubility and biological activity of curcumin when P123/F68 mixed micelles were used as drug carrier.

Mourya *et al.* exploited mixed micelles comprising hydrophilic pluronic P123 and hydrophobic pluronic L81 to solubilize the hydrophobic drug aceclofenac.³¹ DLS fluorescence spectroscopy and TEM measurements were employed for the characterization of these mixed micelles. It is well known fact that hydrophilic pluronics often produce small-sized micelles in aqueous solution whereas hydrophobic pluronics generate larger aggregates. In order to combine the advantages of different kinds of pluronics, they studied the mixture of such two types of pluronics *viz.* hydrophobic pluronic L81 and relatively hydrophilic pluronic P123. Pyrene fluorescence spectroscopy was used to determine the critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) of the mixed micellar system and was found to be 0.032 mg/mL. These measurements also showed that drug is located in between that of the individual pluronics. DLS measurements evidenced the formation of very small particles (sizes~20 nm) and low polydispersity which indicates the formation of mixed micelles. TEM measurements demonstrated the formation of spherical shaped micelles. A stable dispersions were obtained for the mixture of pluronic L81/P123 at appropriate ratio of 0.1/1.0 wt.% and 0.5/3.0 wt.% respectively. Turbidity measurement, size analysis and clarity of dispersion were used to assess stability of mixed micelles. Mixed pluronic micelles were also found to be stable in bovine serum albumin (BSA) solution. Aceclofenac loaded mixed pluronic micelles of L81/P123 showed fairly high entrapment efficiency, loading capacity and sustained release profile. However the solubilization of aceclofenac in pluronic micelles decreased in presence of salt. Thermodynamic parameters for aceclofenac solubilization in pluronic mixed micelles revealed spontaneity of drug solubilization and high partition coefficient values. The authors

reported that the prepared mixed micelles facilitate controlled and target specific drug delivery because of their small size, high encapsulation ability and stability.

Fang *et al.* studied the preparation and characterization of paclitaxel (PTX) loaded mixed micelles of pluronic P123 and F127.³² The effect of four variables, namely P123 mass fraction, amount of water, feeding of PTX and hydration temperature on drug-loading coefficient (DL %), encapsulation ratio (ER %) was investigated by a Doehlert matrix design and the percentage of PTX released from the drug-loaded mixed pluronic micelles after 48 h at 37°C (PTX precipitated %) to improve drug solubilization efficiency and micelle stability. Thin-film hydration method was employed to prepare the PTX-loaded P123/F127 mixed micelles. A particle size of about 25 nm and a sustained release behaviour of the optimized formulation were observed as compared to taxol. NMR spectroscopy confirmed the formation of pluronic P123/F127 mixed micelles. The mixed micelles showed a low *cmc* of 0.0059% in water. In addition, micelle stability studies indicated that addition of pluronic F127 (33 wt%) into P123 micelles significantly increased the stability of PTX-loaded micelles. Moreover, *in vitro* cytotoxicity of PTX loaded mixed micellar formulation was also assessed using human lung adenocarcinoma cell lines SPC-A1 and A-549 and was compared to taxol and the free drug. The result of *in vitro* cytotoxicity assay showed the 50% inhibition concentration (IC₅₀) of PTX-loaded P123/F127 mixed micelles (0.1 µg/ml) in A-549 cells which was much lower than those of taxol injection (0.4 µg/ml) and the free PTX (1.7 µg/ml). Therefore, they emphasized that P123/F127 mixed micelles of paclitaxel can serve as better anticancer drug delivery system for cancer chemotherapy.

7.2 Present work

In this work, the solubilization behaviour of oxcarbazepine (OXC) and clozapine (CLZ) in binary mixtures of lower molecular weight pluronics *viz.* L64 (PEO₁₃PPO₃₀PEO₁₃) and L35 (PEO₁₁PPO₁₆PEO₁₁) with relatively higher molecular weight pluronics *viz.* P84 (PEO₁₉PPO₄₃PEO₁₉), F127 (PEO₁₀₀PPO₆₅PEO₁₀₀), F68 (PEO₇₇PPO₂₉PEO₇₇) and P123 (PEO₂₀PPO₇₀PEO₂₀) has been adjudged by UV-visible measurements at 37°C. The drug solubility, drug loading efficiency, the micelle–water partition coefficient (*P*), and

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Gibbs free energy (ΔG°) were measured. Critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) of mixed micelles was calculated using fluorescence measurements. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements have been used to determine the hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of the loaded and unloaded pluronic mixed micelles. *In vitro* drug release studies of the best solubilized formulation of binary mixed micellar systems containing CLZ were performed to determine the drug release behaviour of the drug from the mixed micellar systems. Antioxidant activity of different formulations was determined by various antioxidant assays such as 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl free radical (DPPH•), total reducing ability determination by the Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} transformation method (reducing power activity), metal chelating activity and the scavenging assay of nitric oxide (NO).³²⁻³⁶ The molecular structures of CLZ, OXC and different pluronics are presented in **Figure 7.1**.

Figure 7.1: Molecular structure of (a) Pluronics (b) Clozapine (CLZ) (c) Oxcarbazepine (OXC)

7.3. Results and Discussion

7.3.1 Fluorescence measurements

The critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) is a major parameter in determining the *in vitro* and *in vivo* stability of polymeric mixed micelles. The *cmc* values were calculated using fluorescence spectroscopy, as shown in **Table 7.1**. The values of binary mixed micelle system are lower than the pure individual systems, which emphasises the synergistic interactions between the pluronics in the binary mixed micelles. Low *cmc* values of L64/P84(1:4) and L64/F127(1:4) mixed micelles demonstrate the high stability of these micelles upon dilution.

Table 7.1: Critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) values obtained from Fluorescence spectroscopy: Binary mixed micelles of L64 and L35 with different pluronics (P84 and F127) at different % w/v at 37°C.

Systems	0%+5%	1%+4%	2%+3%	2.5%+2.5%	3%+2%	4%+1%	0%+5%
L64+P84	0.150	0.054	0.049	0.44	0.066	0.070	0.400
L35+P84	0.150	0.063	0.058	0.068	0.088	0.089	0.452
L64+F127	0.035	0.030	0.030	0.034	0.033	0.049	0.400
L35+F127	0.035	0.031	0.039	0.037	0.047	0.062	0.452

7.3.2 Solubilization of hydrophobic drugs clozapine (CLZ) and oxcarbazepine (OXC)

The stock solution (2 mM of CLZ and OXC) was prepared in methanol and further diluted with water for obtaining the desired concentration range of 0.01 mM to 0.1 mM. The λ_{max} of CLZ and OXC was determined to be 292 nm and 255 nm respectively. The amount of methanol was low enough for directly measuring the UV absorption spectrum. The molar absorption coefficient of CLZ and OXC were calculated to be 10.54 L mol⁻¹cm⁻¹ and 8.81 L mol⁻¹cm⁻¹ respectively, using the slope of the calibration curve

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(absorbance versus concentration of CLZ and OXC). From this molar absorption coefficient, the concentration of loaded amount of CLZ and OXC was computed. The solubilization of CLZ and OXC in aqueous media at room temperature is 0.0373 mM and 0.415 mM respectively. To increase their solubility in aqueous media, we have used binary mixtures of lower molecular weight pluronics L64 and L35 and relatively higher molecular weight pluronics P84, P123, F127 and F68 with different % w/v far above their critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) values at 37°C.³⁷ As shown in **Figure 7.2 (a)** and **(b)** among all the binary mixtures, the highest solubility of CLZ was found to be 9.641 mg/5 mL in case of binary mixture of L64/P84(1:4) because of the hydrophobic nature of P84 and L64. Due to the hydrophobic nature of the CLZ, the majority of the drug prefers the hydrophobic PPO core region of L64/P84(1:4) mixed micelles.³⁸ But in the case of OXC, as shown in **Figure 7.3 (a)** and **(b)**, the highest solubility was observed for a mixture of L64/F127(1:4) (5.036mg/5mL). This is due to OXC solubilization both in the PPO core and PEO corona region because of its polar carboxamide moiety (F127 has longer corona region made up of total 130 PEO units).³⁹⁻⁴¹

Figure 7.2 Amount of CLZ solubilized in binary mixtures of **(a)** L64 with pluronics (P84, F127, F68 and P123) **(b)** L35 with pluronics (P84, F127, F68 and P123) at 37°C.

Figure 7.3 Amount of OXC solubilized in binary mixtures of (a) L64 with pluronics (P84, F127, F68 and P123) (b) L35 with pluronics (P84, F127, F68 and P123) at 37°C.

The drug loading efficiency is expressed as the percentage of solubilized drug compared to original drug feed in different pluronic micelles as shown in equation (7.1)

$$\text{Drug loading efficiency} = \frac{\text{weight of drug in micelles}}{\text{weight of drug fed initially}} \times 100 \quad (7.1)$$

As shown in **Table 7.2** and **7.3**, the drug loading efficiency of CLZ in the binary mixture L64/P84(1:4) was higher than the other binary mixtures of L64 and L35 with other pluronics (P84, F127, F68 and P123) at all % w/v, indicating the higher drug loading efficiency of this system. In case of OXC, the drug loading efficiency is higher in L64/F127(1:4) as compared to other binary mixtures of L64 and L35 with other pluronics (P84, F127, F68 and P123) and presented in **Table 7.4** and **7.5** respectively.

The micellar/water partition coefficient can be calculated from UV-visible results and is defined as the ratio of drug concentration in the micelle to the drug concentration in water at a particular surfactant concentration (Equation 7.2).

$$P = \frac{S_{tot} - S_w}{S_w} \quad (7.2)$$

where S_{tot} and S_w is the total solubility of the drug and solubility of drug in water respectively. It was found that the value of the partition coefficient increased by increasing the concentration of the pluronics. Among all the pluronics, the highest value

of the partition coefficient for CLZ was found in case of L64/P84(1:4) as tabulated in **Table 7.2 and 7.3** (binary mixtures of L64 and L35 with other pluronics (P84, F127, F68 and P123)). The partition coefficient values for OXC tabulated in **Table 7.4 and 7.5** (binary mixtures of L64 and L35 with other pluronics (P84, F127, F68 and P123)). The highest value of the partition coefficient was found in a system comprised of a mixture of L64/F127(1:4) due to solubilization of OXC in both core and corona regions.

Table 7.2: Different parameters obtained from UV-visible measurements: amount of CLZ solubilized, CLZ loading efficiency, partition coefficient (P), and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) in the mixed micelles of L64 with pluronic (P84, F127, F68 and P123).

Ratio %(w/v)	Parameters	L64+P84	L64+F127	L64+F68	L64+P123
1%+4%	CLZsolubilized (mg/5mL)	9.641	5.036	5.623	6.238
	CLZ loading efficiency(%)	96.41	50.36	56.23	62.38
	Partition coefficient (P)	157.178	81.625	91.255	101.346
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-13.040	-11.351	-11.638	-11.909
2%+3%	CLZ solubilized (mg/5mL)	4.633	3.335	0.539	0.781
	CLZ loading efficiency(%)	46.33	33.35	5.39	7.81
	Partition coefficient (P)	75.013	53.716	7.843	11.813
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-11.133	-10.272	-5.311	-6.367
2.5%+2.5%	CLZ solubilized (mg/5mL)	8.772	3.879	6.878	6.684
	CLZ loading efficiency(%)	87.72	38.79	68.78	66.84
	Partition coefficient (P)	142.921	62.642	111.846	108.663
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-12.795	-10.668	-12.163	-12.089
3%+2%	CLZ solubilized (mg/5mL)	8.264	1.079	1.078	4.688
	CLZ loading efficiency(%)	82.64	10.79	10.78	46.88
	Partition coefficient (P)	135.25	16.703	16.686	75.915
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-12.65	-7.260	-7.257	-11.164
4%+1%	CLZ solubilized (mg/5mL)	3.935	0.484	1.028	3.819
	CLZ loading efficiency(%)	39.35	4.84	10.28	38.19
	Partition coefficient (P)	63.561	6.940	15.866	61.057
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-10.703	-4.995	-7.127	-10.627

Table 7.3: Different parameters obtained from UV-visible measurements: amount of CLZ solubilized, CLZ loading efficiency, partition coefficient (P), and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) in the mixed micelles of L35 with pluronic (P84, F127, F68 and P123).

Ratio %(w/v)	Parameters	L35+P84	L35+F127	L35+F68	L35+P123
1%+4%	CLZ solubilized (mg/5mL)	9.349	4.522	3.963	7.004
	CLZ loading efficiency (%)	93.49	45.22	39.63	70.04
	Partition coefficient (P)	152.388	73.191	64.020	113.913
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-13.040	-11.351	-11.638	-11.909
2%+3%	CLZ solubilized (mg/5mL)	4.512	0.856	0.446	2.829
	CLZ loading efficiency (%)	45.12	8.56	4.46	28.29
	Partition coefficient (P)	73.027	13.044	6.377	45.415
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-11.064	-6.622	-4.753	-9.839
2.5%+2.5%	CLZ solubilized (mg/5mL)	9.361	2.441	5.986	7.479
	CLZ loading efficiency (%)	93.61	24.41	59.86	74.79
	Partition coefficient (P)	152.584	39.049	97.211	121.707
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-12.964	-9.450	-11.801	-12.381
3%+2%	CLZ solubilized (mg/5mL)	4.646	0.856	2.252	3.897
	CLZ loading efficiency (%)	46.46	8.56	22.52	38.97
	Partition coefficient (P)	75.226	13.044	35.948	62.937
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-11.140	-6.622	-9.236	-10.680
4%+1%	CLZ solubilized (mg/5mL)	3.925	0.559	1.088	1.837
	CLZ loading efficiency (%)	39.25	5.59	10.88	18.37
	Partition coefficient (P)	63.397	8.171	16.850	29.139
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-10.699	-5.416	-7.282	-8.695

The standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) can be determined from the partition coefficient and is given by the following expression (7.3).

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln P \quad (7.3)$$

where R is the gas constant (J/mol), T is the temperature (in Kelvin), and P is the partition coefficient between the micelle and the aqueous phase. The ΔG° values depict the Gibbs free energy of transfer of one mole of the drug in the micellar phase. The ΔG° values were found to be negative, indicating the spontaneity of the solubilization and transfer of water molecules from the micellar core persuading a more favourable environment and hence leading to spontaneous partition of OXC into the micelles.⁴²⁻⁴⁵

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Higher negative values of ΔG° in case of CLZ were encountered in mixtures of L64/P84(1:4) which is attributed to the more hydrophobic nature of this binary mixture (Table 7.2 and 7.3). In the case of OXC (Table 7.4 and 7.5), the highest negative value of ΔG° was observed in L64/F127(1:4) micellar medium indicated a spontaneous OXC solubilization process which can be ascribed to the solubilization of polar OXC in both core and corona region of this binary system.

Table 7.4: Different parameters obtained from UV-visible measurements: amount of OXC solubilized, OXC loading efficiency, partition coefficient (P), and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) in the mixed micelles of L64 with pluronic (P84, F127, F68 and P123).

Ratio %(w/v)	Parameters	L64+P84	L64+F127	L64+F68	L64+P123
1%+4%	OXC solubilized (mg/5mL)	3.866	6.712	5.489	3.285
	OXC loading efficiency (%)	38.66	67.12	54.89	32.85
	Partition coefficient (P)	6.385	11.824	9.486	5.277
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-4.780	-6.369	-5.801	-4.289
2%+3%	OXC solubilized (mg/5mL)	1.314	0.789	0.824	1.121
	OXC loading efficiency (%)	13.14	7.89	8.24	11.21
	Partition coefficient (P)	1.510	0.508	0.575	1.313
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-1.064	-1.744	1.422	-0.702
2.5%+2.5%	OXC solubilized (mg/5mL)	1.894	5.127	1.482	1.571
	OXC loading efficiency (%)	18.94	51.27	14.82	15.71
	Partition coefficient (P)	2.619	8.795	1.831	2.002
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-2.482	-5.606	-1.560	-1.790
3%+2%	OXC solubilized (mg/5mL)	1.048	0.850	0.962	0.932
	OXC loading efficiency (%)	10.48	8.50	9.62	9.320
	Partition coefficient (P)	1.002	0.624	0.838	0.780
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-0.006	1.215	0.454	0.638
4%+1%	OXC solubilized (mg/5mL)	0.696	0.773	0.764	0.858
	OXC loading efficiency (%)	6.96	7.73	7.64	8.580
	Partition coefficient (P)	0.330	0.477	0.460	0.640
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	2.857	1.908	2.000	1.146

Table 7.5: Different parameters obtained from UV-visible measurements: amount of OXC solubilized, OXC loading efficiency, partition coefficient (P), and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) in the mixed micelles of L35 with pluronic (P84, F127, F68 and P123).

Ratio %(w/v)	Parameters	L35+P84	L35+F127	L35+F68	L35+P123
1%+4%	OXC solubilized (mg/5mL)	4.561	6.507	4.844	2.628
	OXC loading efficiency (%)	45.61	65.07	48.44	26.28
	Partition coefficient (P)	7.713	11.431	8.255	4.021
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-5.267	-6.282	-5.443	-3.588
2%+3%	OXC solubilized (mg/5mL)	1.430	1.082	1.116	1.125
	OXC loading efficiency (%)	14.30	10.82	11.16	11.25
	Partition coefficient (P)	1.732	1.067	1.132	1.149
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	-1.417	-0.168	-0.320	-0.359
2.5%+2.5%	OXC solubilized (mg/5mL)	1.017	1.769	1.635	1.700
	OXC loading efficiency (%)	10.17	17.69	16.35	17.00
	Partition coefficient (P)	0.944	2.380	2.125	2.248
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	0.147	-2.236	-1.944	-2.088
3%+2%	OXC solubilized (mg/5mL)	0.940	1.262	0.832	1.305
	OXC loading efficiency (%)	9.400	12.62	8.320	13.05
	Partition coefficient (P)	0.797	1.412	0.590	1.493
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	0.583	-0.889	1.358	-1.035
4%+1%	OXC solubilized (mg/5mL)	0.687	0.626	0.523	0.807
	OXC loading efficiency (%)	6.870	6.260	5.230	8.07
	Partition coefficient (P)	0.313	0.197	0.048	0.542
	$\Delta G^\circ(kJmol^{-1})$	2.993	4.181	7.819	1.578

7.3.3 Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) is a very versatile technique for the determination of size changes in colloidal particles.⁴⁶ The size of drug carrier is also important in drug delivery because it plays an important role in drug accumulation and penetration in cells i.e. the micelle size should be large enough for circulation as well as small enough for

their penetration.⁴⁷ Among all the binary mixtures of pluronic formulations, L64 and L35 with P84 show higher solubilization for CLZ. In case of OXC, binary mixture of L64/F127(1:4) showed higher solubilization. Therefore, DLS measurements of these best solubilized mixed micellar formulations were observed (at 37°C) to further explore these mixtures as potential drug carriers.³⁸ To understand the effect of drug solubilization on the mixed micellar size of the pluronics, DLS studies were performed for loaded and empty binary mixed micellar solutions. The D_h value of pure P84 was 13.54 ± 0.1 nm. The D_h value [from **Figure 7.4 (a-e)**] of empty binary mixed micelles of L64 with P84 at different % w/v viz. L64/P84(1:4), L64/P84(2:3), L64/P84(2.5:2.5), L64/P84(3:2), L64/P84(4:1) were found to be 10.971, 8.391, 9.574, 9.553 and 8.949 ± 0.1 nm respectively. The size decreases due to the synergistic interactions between pluronics which confirm the formation of mixed micelles.⁴⁸ On the other hand, after solubilization of CLZ in the binary mixtures of pluronics, D_h of CLZ loaded mixed micelles were found to be 16.615, 13.757, 15.056, 18.235 and 14.802 ± 0.1 nm, respectively [**Figure 7.4 (a-e)**]. A significant difference was observed between the D_h of unloaded and loaded binary mixed micelles of different pluronics indicated that CLZ has got solubilized in the core of mixed micelles of the pluronics and it was responsible for swelling of the mixed micelles. In the binary mixture of L64/F127(1:4), the size of empty mixed micelle was 12.045 ± 0.1 nm and size of OXC loaded mixed micelle was 20.880 ± 0.1 nm as shown in **Figure 7.4 (f)**. There was a significant increase in size of mixed micelle because OXC solubilized both in PPO core and PEO corona region. In the binary mixtures of L35 with P84 at different % w/v, D_h (shown in **Figure 7.5**) of empty binary mixed micelles were found to be 13.80, 14.122, 14.468, 14.802 and 16.420 ± 0.1 nm in L35/P84(1:4), L35/P84(2:3), L35/P84(2.5:2.5), L35/P84(3:2) and L35/P84(4:1) respectively. On the other hand, D_h of CLZ loaded binary mixed micelles L35/P84(1:4), L35/P84(2:3), L35/P84(2.5:2.5), L35/P84(3:2) and L35/P84(4:1) were found to be 16.919, 18.747, 19.810, 20.128 and 20.371 ± 0.1 nm. These results also showed that there was swelling of mixed micelles after the addition of CLZ which confirm its solubility in different binary mixed micelles.

Figure 7.4: Intensity weighed size distribution profiles for empty and CLZ loaded mixed micelles of L64 + P84 at different % w/v **(a)** 1% w/v L64 + 4% w/v P84 **(b)** 2% w/v L64 + 3% w/v P84 **(c)** 2.5% w/v L64 + 2.5% w/v P84 **(d)** 3% w/v L64 + 2% w/v P84 **(e)** 4% w/v L64 + 1% w/v P84; **(f)** OXC loaded mixed micelles of 1% w/v L64 + 4% w/v F127.

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Figure 7.5: Intensity weighed size distribution profiles for empty and CLZ loaded mixed micelles of L35 + P84 at different % w/v (a) 1% w/v L35 + 4% w/v P84 (b) 2% w/v L35 + 3% w/v P84 (c) 2.5% w/v L35 + 2.5% w/v P84 (d) 3% w/v L35 + 2% w/v P84 (e) 4% w/v L35 + 1% w/v P84.

7.3.4 *In vitro* drug release

In vitro drug release from the micellar medium is an important test since it provides an idea about their behaviour *in vivo*.¹⁹ To determine the CLZ release in the binary mixture of L64 and L35 with P84 and OXC release in the binary mixture of L64/F127(1:4) the dialysis bag method has been employed (at 37°C). In the binary mixed micelles of L64 with P84, CLZ release profile shows that there was 65.56%, 78.02%, 76.84%, 72.66% and 100% release from the binary mixtures of L64/P84(1:4), L64/P84(2:3), L64/P84(2.5:2.5), L64/P84(3:2), L64/P84(4:1) respectively after 5h [Figure 7.6 (a)]. The CLZ drug release becomes slow after initial burst release. The 100% release from the binary mixtures of L64/P84(1:4), L64/P84(2:3), L64/P84(2.5:2.5) and L64/P84(3:2) takes 26h, 22h, 20h and 20h respectively. This shows that the release become slower with increases in the amount of P84.

On the other hand, in the binary mixtures of L35 with P84, burst CLZ release was observed from the binary micelles *viz.* L35/P84(1:4), L35/P84(2:3), L35/P84 (2.5:2.5), L35/P84 (3:2) and L35/P84 (4:1) *i.e.* 58.53%, 61.37%, 85.44%, 73.03% and 100% respectively in 5 h [Figure 7.6 (b)]. The release slowed down with time and takes 56 h, 48 h, 22 h and 28 h to release from the binary mixtures L35/P84(1:4), L35/P84(2:3), L35/P84(2.5:2.5) and L35/P84(3:2) respectively. This shows a similar trend as the above mentioned binary systems (L64/P84) and indicates that with the increase in amount of P84, the release slowed down.

Figure 7.6: *In vitro* release of CLZ from binary mixtures at 37°C of (a) L64 with P84 at different % w/v (b) L35 with P84 at different % w/v.

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In case of OXC, it showed a sustained release from the binary system of L64/F127(1:4) but release was faster than pluronic P84 formulations. This was attributed to the longer hydrophilic corona region of pluronic F127 that results in faster release of OXC. After 5 h, 74% of the drug was released (**Figure 7.7**). The 100% drug was released after the 20 hours.

Figure: 7.7 *In vitro* release of OXC from binary mixture of 1% w/v L64 + 4% w/v F127 at 37°C.

The drug release data was analysed using five mathematical models viz. zero-order kinetics, first-order kinetics, Higuchi kinetics, Hixson-Crowell model and the Korsmeyer-Peppas (KP) model. Correlation coefficient (R^2) and rate constant (K) values were calculated for all five models and presented in **Table 7.6** and **Table 7.7**. The most appropriate model was chosen based on the R^2 values of the fit. In the binary mixtures of L64/P84(1:4), L64/P84(3:2), L64/P84(4:1), L35/P84(1:4) and L35/P84(2:3) the R^2 values obtained from Korsmeyer-Peppas model are higher than the other models. In the binary mixtures viz. L64/P84(1:4), L64/P84(3:2), L35/P84(1:4) and L35/P84(2:3) the values of n of less than 0.45 correspond to a Fickian diffusion mechanism, whereas in L64/P84(4:1) the value of n was greater than 0.45 which corresponds to non-Fickian transport.⁴⁹

On the other hand in the binary systems of L64/P84(2.5:2.5), L35/P84(2.5:2.5) and L35/P84(3:2) the higher values of R^2 obtained from the first order kinetics model

which describes systems where the drug release rate is independent of the concentration of the dissolved drug. In the binary mixture of L64/P84(2:3), the highest value of R^2 was obtained from Hixson-Crowell model which shows that the release is from the systems where there is change in diameter and surface area of particles. In the binary mixture of L35/P84(4:1) the highest value of R^2 was obtained from Higuchi model kinetics suggesting that CLZ release from the binary mixture follows the Higuchi model and the process is diffusion controlled. In the binary system of L64/F127(1:4) containing OXC, the highest value of R^2 was also obtained from the first order kinetics model which describes the systems where the drug release rate is independent of the concentration of the dissolved drug.⁵⁰

Table 7.6: Rate constants and regression correlations using different kinetic models for the release behaviour of CLZ from the binary mixtures of L64 with P84 at different %w/v.

System	Zero order kinetics		First order kinetics		Higuchi kinetics		Hixson-Crowell model		KP model		
	R^2	$K_0 (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K_H (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K_H (h^{-1})$	n
1%L6+ 4%P84	0.827	2.600	0.942	-0.054	0.953	15.520	0.864	0.126	0.981	1.593	0.302
2%L6+ 3%P84	0.667	3.099	0.877	-0.083	0.849	17.940	0.899	0.141	0.895	1.600	0.362
2.5%L64 + 2.5%P84	0.745	3.875	0.984	-0.090	0.906	21.040	0.933	0.191	0.957	1.573	0.389
3%L64 + 2%P84	0.775	4.072	0.953	-0.096	0.928	21.890	0.959	0.173	0.960	1.513	0.439
4%L64 + 1%P84	0.938	17.290	0.925	-0.348	0.984	48.57	0.916	0.804	0.986	1.636	0.557

Table 7.7: Rate constants and regression correlations using different kinetic models for the release behaviour of CLZ from the binary mixtures of L35 with P84 at different %w/v.

System	Zero order kinetics		First order kinetics		Higuchi kinetics		Hixson-Crowell model		KP model		
	R^2	$K_0 (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K_H (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K (h^{-1})$	R^2	$K_H (h^{-1})$	n
1%L35+ 4%P84	0.738	1.469	0.875	-0.024	0.915	9.758	0.921	0.046	0.939	1.540	0.275
2%L35+ 3%P84	0.766	1.686	0.895	-0.038	0.919	11.930	0.940	0.067	0.951	1.558	0.294
2.5%L35+ 2.5%P84	0.557	2.673	0.893	-0.081	0.752	15.980	0.820	0.134	0.833	1.675	0.313
3%L35+ 2%P84	0.737	2.206	0.942	-0.057	0.891	13.980	0.885	0.119	0.937	1.642	0.276
4%L35+ 1%P84	0.976	14.69	0.907	-0.327	0.988	39.85	0.817	0.858	0.954	1.743	0.348

7.3.5 DPPH radical scavenging activity

The DPPH radical scavenging capacity was determined for pure drugs CLZ and OXC, CLZ and OXC unloaded and loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64/P84(1:4) and L64/F127(1:4) respectively, depicted in **Figure 7.8**.⁵¹ The antioxidant reduces the DPPH radical from a dark purple-colored compound to a light yellow-colored compound, diphenyl-picryl hydrazine; the degree of the reaction relies on the hydrogen- or electron-donating ability of the antioxidant. After addition of both the test formulations and free drugs at a concentration ranging from 200-1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, partial free radicals consumption was observed. Our results evidenced higher radical scavenging activity of CLZ loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64/P84(1:4) and found to be 79.88 % at a concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ as compared to unloaded mixed micelles of L64/P84(1:4) and the free drug (CLZ). In case of OXC loaded mixed micelles of L64/F127(1:4), the % DPPH scavenging activity was found to be 49% at a concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ which indicated a lower radical scavenging activity compared to L64/P84(1:4)/CLZ mixed micelles [**Figure 7.8 (a)**]. Moreover IC_{50} (50 % inhibitory concentration) of CLZ loaded mixed micelles was also calculated and was found to be 481.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ as shown in **Figure 7.8 (b)**. There was a significant statistical difference between the mean DPPH radical scavenging values ($p < 0.01$). The higher antioxidant activity of CLZ loaded mixed micelles of L64/P84(1:4) can be attributed to the increased particle distribution and smaller size of L64/P84(1:4) micelles.⁵²

Figure 7.8: (a) DPPH scavenging activity (%) of bare drugs (CLZ and OXC), OXC and CLZ unloaded and loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64:F127(1:4) and L64:P84(1:4) respectively (b) IC_{50} of CLZ loaded L64: P84(1:4) mixed micelles.

7.3.6 Metal chelating activity

The method by Dinis *et al.* was used to estimate the chelating of ferrous ions by pure drugs CLZ and OXC, CLZ and OXC unloaded and loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64/P84(1:4) and L64/F127(1:4) respectively.³⁴ Ferrozine can quantitatively form complexes with Fe^{2+} . In the presence of chelating agents, the complex formation is disrupted with the result that the red colour of the complex is decreased. As shown in **Figure 7.9 (a)**, both CLZ and OXC loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64/P84(1:4) and L64/F127(1:4) respectively interfered with the formation of ferrous and ferrozine complex, suggesting that it has chelating activity and captures ferrous ion before ferrozine. There was a linear decrease in the absorbance of the ferrozine- Fe^{2+} complex in a concentration dependent manner (from 200 to 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). The higher metal chelating activity of CLZ loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64/P84(1:4) was observed compared to unloaded mixed micellar formulation and CLZ alone. At concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the percent metal chelating capacity of CLZ unloaded and loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64/P84(1:4) was found to be 20% and 78% respectively. Although OXC loaded mixed micelles L64/F127(1:4) also showed good metal chelating activity as compared to OXC alone. The percent metal scavenging capacity (at 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) of OXC unloaded and loaded L64/F127(1:4) mixed micellar formulation was found to be 10% and 52% respectively. IC_{50} value of CLZ loaded mixed micelles of L64:P84 was found to be 343.2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ [**Figure 7.9 (b)**] whereas OXC loaded L64:F127 mixed micelles showed IC_{50} at 755.3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ [**Figure 7.9 (c)**]. From IC_{50} values it can be evidenced that CLZ loaded mixed micellar formulation has better antioxidant activity as compared to OXC loaded mixed micellar formulation. However, a significant difference in the ferrous ions chelating capacity for both mixed micellar formulations of CLZ and OXC was observed as compared to drug alone.

Neurodegenerative diseases like Schizophrenia and Alzheimer, oxidative reactions *in vivo* are the one of the major contributors to the pathogenesis. As the transition metals iron and copper can promote oxidative damage thus agents which chelate the metal ions can have an antioxidant effect. The data obtained from **Figure 7.9 (a)** reveal that the both mixed micellar formulation of CLZ and OXC demonstrate an

effective capacity for iron binding, suggesting that its action as peroxidation protector may be related to its iron binding capacity. So it can be suggested that these drug loaded mixed micellar approach can serve as a better drug carrier and can be explored in future for the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases.⁵³

Figure 7.9: (a) Metal chelating activity (%) of bare drugs (CLZ and OXC), OXC and CLZ unloaded and loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64:F127(1:4) and L64:P84(1:4) respectively and IC₅₀ of (b) CLZ loaded mixed micelles of L64:P84(1:4), (c) OXC loaded mixed micelles of L64:F127(1:4).

7.3.7 Reducing power assay

The reducing power method of Oyaizu was applied to quantify the antioxidant activity of pure drugs CLZ and OXC, CLZ and OXC unloaded and loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64/P84(1:4) and L64/F127(1:4) respectively.³⁵ As can be seen from **Figure 7.10**, both the mixed micellar formulations at different concentrations (200-1000

$\mu\text{g/mL}$) showed effective reducing power activity when compared to pure drugs. The reducing power of investigated formulations and free drugs increased steadily as with increase in concentration. The reducing power of both mixed micellar formulations and drug alone at higher concentration (1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were in the following order: L64/P84(1:4)/CLZ > L64/F127(1:4)/OXC > L64/P84(1:4) > CLZ > L64/F127(1:4) > OXC. The results demonstrated that both formulations neutralized free radicals by forming stable products and can be attributed to electron donating capacity of investigated formulations.⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶

Figure 7.10: Reducing power activity of of bare drugs (CLZ and OXC), OXC and CLZ unloaded and loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64:F127(1:4) and L64:P84(1:4) respectively.

7.3.8 Nitric oxide (NO) scavenging activity

The method of Garrat *et al.* was employed to study the NO scavenging activity of pure drugs CLZ and OXC, CLZ and OXC unloaded and loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64/P84(1:4) and L64/F127(1:4) respectively.³¹ **Figure 7.11 (a)** represents the comparative NO scavenging activity of the both mixed micellar formulations and drugs alone. Both mixed micellar formulations exhibited well NO scavenging by reducing nitrite concentration in the assay medium in concentration dependent manner (200-1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). The mixed micellar formulations of CLZ loaded L64/P84(1:4) and OXC loaded L64/F127(1:4) showed maximum activity of 78.06% and 58.48% (at 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) respectively as compared to drug alone whereas NO scavenging activity for

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unloaded mixed micelles of L64/P84(1:4) and L64/F127(1:4) was found to 30% and 20% respectively. IC₅₀ value of CLZ and OXC loaded mixed micellar formulations was found to be 383.9µg/mL and 756.9µg/mL respectively as shown in **Figure 7.11 (b)** and **(c)** respectively. A decrease in the absorbance at 550nm by the test compound is linked to the NO scavenging capacity.

Figure 7.11: (a) NO scavenging activity (%) of bare drugs (CLZ and OXC), OXC and CLZ unloaded and loaded mixed micellar formulation of L64:F127(1:4) and L64:P84(1:4) %w/v) respectively and IC₅₀ of **(b)** CLZ loaded mixed micelles of L64:P84(1:4), **(c)** OXC loaded mixed micelles of L64:F127(1:4).

As sodium nitroprusside releases NO which can alter the structure and function of many cellular components. Besides, incubation of solutions of sodium nitroprusside in phosphate buffer saline at 25°C for 2 hour resulted in linear time-dependent nitrite production, a stable product of NO, potentiates nitrosative stress which can aggravate diseases like schizophrenia. Therefore, mixed micellar formulations can be useful in

pharmaceutical industries as potential drug carrier for drugs which are used to treat neurodegenerative diseases like schizophrenia.⁵⁷

7.4 Conclusions

In this work, we studied the solubilization of the hydrophobic drugs clozapine (CLZ) and oxcabazepine (OXC) in binary mixed micelles of low molecular weight pluronics L64 and L35 and high molecular weight pluronics P84, F127, F68 and P123. From the obtained results, it was concluded that the highest solubility of CLZ was observed in binary mixture of L64/P84(1:4) due to the hydrophobic nature of P84 and L64. In case of OXC, the highest solubility was observed in L64/F127(1:4) because the drug solubilized both in the core and the corona region of F127 since OXC contains a carboxamide polar moiety. From dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements, it was concluded that there was an increase in the size of mixed micelles from empty mixed micelles to drug (CLZ and OXC) loaded mixed micelles. Further fluorescence spectroscopy indicated that the *cmc* decreased with the formation of mixed micelles as compared to pure individual micelles. *In vitro* release study of CLZ showed that as the amount of P84 in the binary mixtures of L64/P84 and L35/P84 decreases, the release become faster. Therefore, it is possible to control the drug release from the pluronic micelles by simply varying the concentration of one pluronic. The results of DPPH, Metal chelating activity, Nitric oxide and Reducing power assays evidenced the significantly higher antioxidant activity of formulations than the bare drugs (CLZ and OXC). It is anticipated that the formulations L64/P84(1:4)/CLZ and L64/F127(1:4)/OXC may act as the efficient drug carriers for the drug delivery of CLZ and OXC respectively.

7.5 References

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Summary

Amphiphile is described as a chemical compound that owns both hydrophilic and hydrophobic moieties attached by covalent bonds. Amphiphiles have gained immense attention due to their properties as they can self-assemble in aqueous solution to form different structures, *viz.* micelles, vesicles, nanotubes, nanorods, and nanosheets which can be applied in many fields ranging from drug/gene delivery, nanodevices, template synthesis and cell imaging. The properties and the structures of self-assemblies created by amphiphiles are determined by their architectures such as geometric packing constraints and the hydrophilic-hydrophobic balance (HLB) and experimental conditions, such as temperature, concentration, pH, and ionic strength. For instance, bolaform amphiphiles have two head groups attached to one alkyl chain that are normally found in the cell membranes of thermophilic bacteria and possess high thermal resistance. The idea of amphiphile has been expanded to polymers. Predominantly, polymeric amphiphiles are formed by linking a hydrophilic part and a hydrophobic part via a covalent bond. Polymeric amphiphiles provide structural diversity and stability as that of low molecular weight amphiphiles. The self-assemblies produced by polymeric amphiphiles possess greater capacity for guest molecules and improved thermal sustainability. For instance, the assemblies formed by low molecular weight amphiphiles are comparatively dynamic in nature, due to the balance between the aggregated molecules and the dissociated non-aggregated molecules in the bulk solution. However the stronger interactions as well as the entanglement between the polymer chains of aggregates constructed by polymeric amphiphiles prevent quick molecular exchange. The unique property of the polymeric topology has led to applications in drug delivery and template synthesis of nanomaterials.

Pluronics are commercially available ABA type water soluble triblock copolymers, consists of polyethylene oxide (PEO) and polypropylene oxide (PPO) units arranged in a PEO-PPO-PEO structure. The blocks of the pluronic constructed via both hydrophilic PEO segment and hydrophobic PPO segment enable them to form the micelles in aqueous medium. There are two ways via which pluronic micelles formation

can occur by **(a)** increasing the concentration of pluronic at or above the critical micelle concentration (*cmc*), or **(b)** increasing temperature of the pluronic solution until the critical micelle temperature (*cmt*) which results in decrease of *cmc*. The interest in pluronics have arises over the conventional block copolymers due to their enormous properties such as high surface-active, low-toxicity with excellent biodegradability and biocompatibility. Pluronic have been applied in many industries in dispersion as stabilizing agents, emulsifiers, foaming, lubrication, cosmetics and detectable inks etc., along with number of pharmaceutical applications such as in drug solubilization including proteins, growth factors, gene and nano-medicine.

Ionic liquids (ILs) are extraordinary chemical compounds, which have multiple applications in modern science. On account of their highly tunable nature and exceptional properties, ILs become essential players in the fields of extraction, synthesis and catalysis, electrochemistry, biotechnology, analytics, etc. In addition to physical and chemical features of ILs, their high biological activity has been attracting significant attention from biochemists, ecologists, and medical scientists. The ILs having long chain cations are amphiphilic and are known as surface active ionic liquids (SAILS). The most unique characteristics of SAILS are their physicochemical properties as these can be easily modified by simply changing the cation or anion. Another important class of bio-surfactants known as bile salts; exist in ionic form at physiological conditions and amphipathic in nature. Bile salts are obtained from cholic acid and the end products of cholesterol. The synthesis of bile salts occurs in the liver and then released into the intestinal lumen where they incorporate cholesterol and other hydrophobic compounds facilitating their gastrointestinal absorption. Bile salts possess hydrophilic groups that are attached to the hydrophobic tetracyclic steroid ring system; and they are ranging from one to three hydroxyl (OH) groups and one acidic group.

The low to minimal water solubility is the major disadvantage faced by about 40% of drugs in the market and nearly 90% of molecules in the new drug development pipeline. Moreover, the poor solubility of drugs often led to the low bioavailability which results in suboptimal drug delivery. Several attempts have been made by many pharmaceutical companies to reformulate the hydrophobic drugs in order to enhance their water solubility, bioavailability, efficacy with targeted drug delivery. In the present

thesis, we mainly focused on conventional surface active agents such as pluronic triblock copolymer and their mixture with bile salts and surface active ionic liquids (SAILs) to explore the solubilization of antiepileptic, antipsychotic and anticancer hydrophobic drugs. Incorporation of hydrophobic drug into pluronic co-polymeric amphiphilic micelles leads to increased solubility, metabolic stability and circulation time. Moreover mixed micelles manifest synergistic properties, such as increased micelle stability and drug loading efficiency, superior to those of the individual micelles. The present thesis aims to explore the drug solubilization capacity and drug release behaviour of pluronic micelles; factors affecting the solubilization capacity such as length of corona region or palisade layer; temperature and presence of different ionic and non-ionic surfactants for their potential use in drug formulations. To estimate the solubilization capacity and *in vitro* drug release of various hydrophobic drugs in different surfactant micelles, UV-visible spectroscopy has been employed. Steady state fluorescence spectroscopy has been used to determine the *cmc* values of amphiphilic micelles. The solubilization locus of these drugs is studied by various techniques such as proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (^1H NMR), high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV). The compatibility between the drugs and amphiphilic micelles is determined by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD), fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The morphological characteristics of unloaded and loaded micelles are identified by dynamic light scattering (DLS), Heat Transfer Method (HTM) and small angle neutron scattering (SANS) measurements. The main objectives of this thesis are outlined as follows:

1. To compare the effect of corona region or palisade layer of different pluronic micelles on the solubilization capacity of hydrophobic drug molecules and probe the possible location of the drug in these micelles.
2. To evaluate the physicochemical aspects such as solubilization capacity, drug loading efficiency, average number of drug molecules solubilized per micelle (n_s), partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) of hydrophobic drug in mixed micellar system comprising pluronic and ionic bile salts.

3. To investigate the solubilization behaviour of hydrophobic drug in the mixed micelles of pluronic and surface active ionic liquids (SAILs) to enhance their aqueous solubility and cytotoxic effects on cancer cell lines.
4. To evaluate the effect of temperature on the morphology, solubilization and *in-vitro* release behaviour of hydrophobic drugs in different pluronic micelles.
5. To identify the mixed micellar system for the delivery of hydrophobic drugs and to enhance their antioxidant potential for their desired effects.

The thesis has been divided into seven chapters and are briefly described as below:

Chapter 1: Introduction

Chapter 1 emphasize on the brief introduction about the amphiphiles *viz.* Pluronic, bile salts and surface active ionic liquids (SAILs). Furthermore, a short survey of literature related to the thesis is discussed in this chapter. The effect of temperature and different amphiphilic molecules on the micellar properties and hydrophobic additive (such as drug molecules) solubilization of pluronic micelles and their use in drug delivery purposes have been described. An updated list of most relevant and important publications to the work reported is provided in this chapter,

Chapter 2: Experimental

The experimental chapter is divided into two sections. First section, provides the molecular structures of the compounds, molecular formulae, molecular weight, purity percentage and source of purchase of commercially available compounds, Second section concerned on the methods that are used to investigate the interactions of pluronic micelles with other amphiphiles such as bile salts and SAILs; solubilization capacity and solubilization locus of hydrophobic drugs in pluronic micelles. This section is divided into sixteen sub sections which are as follows:

- ❖ UV-visible measurements
- ❖ Fluorescence measurements
- ❖ Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) measurements
- ❖ Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR) measurements

- ❖ Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements
- ❖ Small angle neutron scattering (SANS) measurements
- ❖ Differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) measurements
- ❖ Heat Transfer Method (HTM) measurements
- ❖ High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) measurements
- ❖ Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) measurements
- ❖ Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements
- ❖ *In vitro* cell viability assay
- ❖ DPPH free radical scavenging activity
- ❖ Metal chelating activity
- ❖ Reducing power assay
- ❖ Nitric oxide (NO) scavenging assay

Chapter 3: Solubilization and In Vitro Release of Hydrophobic Drug Oxcarbazepine (OXC) in Pluronic Micelles

The **chapter 3** focussed to enhance the solubility of oxcarbazepine (OXC) in different pluronics *viz.* F108 (PEO₁₃₃-PPO₅₀-PEO₁₃₃), F127 (PEO₁₀₀-PPO₆₅-PEO₁₀₀) and P84 (PEO₁₃-PPO₄₃-PEO₁₃) micelles and probed the effect of length of the corona on the solubilization of OXC in the core of different pluronic micelles. UV-visible spectroscopy measurements were employed to estimate the solubilization capacity of different pluronic micelles. The UV-visible results revealed that maximum amount of OXC are solubilized in P84 among the investigated pluronics. The reason behind the higher solubility in case of P84 can be its smaller PEO region (only 38 PEO units) that makes it more hydrophobic in nature which allows the transfer of OXC into the core region. The lower solubilization in case of F127 and F108 can be attributed to their longer corona region which acts as a barrier for the movement of OXC in the core region which in turn is responsible for its higher solubilization in corona region. Besides, solubility was found to be higher in F127 (200 PEO units) as compared to

F108 (266 PEO units). Different solubility parameters *viz.* Partition coefficient, Gibbs free energy of solubilization and drug loading efficiency has been determined for all pluronic micellar formulations. The higher value of partition coefficient was found to be for P84 among all the pluronics which is due to its more hydrophobic microenvironment for solubilized OXC. Higher negative value of ΔG° in case of P84 was ascribed to the more spontaneous solubilization of the OXC in P84 micellar medium. On the other hand in case of F127 and F108 micellar medium, the less negative values of ΔG° signifies that OXC solubilization process was less spontaneous which can be ascribed to the more amount of the OXC solubilized in the corona region of micelles. Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) and proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (^1H NMR) techniques were employed to adjudge the locus of solubilization. The difference between the ITC enthalpograms of hydrophilic pluronics (F127 and F108) and hydrophobic pluronic (P84) highlights the different mode of interaction of OXC with these pluronics. ^1H NMR measurements evidenced the chemical shifts in both PPO and PEO proton, revealed that polar OXC interact with both PPO block forming core and PEO units forming corona. However the higher chemical shift in PPO region confirms that more OXC is located in PPO region while in case of pluronic F127 and F108, the PPO protons experienced a small upfield shift as compared to the pluronic P84. Higher chemical shift in PPO protons as compared to PEO protons confirms stronger interaction of OXC with PPO blocks. In the presence of OXC, the PPO protons showed higher chemical shift in P84 as compared to F127, corroborating with UV-visible results that more OXC located in core of P84 micelles. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) techniques further confirmed the solubilization of OXC in pluronic micelles. *In vitro* drug release study evidenced that the locus of solubilization has a great impact on their drug release. The OXC being solubilized in the core of P84 micelles takes more time to release as compared to hydrophilic pluronics i.e. F127 and F108 where most of OXC is solubilized in the corona region. Different kinetic models *viz.* Zero order release kinetics, First order release kinetics and Higuchi model kinetics was fitted on the drug release data to get further insight on the drug release behaviour. The study suggests that P84 pluronic micelles can be used as nano drug carrier due to its high loading capacity

and stable formulation even after 3 months. Thus, the present findings can prove useful in delivering such type of polar hydrophobic drugs in the different pluronic micelles as optimum size of the corona facilitates the solubilization of the polar hydrophobic drugs.

Chapter 4: Sodium Deoxycholate Mediated Enhanced Solubilization and Stability of Hydrophobic Drug Clozapine in Pluronic Micelles

This chapter aims to enhance the solubilization efficiency of pluronic micelles by preparing the mixed micelles of pluronics *viz.* P84 (PEO₁₉-PPO₄₃-PEO₁₉), F127 (PEO₁₀₀-PPO₆₅-PEO₁₀₀) and F108 (PEO₁₃₃-PPO₅₀-PEO₁₃₃) and bile salts, sodium deoxycholate (SDC). For this purpose, clozapine (CLZ) was chosen as a model hydrophobic drug which is an atypical antipsychotic with unparalleled efficacy against refractory schizophrenia. A number of serious risks are associated with CLZ many of which are potentially fatal *viz.* agranulocytosis, seizures, myocarditis and increased mortality in elderly patients, which limits its clinical use. Therefore to improve the patient compliance for CLZ, optimization of formulation for CLZ is important for drug delivery. UV-visible spectroscopy was employed to observe the solubilization capacity of the investigated micellar systems (pluronic + SDC) in terms of drug loading efficiency, average number of drug molecules solubilized per micelle (n_s), partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°). The results demonstrated that mixed micellar formulations of pluronics with SDC were able to solubilize significantly higher amounts of drug as compared to pure pluronic micelles. The increase in solubility of CLZ in the pluronic-SDC was due to the alterations in the micro-environment of these micelles, we expected that the SDC molecules dehydrate the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles and also induces negative charge on these mixed micelles, which is responsible for the electrostatic repulsion between the micelles. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) and small angle neutron scattering (SANS) measurements confirmed the formation of mixed micelle of pluronic with SDC and solubilization of CLZ in the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles. Besides, the mixed micellar formulations comprising P84 and SDC showed marked stability against precipitation.

SANS results described that upon solubilization of CLZ drug in pluronic micelles, an increase in the core radius (R_c) as well as hard sphere radius (R_{HS}) of

pluronic micelle was observed which confirms the fact that CLZ has been solubilized in the pluronic micelles. As obtained from UV-visible results, pluronic-SDC mixed micelles show improved solubilization and stability of CLZ drug in pluronic P84-SDC mixed micelles. So we firstly characterize the P84-SDC mixed micelles by SANS measurements. It reveals that as the concentration of SDC is increased, the scattering intensity decreased at low Q values followed by gradual increase in scattering at high Q region. Also, it was observed that the scattering cross section decreases and peak position shifts towards higher Q region. The values of core radius and hardsphere radius decreased significantly with the addition of SDC until 40 mM. However, beyond 40 mM, the addition of SDC witnesses a decrease in hard sphere radius at a higher rate as compared to core radius. The decrease in core radius as well as hard sphere radius clearly indicates the formation of smaller P84-SDC mixed micelles. Effective packing of the hydrophobic part of the SDC in the micellar core decreases the size of the core radius and due to the hydrophobic interactions, water from the core is expelled out into corona results in dehydration of core. Comparison of SANS results of solubilization of CLZ in pure pluronic micelles with the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles shows improved aggregation behaviour has improved in the pluronic-SDC mixed micelles. This is the main reason of greater solubility of CLZ in pluronic-SDC mixed micelles.

Micropolarity measurements have been performed to adjudge the locus of solubilization of CLZ in these micelles. The results from micropolarity measurements indicated that CLZ experiences better hydrophobic environment in pluronic-SDC mixed micelles as compare to pure pluronic micelles. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) confirmed that there is good compatibility between CLZ and components of formulation. The results indicated that pluronic P84-SDC mixed micellar system is better for CLZ solubilization than other two investigated pluronic (F127 and F108)-SDC mixed micellar systems. Since a good drug carrier must possess long term stability and should be resistant to subsequent dilutions. Therefore, CLZ loaded P84-SDC mixed micelles were further tested for long term stability and effect of dilution. The results of long term stability evidenced that CLZ loaded P84-SDC mixed micellar formulations remained stable for 3 months at 25°C. During the course of dilution study, it was revealed that upon dilution of

formulation to 30 folds, CLZ loaded P84-SDC mixed micelles get converted into CLZ loaded pure P84 micelles. On further diluting the formulation even up to 480 times, the hydrodynamic size remained stable and no drug precipitation occurred. Thus, the results obtained from the present study can facilitate the optimization of concentration of bile salts that stabilized the formulation but did not interfere with the polymeric micelles when they enter the body.

Chapter 5: Mixed Micelles of Pluronic-Surface Active Ionic Liquids (SAILs) as Efficient Hydrophobic Quercetin Drug Carriers

In this chapter, we investigated the potential of pluronic-surface active ionic liquids (SAILs) mixed micelles for solubilization of hydrophobic drug quercetin (QCT). The investigated SAILs have similar dodecyl chain length and different headgroups viz. imidazolium (Mim), piperidinium (Pip) and pyrrolidinium (Pyr). The solubility as well as loading efficiency of pluronic F108-SAILs mixed micelles was observed to be significantly higher as compared to individual F108 and SAILs micelles. In addition, we observed that the composition of mixed micelles has a profound effect on solubilization capacity as maximum solubility was observed at equimolar concentration ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$). Amongst all investigated F108-SAILs mixed micelles, F108-Mim mixed micelles showed higher solubilization capacity which is ascribed to presence of the π - π interactions between the π -electron system of imidazolium ring of Mim and QCT. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements showed an increment in size of mixed micelles after QCT loading which in turn also indicates the solubilization of QCT in mixed micelles. Differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) measurements revealed that binding of QCT with F108-Mim mixed micelles was relatively stronger than other investigated F108-SAILs. QCT shows anodic peak at oxidation potential (E_p)= 0.280 V corresponding to oxidation of 3'-OH and 4'-OH groups on the B-ring of QCT. The oxidation of QCT is $2e^-$ and $2H^+$ transfer process. Upon the first addition of the pluronic solution (where F108 is in form of monomers) the oxidant peak of QCT moves towards a higher potential (0.284 V) with decreased peak current (-2.35 μ A). However with further increase of F108, no longer change in potential of QCT was observed which implies that the environment of QCT does not change and it gets solubilized in micelles.

This is further confirmed from the fact that saturation occurs near *cmc* value. On the other hand in SAILs, upon addition of Mim micelles, the oxidation peak of QCT moves towards lower potential and then to higher potential with decreased current. These results revealed that when SAIL is in form of monomers the interaction of the A-ring of QCT become dominant with SAILs that exposes the B-ring and facilitates the oxidation of B-ring. However, as the concentration of SAILs is increased, B-ring of QCT also interacts with the SAILs micelles because more SAILs molecules are available to interact with both of rings. In case of F108-Mim ($\alpha_{F108}=0.5$) mixed micelles, the potential first decreases and then increases to certain value followed by a plateau at a potential value of 0.292 V. Similar type of behaviour have been observed in case of other two mixed micellar systems i.e. F108-Pip and F108-Pyr. These results indicate that interaction of SAILs and F108 both play an important role in the solubilization of QCT. When both SAILs and F108 are in form of monomers, a decrease in potential of QCT is due to interaction of A-ring of QCT with SAILs because interaction of SAILs is predominant than F108. The higher availability of SAILs and F108 leads to interaction of B-ring of QCT becoming predominant in the solubilization of QCT and hence the potential of QCT become harder.

In vitro drug release study evidenced that interactions of the QCT with head group of SAILs have a great impact on their drug release behaviour. The presence of stronger cation- π interactions as well as π - π interactions between QCT and Mim is responsible for slower release than other two investigated SAILs systems (Pip and Pyr). The results demonstrated that composition of mixed micelles had a profound effect on solubilization capacity and the drug release behaviour from F108-SAILs mixed micelles can be easily tuned by changing the head group of SAILs. Moreover, higher cytotoxicity was observed in the case of micellar QCT than free QCT confers the anticancer efficiency of the formulations. From these results we concluded that pluronic F108-Mim mixed micellar system are proved to be better drug delivery vehicles for QCT than pure pluronic micelles and among investigated pluronic F108-SAILs (F108-Pip and F108-Pyr) mixed micellar system.

Chapter 6: Temperature Dependent Solubilization of Hydrophobic Antiepileptic Drug Lamotrigine in Different Pluronic Micelles

This chapter deals with the solubilization of hydrophobic antiepileptic drug lamotrigine (LAM) in five different pluronic micelles *viz.* P84 (PEO₁₉PPO₄₃PEO₁₉), P85 (PEO₂₆PPO₄₀PEO₂₆), F127 (PEO₁₀₀PPO₆₅PEO₁₀₀), F108 (PEO₁₃₃PPO₅₀PEO₁₃₃) and F68 (PEO₇₇PPO₂₉PEO₇₇) with 40, 50, 70, 80 and 80 % PEO content respectively at three different temperatures (37°C, 47°C and 57°C) using UV-visible spectroscopy. It was observed that upon increasing the temperature, the solubilization in all pluronics was also enhanced, this was ascribed to the increase in area for solubilization of LAM in pluronic micelles due to the thermal agitation, besides the fact that LAM solubility in water also increases with increase in temperature. The impact of temperature on the amount of drug loading also depends on whether drug molecules solubilized inside in PEO forming hydrophilic corona or a PPO forming hydrophobic core region of pluronic micelles. The solubility of drugs increased with increase in temperature if most of drug molecules solubilized in core forming PPO blocks of the micelles and decreased if drug solubilized in the PEO corona region. The dehydration of PEO region upon increasing the temperature leads to a decrease in the solubilizing area available for the drug. The micellar growth of pluronic micelles obtained as a result of increased temperature is the driving force for solubilization of hydrophobic drugs that especially prefer the core region of micelles. In present case, solubility was increased in all pluronic micelles with increase in temperature and therefore it can be concluded that most of LAM drug has been solubilized in the core region of micelles. This micellar growth has been confirmed by the SANS measurements. Different solubilization parameters such as the drug loading capacity, partition coefficient (P) and standard free energy of solubilization (ΔG°) were also determined. Among all the investigated pluronics, P84 has the best solubilization capacity in the temperature range 37°C-57°C. Furthermore, the effect of temperature and LAM solubilization in the investigated different pluronic micelles has been adjudged by indigenously built small angle neutron scattering (SANS) and the Heat Transfer Method (HTM). This is first report in which HTM measurements are established for the analysis of morphological changes in the thermo-responsive pluronic micelles in real time manner. SANS experiments revealed that

pluronic P84 micelles converted in prolate ellipsoidal micelles from spherical micelles at 57°C. This was confirmed by dynamic light scattering (DLS) and HTM measurements and was due to higher hydrophobicity of P84 compared to other investigated pluronics. SANS results showed increase in aggregation number with increase in temperature in case of hydrophobic pluronic P84 and act as driving force for morphological changes in the micelles. HTM results exhibited that the conversion of spherical micelles to prolate ellipsoidal micelles starts at 55°C and ends at 58°C. Instead, hydrophilic pluronic F127 does not show any significant change in the R_{th} (resistance in heat transfer) value confirming that no morphological changes occur as a function of temperature. *In vitro* drug release revealed that release behaviour of LAM can be modulated by simply changing the temperature for preparation of pluronic micelle formulation. The rate of controlled release of LAM from five different pluronic micelles was accessed by using different kinetic models to evaluate the *in vitro* drug release profile. The present work corroborate that how we can control the drug loading capacity, morphological structure of drug carrier as well as drug release by simply changing the temperature of pluronic micellar media. Therefore, this work opens many new areas to modulate the drug loading capacity of the hydrophobic drug in the different pluronic micelles by varying the temperature and drug release behaviour.

Chapter 7: Solubilization of Hydrophobic Drugs Clozapine and Oxcarbazepine in the Lower and Higher Molecular Weight Pluronic Mixed Micelles

In this chapter, we hereby report the solubilization behaviour of clozapine (CLZ) and oxcarbazepine (OXC) in binary mixtures of low molecular weight pluronics *viz.* L64 (PEO₁₃PPO₃₀PEO₁₃) and L35 (PEO₁₁PPO₁₆PEO₁₁) with relatively high molecular weight pluronics *viz.* P84 (PEO₁₉PPO₄₃PEO₁₉), F127 (PEO₁₀₀PPO₆₅PEO₁₀₀), F68 (PEO₇₇PPO₂₉PEO₇₇) and P123 (PEO₂₀PPO₇₀PEO₂₀) by use of UV-visible measurements. The drug solubility, drug loading efficiency, the micelle-water partition coefficient (P), and Gibbs free energy (ΔG°) were measured. From the obtained results, it was concluded that the highest solubility of CLZ was observed in binary mixture of L64/P84 (1:4) due to the hydrophobic nature of P84 and L64. In case of OXC, the highest solubility was observed in L64/F127 (1:4) because the drug solubilized both in the core and the corona region of F127 since OXC contains a carboxamide polar

moiety. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements have been used to determine the hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) of the loaded and unloaded pluronic mixed micelles. From DLS measurements, it was observed that there was an increase in the size of mixed micelles from empty mixed micelles to drug (CLZ and OXC) loaded mixed micelles. Further fluorescence spectroscopy indicated that the *cmc* decreased with the formation of mixed micelles as compared to pure individual micelles. *In vitro* drug release studies of the best solubilized formulation of binary mixed micellar systems containing CLZ were performed to determine the drug release behaviour of the drug from the mixed micellar systems. *In vitro* release study of CLZ showed that as the amount of P84 in the binary mixtures of L64/P84 and L35/P84 decreases, the release become faster. Therefore, it is possible to control the drug release from the pluronic micelles by simply varying the concentration of one pluronic. Antioxidant activity of different formulations was determined by various antioxidant assays such as 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl free radical (DPPH•) scavenging assay, total reducing ability determination by the Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} transformation method (reducing power activity), metal chelating activity and the scavenging assay of nitric oxide (NO). The results evidenced that pluronic formulations showed significantly higher antioxidant activity than bare CLZ and OXC drugs. It is anticipated that the formulations L64/P84(1:4)/CLZ and L64/F127(1:4)/OXC may act as the efficient drug carriers for the drug delivery of CLZ and OXC respectively.

List of Publications

Publications from the present work:

1. A systematic physicochemical investigation on solubilization and *in vitro* release of poorly water soluble oxcarbazepine drug in pluronic micelles, **P. Singla**, S. Chabba, R. K. Mahajan, *Colloids Surf. A* **2016**, *504*, 479-488.
2. Sodium deoxycholate mediated enhanced solubilization and stability of hydrophobic drug clozapine in pluronic micelles, **P. Singla**, O. Singh, S. Chabba, V. K. Aswal, R. K. Mahajan, *Spectrochimica Acta A* **2018**, *191*, 143-154.
3. Pluronic-SAILs (surface active ionic liquids) mixed micelles as efficient hydrophobic QCT drug carriers, **P. Singla**, O. Singh, S. Chabba, R. K. Mahajan, *Journal of Molecular Liquids* **2018**, *249*, 294-303.
4. Temperature dependent solubilization of the hydrophobic antiepileptic drug lamotrigine in different pluronic micelles-A spectroscopic, heat transfer method, small-angle neutron scattering, dynamic light scattering, and *in vitro* release study, **P. Singla**, O. Singh, S. Sharma, K. Betlem, V. K. Aswal, M. Peeters, R. K. Mahajan, *ACS Omega* **2019**, *4*, 11251-11262.
5. Solubilization of hydrophobic drugs oxcarbazepine and clozapine in the binary mixtures of lower and higher molecular weight pluronic micelles-A physicochemical, *in vitro* release and *in vitro* anti-oxidant study, **P. Singla**, S. Garg, R. Bhatti, M. Peeters, O. Singh, R. K. Mahajan (Communicated to *Journal of Molecular Liquid*, Manuscript number MOLLIQ_2019_4308).

Other Publications:

6. Tailoring the interfacial and bulk behavior of ionic-liquids with non surface active drug diclofenac sodium, O. Singh, **P. Singla**, R. Kaur, R. K. Mahajan, *Colloids Surf. A* **2017**, *523*, 43-53.

7. Aggregation and morphological aptitude of drug based ionic liquids in aqueous solutions, O. Singh, **P. Singla**, V. K. Aswal, R. K. Mahajan, *ACS Omega* **2017**, 2, 3296-3307.
8. Colloidal and interfacial attitude of aromatic anions based ionic liquids in aqueous solutions, O. Singh, **P. Singla**, R. K. Mahajan (*Under revision in Langmuir*, Manuscript ID: la-2018-035405).
9. A novel application of the heat-transfer method (HTM): real-time monitoring of staphylococcus aureus growth in buffered solutions and digestate samples, K. Betlem, A. Kaur, A. Hudson, R. Crapnell, G. Hurst, **P. Singla**, M. Zubko, S. Tedesco, C. Banks, K. A. Whitehead, M. Peeters (Revision submitted-ACS Applied biomaterials).

Conferences Attended

1. **Poster presentation** in National Symposium on Advances in Chemical Sciences, GNDU, Amritsar on 2nd-3rd February, 2016.
2. **Attended Workshop** on Amphiphilic Molecules and Self-Assembly: Principles and Applications, Panjab University, Chandigarh on 22nd-28th March, 2016.
3. **Poster presentation** in International Conference on Harnessing Engineering, Technology and Innovation for Sustainable Growth, Panjab University, Chandigarh on 30th September-1st October 2016.
4. **Poster presentation** in Silver jubilee conference on Study of Matter Using Intense Radiation Sources and Under Extreme Conditions, DAVV University, Indore on 3rd-6th November, 2016.
5. **Poster presentation** in International conference on Recent Advances For Quality Enhancement In Science and Technology, Hans Raj Mahila Mahavidyalaya, Jalandhar on 16th-17th January, 2017.
6. **Poster presentation** in 20th C.R.S.I National & 11th RSC-CRSI Symposium in Chemistry, Guwahati university, Guwahati on 3rd-5th February, 2017.
7. **Poster presentation** in Symposium on Recent Trends in Chemical Sciences, GNDU, Amritsar on 27th January, 2017.
8. **Oral Presentation** in 6th National Symposium on Advances in Chemical Sciences, GNDU, Amritsar on 6th-7th March, 2017.
9. **Poster presentation** in Bioinspired Materials 2018 conference, Manchester Metropolitan University (MMU), Manchester, United kingdom (UK) on 10th October, 2018.
10. **Video Presentation** in World Drug Delivery and Novel Therapy summit, Toronto, Canada on 25th -26th, October, 2018.
11. **Oral and poster presentation** in International conference on Nanotechnology, Edinburgh, Scotland on 3rd -4th December, 2018.
12. **Poster Presentation** in Mercia Symposium, Manchester Metropolitan University (MMU), Manchester, United Kingdom (UK) On 12th December, 2018 (**First Poster Prize**).